

Vague Language in Nigerian Presidents' Speeches

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Abstract

The extent to which vague language is present in formal written discourse is the focus of this paper. The study compared the use of vague language in the speeches of four Nigerian presidents focusing on vague quantifiers and linguistic approximators as types of vague language and it investigated the functions and frequency of the items. Using the relevance theory framework and employing corpus linguistics methodologies through AntConc 3.5.8, the study analysed a corpus of 16 Nigerian presidential speeches from Presidents: Olusegun Obasanjo, Umaru Yar'Adua, Goodluck Jonathan and Muhammadu Buhari (from 1999 to date). The study examined the functions of the quantifying expressions and determined their frequency of use, on president-by-president basis in the corpus. The study found that vague quantifying expressions were used to make quantifications inexact and to convey a range of vague propositions as well as make statements that were general in nature rather than being specific.

Keywords: corpus, linguistics, presidential, speeches, vague

1. Introduction

Human existence is enhanced by interrelatedness with one another which involves communicating informally and formally to become “communicative competent” (Kreps, 1986, p. 5). This entails, amongst others: critical thinking and mindfulness, making reasoned choices, being able to codeswitch between different language styles depending on the situation, being culturally aware and sensitive, and communicating ethically (DeVito, 2017, pp. 18–21). All achieved through the human language. The human language is vital to human existence without which humans would not be humans. Despite the importance of language to humans, it is accused of inadequacy in its communicative function and found to be vague or inexplicit, most times. Though, vagueness in communication was seen as a deficiency, the deficiency view of language has since changed as vague language (VL) is now viewed as an inadvertent and a deliberate human communication characteristic deployed for different purposes (Parvaresh & Sheikhan, 2019). Commentators of vagueness stress that purposeful use of VL should not be censured but be encouraged because it is an “integral component” of the human language and communication (Channell, 1994, p. 5). Attention on vagueness has become subject of study in different aspects of human knowledge depending on the foci of scholars and forms “part of a detailed description of the pragmatics of a particular delimited area of language use” as against a general theory of language use (Channell, 1985a). Except in some rare occasions, every human culture and endeavour thrives on VL, intentionally or inadvertently, and VL has been of interest to man since human civilisation (Fisher, 2000).

The notion of VL as pejorative no longer holds as experience has shown that language use without vagueness is unattainable (Partridge, 1947, 1947, cited in Channell, 1994, p. 1). At the same time, the idea that vagueness makes human interaction unclear or that it is suitable for informal communication alone is no longer tenable (Cutting, 2019). VL is now viewed positively as an effective, deliberate, human interactional device as most of what was once assumed to be a

good form of language actually contained some aspects of VL (Stubbs, 1986). It is thus rare to see an aspect of human knowledge that does not contain VL (Li, 2017, 2019; McGee, 2018; O’Keeffe, 2004; Prince, et al., 1982; Quammie–Wallen, 2019; Ruzaitė, 2007; Samigoullina, 2020). Apart from inherently vague linguistic elements, humans will be vague as blunt expressions are inappropriate. VL helps humans make reference in a “non-specific, imprecise way” and is a central part of a native speaker’s “communicative competence” (Carter & McCarthy, 2006 cited Cutting, 2007, p. 6).

Despite the importance of VL to humans, however, defining it or what constitutes VL, itself is contentious. More so, the language examples touted as VL are most times all borderline cases. In addition, scholars who study vagueness do so differently because they (scholars) are from different fields of knowledge. Thus, looking at VL from the different perspectives, make commentators argue that VL is “a vague concept” with undefined boundaries (Adolphs, et al, 2007; Fraser, 2010). For the purpose of this study, we shall take our working definition from these criteria of vague language:

- a. it can be contrasted with a precise term;
- b. its vagueness is intrinsic; and
- c. it is purposely vague (Channell, 1994)

and categorise how VL can be achieved into:

- i) vague additives,
- ii) vague words,
- iii) vagueness by omission, and
- iv) vagueness by implicature (Channell, 1983, p. 51).

The extent to which humans deliberately use VL in their interactions to achieve communication goals is the focus of this study. The study argues that deliberately, humans, in this case the Nigerian presidents, use vague language to sell their policies and stands to their audience.

The study focuses on the following purposively sampled 15 quantifying expressions (quantifiers and approximators): *less than, the majority, little, almost, often, within, about, more than, several, (a) few, some, most, much (more), over* and *many* aspects of VL.

2. Importance of Vague Language in Human Interaction

VL is crucial to human interaction in many ways. It helps speakers in not imposing on their interlocutors. At the same time, VL leaves room for escape for speakers by not committing themselves; and serves as a sign of social and personal relaxation in interaction. Understanding the dynamics of VL serves as part of our socio-pragmatic norms and conventions and a crucial component of our communicative competence (Cucchi, 2007; Terraschke & Holmes, 2007). VL serves as a strategic discourse device that helps interlocutors prevent boredom; make communication flow; achieve inclusiveness (Li, 2019); as well as serves as a threat-minimizing strategy (Salager-Meyer, 1994). VL helps speakers talk about subjects they are very knowledgeable about or subjects they lack the necessary vocabulary (Channell, 1985b). It is also used as a tentative discourse strategy to make claims and an in-group membership marker used to shut out outsiders (Cutting, 2000, 2019). At the same time, VL enhances social and personal equality which must be encouraged in interactions so that foreign learners would understand

them. Whilst without VL in human interaction, communication becomes unintelligent, inappropriate, “blunt and pedantic” (McCarthy & Carter, 2004).

2.1 Vague Quantifiers and Approximators

The vague quantification expressions covered in this study are from the English non-numerical quantifiers (here classified as vague quantifiers) and linguistic approximators (here described simply as approximators). Natural languages quantify. Whilst English portrays quantification through determiners and noun phrases, other languages do so differently (Peters & Westerstahl, 2006, p. 11). The English quantification words come under quantifiers. They include words such as: *some, no, both, (a) few, (a) little, several, enough, many, most, each, every, and all*. They are part of the noun phrase and modify nouns to provide countability in terms of quantities, degree and amounts in sentences. They are subcategorised as determiners that quantify both countable and uncountable nouns. Broekhuis, *et. al.* (2012), compare them with cardinal numerals because they “indicate the size or the cardinality of intersection” but say they differ as they are imprecise (p. 895). In Dutch, because of their indeterminacy, they are taken as “indefinite cardinal numerals”; and “indefinite pronouns” (p. 896). This helps drive home the point that quantifiers are vague elements that do not make explicit their quantifications. They are generality terms in philosophy (Glanzberg, 2009) due to their inexplicitness. Unlike formal languages that abhor vagueness and imprecision, natural languages thrive in them because of their imprecision.

Quirk & Greenbaum (1987) take quantifiers as members of two small groups of closed-system: those that co-occur only with plural count nouns: *many, (a) few, and several*; and those that co-occur only with non-count nouns: *much* and *(a) little* (p. 64). In traditional grammar, quantifiers function as *pronominal* (they occur alone or form part of the prepositional phrase with *of*) “some (of the men)” and as *adjectival* that precede nouns, “some men” (Jackendoff, 1968).

Here are some examples of quantifiers from our corpus:

- i) Some of their successors behaved like spoilt children breaking everything and bringing disorder to the house (President Buhari, Inaugural speech, May 29, 2015).
- ii) ... the past few years have witnessed growth in some aspects of South-South cooperation. (President Obasanjo, Independence Day speech, 1 October 2002).
- iii) In Nigeria, the threat of terrorism in a few States in the North Eastern part of our country (President Jonathan, UN General Assembly, 24 September 2013).
- iv) We acknowledge that our elections had some shortcomings (President Yar'adua, Inaugural speech, 29 May 2007).

At the same time, we have instances where quantifiers are used without *of* (that is they function as *adjectival*) in our corpus:

- v) Nigeria will continue to partner with the WHO and some countries to ensure accelerated development and manufacturing... (President Buhari, Address to the 75th Session of the United Nations General Assembly. 22 September, 2020)
- vi) These changes were bound to cause some anxiety among various sections of our

national community (President Obasanjo, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2002).

- vii) Unfortunately, despite the free, fair and transparent manner the elections were conducted, a senseless wave of violence in some parts of the country ... (President Jonathan, Inaugural speech, 29 May, 2011)

Approximators are part of linguistic hedging elements used to shield attention or beam the spotlight in discourse. They come with different headings in academic discourse because of their diverse functions in human interaction (Mihatsch, 2010, p. 93). According to Lakoff (1972), hedgings “make things fuzzier”. To Caffi (1999), hedgings fall under *mitigation* elements synonymous with *attenuation*, which “is the result of a weakening of one of the interactional parameters, and a downgrading when the parameters involved are scalar”. Fraser (1980) adds that *mitigation* is not a type of speech act rather it reduces some unwelcome effects speech acts might have on the hearer.

To Fraser, hedgings are not in any exclusive class of words but are from different word classes. It is thus not surprising that some approximators are also part of quantifiers. Prince, *et al.* (1982) classify approximators as hedging devices into: adaptors (with examples from our corpus as: *almost*, *some*, and *little*) whose function is to “apply to class membership and contribute to the interpretation of the utterance”, and rounders (with examples from our corpus as: *about*, and *around*) that “indicate a range, within which a notion is approximated” (Gribanova & Gaidukova, 2019). The general function of approximators in discourse is to semantically modify a discursual proposition (Mihatsch, p. 94). Approximators make guess and make communication flow easier, as the precise quantification is not important since the essence of the information in the interaction can be understood without the exact details. In the view of Channell (1985b), approximators “are understood by hearers as designating a continuous sequence of numbers (=INTERVAL) which contains the exemplar number”.

From another angle, linguistic hedgings are viewed as a “discourse strategy that reduces the force or truth of an utterance and thus reduces the risk a speaker runs when uttering a strong or firm assertion or other speech act” (Kaltenböck, *et. al.*, 2010, p. 1). This is very common in scientific reporting, as scientists (speakers) are expected to present their claims and themselves, humbly. This means it is not in all cases that approximators act as vague elements. Some approximators “are indeed used when exact figures are irrelevant or unavailable or when the state of knowledge does not allow” (Salager-Meyer, 1994) the speaker to be more exact. Thus, if a speaker does not know the exact information and they used an approximator, this is not to be taken as vague but because the exact information is not within reach or unknown. The bottom line is that approximators could make the speaker’s claim vague and tentative thus presenting the claims made by the speaker to be acceptable thereby reducing the chances of face-threats (Fand, 1989).

Let us take a look at some examples in our corpus to prove these claims:

- 1) With the railways, we plan to concession some existing routes including the Western and Eastern rail lines ... (President Yar’Adua, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2008)

- 2) I am pleased to report that the yielded results include an increase in our proven reserves from about 25 to almost 32 billion barrels of oil (President Obasanjo, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2002).

We would see that in (1), it would be a wasted effort for President Yar'Adua naming the "existing routes" that would be concessioned as everyone familiar with the Nigerian railway, who the president is addressing, knows the routes in question.

In (2), we would see that President Obasanjo did not mention the exact amount. In the first instance, he gave a rough estimate of the reserve; *from about 25*. That amount could be 24.1 to 25.4 billion barrels. Then he gives another estimate, which could be from a little above 31 to something above 32 billion barrels of oil. We can see here that President Obasanjo realises that giving an exact figure would not be ideal as he might not have that and if he gives one that was not correct, there would be a face-threat as he could be accused of under or over reporting the true situation of the Nigerian oil reserves. To counter this, the President uses vague quantifying expressions which put everyone's mind at ease. He uses the two approximators, *about*, and *almost* to "express some degree of qualification or uncertainty". With this, we would see that linguistic hedging are discourse elements of "protection and defence" (Wibowo & Yusoff, 2014), to propositions.

From the grammatical perspective, Quirk et al. (1985, p. 597), take approximators as a subcategory of the intensifiers, from the downtoners sub-category. As downtoners, approximators have a lowering effect on the force of the verb or a predication and many of them apply a scale to gradable verbs. It is in this light of lowering the effects of the verb, that scholars take approximators as mitigation discourse elements. Quirk, et al. go on to say that: "approximators serve to express an *approximation* to the force of the verb, while indicating that the verb concerned expresses more than is relevant". According to Prince, et al., one of the options available to the speaker in the use of an approximation is to "... use the closest relevant term but indicate in some way that perceived reality is not prototypical with respect to that term". They (speakers) thus choose a term that would suit the object of discourse.

In discourse, Channell (1994, p. 42) claims that "speakers have the option of either adding something to a precise number or numbers, or using a round number, or using a vague quantifier". This means both quantifiers and approximators are vague linguistic elements that make things "fuzzy or less fuzzy".

Some of the VL usage found in the corpus of four Nigerian presidents include:

1. The difference will be that in the past sacrifices were made and patience exercised with little or no results (President Obasanjo, Inaugural speech, 29 May, 1999).
2. ... the Governor of Plateau State has travelled out of the country more than four times without bothering to notify me (President Obasanjo, Declaration of Emergency Rule in Plateau State, 18 May, 2004).
3. ... a terrifying force taking tens of thousands of lives and capturing several towns and villages covering swathes of Nigerian sovereign territory (President Muhammadu Buhari, Inaugural speech, 29 May, 2015).

4. ... our determined efforts on several fronts notwithstanding, our country still faces a number of challenges (President Jonathan, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2012).
5. ... Nigerians, our economy is on a strong footing with an average growth rate of about 6.9%, a single digit inflation rate, external reserves of about 63 billion dollars ... (President Yar'Adua, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2008)
6. A few people have privately voiced fears that on coming back to office I shall go after them (President Buhari, Inaugural speech, 29 May, 2015).
7. I had the benefit of a university education myself, and without doubt, it has been responsible for much of my personal success (President Yar'Adua, UN General Assembly speech, 24 September, 2009).
8. ... we affirm that much more needs to be done (President Yar'Adua, Address to the 62nd Session of the General Assembly of the United Nations, 18 September, 2007).
9. Apart from the First Lady of Africa, my dear Turai, women are dispensable, and are worth far less than all the trouble they manufacture (President Yar'Adua, 64th General Assembly of the UN address, 27 September, 2009).
10. We have made remarkable progress in almost all segments of the agriculture value chain... (President Buhari, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2019)

3. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of the study is the relevance theory, which is a pragmatic cognitive linguistic theory, by Sperber & Wilson (1986). The relevance theory criticises "one of Grice's central claims: that an essential feature of most human communication is the expression and recognition of intentions" (Wilson & Sperber, 2006, p. 607). The bottom line of the relevance theory is that "the expectations of relevance raised by an utterance are precise and predictable enough to guide the hearer toward the speaker's meaning" (p. 607) which goes against the Grice's Cooperative Principle. We must understand that Grice never meant the maxims as guidelines to be observed (Nunn, 2006).

The basis of the theory is that the understanding and interpretation of utterances is predicated on the contextual background information available to the receiver(s). To understand this is to compare the theory to the code model of human communication. In the *code model* of communication, a person who has a message *encodes* it into a *signal (code)* for the receiver who in turn *decodes (interprets)* the initial signal of the sender, through "an identical copy of the code". This means the sender's and the receiver's signal must match for communication to take place. The inferential approach to pragmatics under which the relevance theory comes holds that the linguistic meaning of words decoded by the receiver is just one of many inputs and not the sole one that can affect interpretation. It stresses that a signal or input from the sender is important to the receiver because of the relevance of such input to the receiver. From the point of view of the theory, "other things being equal, the greater the positive cognitive effects achieved by processing an input, the greater its relevance will be" (p. 609). Thus, when the communication intent of the sender reaches the receiver, the receiver sieves through it to see which of the intents is relevant to them. To Sperber & Wilson (1995, p. 124), therefore, "relevance" is a "a comparative concept" as the receiver compares efforts.

The comparative concept which is predicated on the cognitive background on which the inferential communication is foregrounded is brought about by the processing effort of an input as compared to others. In this, there is a cost/benefit analysis brought to bear as humans consider

the cost of processing versus the conceivable positive cognitive benefits. The theory therefore concludes that in talking about relevance, there are two principles that must be borne in mind: the first relate to cognition and the other to communication. Sperber & Wilson propose that:

- (1) Human cognition tends to be geared to the maximisation of relevance.
- (2) Every act of ostensive communication communicates a presumption of its own optimal relevance (1995, p. 260).

Humans do not only take in information that comes their way during the communication process, they also use context of the inferences to arrive at what the speaker says which helps them arrive at the meaning. This is subsumed under the communicative principle of relevance as “every ostensive stimulus conveys a presumption of its own optimal relevance” (p. 612). Elsewhere, they stress that *relevance* is a matter of degree and that inference is context determined (1995, p. 123) as “... an input (a sight, a sound, an utterance, a memory) is relevant to an individual when it connects with background information he has available to yield conclusions that matter to him” (2006, p. 608). A servant of a wicked ruler, for example, could give a wink to someone who the servant knows does not know how horrible his master is to warn the person because it is not in the servant’s capacity to say anything in that circumstance. The input, the wink, is relevant to the receiver based on human knowledge to warn such a person that there is need for them to be careful. When the average Nigerian hears their presidents make these speeches, they do not rely on the words of the presidents alone, but rely on their background knowledge, the use of vague language, to know that the use of the quantifying expressions do not make the speeches a falsehood but rather that their presidents do not totally commit to the truth value of the statement as they have given escape routes in the speech. In the following:

- (3) “Infrastructure - Water Supply, Energy, Telecommunication, Ports, Airways, National Shipping, Nigerian Railways, etc.” (President Olusegun Obasanjo, Inaugural speech, May 29, 1999)

President Obasanjo could have gone ahead to list further examples of the infrastructure he was talking about but because he did not want to bore his audience and make his speech monotonous, he has used a vague linguistic device, etc. to tell the audience that he could go on but with the little he has mentioned, the audience should have in the mind the picture he was trying to paint. The audience, on the other hand, do not need to bother with other examples of the infrastructure the President had in mind as they and the president both have a common background knowledge of the Nigerian situation.

4. Methodology

The study built a specialised corpus of 16 speeches of the four Nigerian presidents. Olusegun Obasanjo (29 May 1999 and 29 May 2007). Umaru Musa Yar’Adua (29 May 2007 to 9 February 2010), Goodluck Jonathan (6 May 2010 and 29 May 2015) and Muhammadu Buhari (29 May 2015 to Date). For representativeness, each president has four speeches: their inaugural speech as president; an Independent Day (October 1) speech delivered during their tenure as presidents; an address to the UN and any other speech. The study considered 15 quantifying expressions, that were purposively selected: *less than, the majority, little, almost, often, within, about, more*

than, several, (a) few, some, most, much (more), over and many. The study employed the broader concept of corpus linguistics that applies to different aspects of linguistic enquiry (Koteyko, 2006). To be considered in the study, a quantifying element must have at least, one instance of use by two presidents. All the speeches were downloaded from the HTML/PDF/Word formats then converted to the plain text format for (Anthony, 2019) *AntConc* (Version 3.5.8) *concordancer* to process them. The concordancer identified the sub-categorisations of the quantificational expressions under focus. The percentage of the use of the items is then determined for comparison on president-by-president. For ease of identification, the president's name, the occasion and the date the speech served as metadata.

5. Results/Findings

The 15 vague quantifying expressions were used 194 times by the four Nigerian presidents. This is presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Vague Language in Nigerian Presidents' Speeches

quantifiers	Buhari	Jonathan	Obasanjo	Yar'Adua	TOT	% VAL
less than	1	0	1	1	3	1.55%
the majority	2	1	1	0	4	2.06%
little	0	1	3	1	5	2.58%
almost	1	0	4	1	6	3.09%
often	1	0	6	0	7	3.61%
within	3	0	3	2	8	4.12%
about	1	1	5	2	9	4.64%
more than	0	5	4	0	9	4.64%
several	1	8	2	0	11	5.67%
(a) few	4	4	4	2	14	7.22%
some	4	2	5	6	17	8.76%
most	7	3	6	3	19	9.79%
much (more)	3	5	9	3	20	10.31%
over	4	9	7	2	22	11.34%
many	6	11	17	6	40	20.62%
TOTAL	38	50	77	29	194	100%
% of use on individual basis	19.59%	25.77%	39.69%	14.95%	100%	

There are three patterns of use of the items in the corpus. The lowest use of the items was used three to nine instances. Eight items are in this category (*less than, the majority, little, almost, often, within, about, and more than*). The next was 11 to 19 instances and four of the quantifying elements are in this category (*several, (a) few, some, and most*). The last covered those items used 20 instances and above: (*much (more), over, and many*).

Of the eight items in the group of three to nine usage, *about* and *more (than)* were used with nine instances. Only *about* of the two highest used items in the group was used by the four presidents: Buhari (1), Jonathan (1), Obasanjo (5) and Yar'Adua (1) with 4.64% usage of the corpus. *About* however, shared the 4.64% position with *more (than)* which was used by two presidents: Jonathan (5) and Obasanjo (4). *Within* was used next with eight instances by three of the presidents: Buhari (3), Obasanjo (3) and Yar'Adua (2) with 4.12% usage in the corpus. *Often* followed with 3.61% usage to *within* and used by Buhari (1) and Obasanjo (6) in their speeches. Buhari (1), Obasanjo (4) and Yar'Adua (1) used *almost* with a 3.09% of the corpus. *Little* was also used by: Jonathan (1), Obasanjo (3) and Yar'Adua (1). The five instances of usage by the three presidents gave the item a 2.58% of the corpus. With a 2.06% of use *the majority* was used by Buhari (2), Jonathan (1), and Obasanjo (1). *Less than* was used on three occasions by Buhari (1), Obasanjo (1) and Yar'Adua (1) with a 1.55%.

The 11 to 19 instances of usage had four items: *several*, *(a) few*, *some*, and *most* form the next group of items in the 15 quantifying expressions used in the Nigerian presidents' speeches corpus. It is important to note that only *several* of the four items in the group was not used by the four Nigerian presidents. The other three items, *(a) few*, *some*, and *most* were used by the four Nigerian presidents. Of the four items in this group, *several*, and *(a) few* were used 11 and 14 instances respectively. The 11 instances, Buhari (1), Jonathan (8), and Obasanjo (2) gave the item 5.67% of the corpus. With 7.22% of use by the Nigerian presidents, *(a) few* was used 14 times by Buhari (4), Jonathan (4), Obasanjo (4), and Yar'Adua (2). *Some* was used 17 instances: Buhari (4), Jonathan (2), Obasanjo (5), and Yar'Adua (6) with an 8.76% of the corpus. The last item in this group, *most* was used 19 times by Buhari (7), Jonathan (3), Obasanjo (6), and Yar'Adua (3) with a 9.79% usage in the corpus.

Of the three items used 20 and above instances has *much (more)* (20), *over* (22), and *many* (40). With 20 instances *much (more)* was used by: Buhari (3), Jonathan (5), Obasanjo (9), and Yar'Adua (3) with 10.31% of the corpus. *Over* was used by: Buhari (4), Jonathan (9), Obasanjo (7) and Yar'Adua (2) which resulted in 11.34% of the corpus. The last item, *many*, was the most used: Buhari (6), Jonathan (11), Obasanjo (17), and Yar'Adua (6). With 40 instances it had 20.62% of the corpus.

The usage of the items is presented in fig. 1 below:

Fig 1: Usage of Vague Language in Nigerian Presidents' Speeches

6. Discussion of Findings

The 15 quantifying expressions (quantifiers and approximators) were used differently in the corpus. *Less than* had 3 instances of usage with 1.55% of the corpus. It was used by three of the four presidents, Buhari, Obasanjo and Yar'Adua who used it once, respectively. The next to *less than* is *the majority* that was used four times by three of the four Nigerian presidents also. Buhari used the item twice while Jonathan and Obasanjo used it once respectively. The item had 2.06% of the corpus.

With 2.58%, *little* had five instances of usage: Jonathan (1), Obasanjo (3), and Yar'Adua (1). *Almost* had six instances of use which gave it 3.09% of the corpus by: Buhari (1), Obasanjo (4), and Yar'Adua (1).

With 3.61%, *often* was used seven times by Buhari and Obasanjo who used it once and six times, respectively. *Within* is used eight times by, Buhari (3), Obasanjo (3), and Yar'Adua (2) with 4.12% in the 16-speech corpus. *About* was used nine times, Buhari (1), Jonathan (1), Obasanjo (5), and Yar'Adua (2), with a 4.64%.

With nine instances, Presidents Jonathan (5), and Obasanjo (4) used *more than* with 4.64%. Buhari (1), Jonathan (8), and Obasanjo (2) used *several* 11 times with 5.67% in the corpus. *(A) few* was used 14 times by: Buhari (4), Jonathan (4), Obasanjo (4), and Yar'Adua (2) with 7.22% of the corpus. *Some* was used 17 times: Buhari (4) Jonathan (2), Obasanjo (5), and Yar'Adua (6) that gave it 8.76% of the corpus. 9.79% was the result of *most* being used 19 times by: Buhari (7), Jonathan (3), Obasanjo (6), and Yar'Adua (3) in the corpus. *Much (more)* was used 20 times: Buhari (3), Jonathan (5), Obasanjo (9), and Yar'Adua (3) with 10.31% usage of the corpus. With 22 instances of use, Buhari (4), Jonathan (9), Obasanjo (7), and Yar'Adua (2), *over* had 11.34% of the corpus. *Many* is the most used of the 15 items. It was used 40 times: Buhari (6) Jonathan (11), Obasanjo (17), and Yar'Adua (6). The 40 times gave it 20.62% which is the highest of the 15 quantifying elements.

In proving whether the 15 quantifying items were general language rather than informal language specific elements in the corpus, the study agrees with Fraser's (2010, p. 3) opinion who stresses that though studies on hedges, an aspect of VL had been on casual spoken language, interest has expanded to embrace spoken, written formal and informal discourse. The study thus concludes that with the 194 instances in the corpus, the elements are general human language rather than informal-language specific elements.

On the statistical usage of the element on president-by-president basis, Yar'Adua uses 11 out of the 15 items (*less than* (1), *little* (1), *almost*(1), *within* (2), *about* (2), (*a few* (2), *some* (6), *most* (3), *much (more)* (3), *over* (2), and *many* (6)), 29 times (14.95%) which is the least used by the four Nigerian presidents of the 15 items. Jonathan also used 11 of the items (*the majority* (1), *little* (1), *about* (1), *more than* (5), *several* (8), (*a few* (4), *some* (2), *most* (3), *much (more)* (5), *over* (9) and *many* (11)) on 50 instances with 25.77% out of the 194 occasions that the items were used in the corpus. Buhari used 13 of the 15 items (*less than* (1), *the majority* (2), *almost* (1), *often* (1), *within* (3), *about* (1), *several* (1), (*a few* (4), *some* (4), *most* (7), *much (more)* (3), *over* (4), and *many* (6)), 38 times with 19.59% of the corpus. Obasanjo used the items the highest: *less than* (1), *the majority* (1), *little* (3), *almost* (4), *often* (6), *within* (3), *about* (5), *more than* (4), *several*(2), (*a few* (4), *some* (5), *most* (6), *much (more)* (9), *over* (7), and *many* (17) 77 times with 39.69% usage of the 194 instances the 15 quantifying items were used (see Fig. 2 for the individual usage of the quantifying items by the four Nigerian presidents).

Fig. 2: Usage of the Quantifying Elements by the Four Presidents

Commentators ascribe various functions in discourse to VL. One of the functions of vague quantifiers, an aspect of the quantification expression that this study covers is to make the quantification inexact. Here are some examples of use from our corpus:

- a) Our Rebrand Nigeria scheme is now in motion, and our Minister for Information, a very persuasive woman, will soon be coming to as many as 150 countries to tell you what a wonderful country Nigeria is (President Yar'Adua, 64th General Assembly of the UN, 29 September, 2009).
- b) With less than ten ratifications needed for the TPNW's entry into force ... (President Buhari, 75th Session of the United Nations General Assembly (22 September, 2020)

- c) We have a programme by which we expect to become self-sufficient in the production of cement - within four years ... (President Obasanjo, Independence Day speech, 1 October, 2002)
- d) Several government programmes and projects are creating wealth and millions of job opportunities for our youth and general population (President G E Jonathan, Independence Day Speech, 1 October, 2012).

In all the examples of *several*, *within*, *less than*, and *many*, at no time the expressions were used did the presidents mention the exact figure (quantity, amount). This points out that the elements were deliberately used so as not to disclose the exact amount (quantification) involved.

Another function of quantifying expressions is to convey a range of vague proportions (Moxey, 1986) rather than being specific. Here are examples from the corpus to illustrate this:

- e) ... I wish to thank God Almighty for the bountiful blessings he has continually bestowed on us as a people, in spite of the many challenges that we have had to face (President Yar'Adua, Independence Day Speech, 1 October, 2008).
- f) This is particularly important as the current pace of globalisation has made it extremely difficult for most developing countries ... (President Obasanjo, G-77 South Summit, 12 April, 2000).
- g) Over the years, several leaders have built on the foundation laid by our Founding Fathers (President Jonathan, Independence Day Speech, 1 October, 2012).
- h) Some of their successors behaved like spoilt children breaking everything and bringing disorder to the house (President Buhari, Inaugural speech, 29 May, 2015).

From the examples (e-h), we can see that the Nigerian presidents use the items to give rough estimations and none of them disclosed exactly the quantity they had in mind. Linguistic quantification elements are also used to make things general rather than specific. Just as in being inexact, the elements also make things general instead of being specific.

- i) With less than ten ratifications needed for the TPNW's entry into force, we urge other member states who have not done so to quickly ratify the Treaty for the actualization of its important objective (President Buhari, United Nations General Assembly, 22 September, 2020).
- j) As of now, the majority of Nigerians do not have direct access to this national cake (President Obasanjo, Independence Day Speech, 1 October, 2002).
- k) I am determined with your full cooperation, to make significant changes within a year of my administration (President Obasanjo, Inaugural address, 29 May, 1999).
- l) While applauding the successful outcome of the High Level Event on Climate Change, which was held here two days back, we affirm that much more needs to be done (President Yar'Adua, General Assembly of the United Nations, 18 September, 2007).

In the above examples, none of the presidents was specific in their speech. They all used generality instead of specificity.

7. Implications of the Study

The implication of this is that VL is a human interaction's device used in both formal and informal communication. The presidential speech is the most formal of any speech as it involves the image of not only the President presenting it but that of a country, at large. As much as possible, a President does not do this alone as they have presidential advisers and speech writers who work on their speeches with them. The advisers make sure the appropriate language, tone and register are used in the speeches. That the quantifying elements are found in the Nigerian presidential speeches further buttresses the fact that the elements are general human language elements. The presence of the elements in the presidential speeches also debunks the earlier held notion as exemplified by Carter & McCarthy (2006, p. 928) that "purposefully vague language is very common in informal spoken language". The "informal spoken language" notion does not hold as VL is found in the 16-speech corpus which is a written formal language. Thus, corroborating the "integral component" of the human language (Channell, 1994, p. 5), in general, irrespective of formal or informal, spoken or written or any particular language use or language situation.

8. Conclusion

We can see that the four Nigerian Presidents whose speeches were sampled in the study used the quantificational expressions (vague quantifiers and linguistic approximators) in different forms and for different purposes. Categorising the elements as spoken, informal speech elements used among familiars does not arise as shown in the study; as there is no formality than a nation's presidential address. If the argument comes up that the presidents used the elements because they could afford to be casual with their nationals; a counter argument would be, does this casual use by the Nigerian Presidents extend to the United Nations forum where all the four Presidents presented their speeches and the elements were present in their addresses to the UN. This proves that the vagueness in general and the VL in particular are human language specific elements. Humans are comfortable with vague quantifiers than with exact numbers as comprehensibility is easier and communication flows freely when they are used.

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Language Diversity and Globalization of Economies in the 21st Century: The Chinese and American Perspectives

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Abstract

The paper examines language diversity and globalization of economies focusing on two world economic giants, China and the USA which are used here as case studies because of their economic capacity and valency in global business. The USA is the largest economy and followed by China. Given that economic communication is facilitated through the use of language, the paper notes that it is the case that, without the understanding of the language of one's trading partner(s), it will be a little difficult to make a good economic deal. The paper uses historical and multidisciplinary methodological approach. It concludes that language diversity exists even among nations but economic/exchange relations can still function and they require nations to learn one another's language.

Keywords: globalisation, diversity, major, languages, nations

1. Introduction

It is known that of all the numerous human endowments, the ability and capacity to acquire and use language as a means of communication is the most important and very rewarding. Language is man's indispensable tool, with which his day to day activities are being carried on. Language through interaction with one another translates to communication. And communication through the use of language is one of the nuclei of development. In the words of Mac Bride as quoted in Akpan (2006)

Communication maintains life. It is also the motor and expression of social activities and civilization; it leads people and peoples from instinct to inspiration through various processes and systems of enquiry, command and centre; it creates a common pool of ideas, strengthens the feeling of togetherness through exchange of messages and translates thought in action, reflecting every emotion and need from the humblest tasks of human survival to supreme manifestations of creativity-or destruction. As the world has advanced, the tasks of communication has become ever more complex and subtle – to contribute to the liberation of mankind from want, oppression and fear and to unite it in community and communion, solidarity and understanding.

The above quotation means communication is a product of language in a different setting. Without the language and interaction, there would have been no communication. Different peoples the world over have their languages in which they use for interaction. This is the language diversity. Globalization of economics is the utilization of the products of different economies by peoples of different climes for their development and growth. Every country is

involved, there is no barrier. Every country must participate, give out something to another and take from others in return. These are facilitated through the use of language and by extension communication.

However, for the communication to really have value the different countries with their language need to be integrated. For instance large economies such as China and the United States of America and others that have a great deal to play in the global world market, their languages need to be studied and integrated for easy communication by the entrepreneurs. Some languages such as Chinese, Arabic, Japanese etc. are rather too complex, but they are leaders in production of goods and services to the global citizens, their languages become necessary to be studied and vice versa.

2. The Concept of Language and Language Diversity

Many other scholars have tried to conceptualize language from different perspectives. Robins (1985) defines language as “a symbol system based on pure or arbitrary conventions...infinitely extendable and modifiable according to the changing needs and conditions of the speakers.” According To Derbyshire (1967), “Language is undoubtedly a kind of means of communication among human beings. It consists primarily of vocal sounds. It is articulatory, systematic, symbolic and arbitrary”. This definition appears to be dealing with the characteristics of language. It is not intended to be so. Every language is unique and important to the people who use it as an important means of communication and of intellectual discourse, and for advancement of civilization. Language is an indispensable element that drives civilization, as it contributes to building and changing the socio-economic and political conditions of the people. Without language neither civilization nor socio-economic or political development would even have begun, let alone achieve the height it does today in any part of the globe (Akpan, 2013). The term “language”, and for the purpose of this paper, connotes people or group of people uses a particular language for expressing actions and inactions, intentions and demands for what they need at a given time or moment or the use of words that convey meanings to the intended expression and understood only by the users (Akpan, 2013).

3. Conceptualising Globalisation

Globalization is a buzz word that appears to have very many meanings as there are specialists in the subject. It would suffice to look at it as such, as Stiglitz (2002), sees globalization as the closer integration of the countries and peoples of the world which has been brought about by the enormous reduction of cost of transportation and communication, and the breaking down of artificial barriers to the flow of goods, services, capital, knowledge, and (to a lesser extent) people across borders. Kwanashie (1998), puts it that it is a process of integrating economic decision making such as the consumption, investment and saving process all across the world. it is also a process of creating global market place in which increasingly all nations are forced to participate. Ajegi (2005) explains globalization as a process which in all-embracing and includes human migration, trade in goods and services, movements of capital across national boundaries and integration of financial markets. It is a process that has even driven by the rapid development of communication, technological innovations as well as major changes in public policy and economic management. Globalization is a complete process developed by advanced industrial nations to frustrate the emerging economies from advancing to catch up with developed nations. It is a formula to perpetuate dependence and economic imperialism because of their advantaged position, a slow process of killing indigenous technology (Akpan, 2005).

4. Language Diversity and its Connotations within the International System

There are very many languages in the world as there are people speaking them. This is the application of language diversity. The people who use these various languages apply them in their day to day interaction either in business, or commerce, government business or for cultural entertainments etc. On other perspective, language diversity could also be seen as cultural acculturation by major dominant powers, nations mainly from Western Europe who ventured into other lands during the age of discovery and later colonization of the 18-20 centuries. These countries include Britain, France, Germany, Portugal, Spain, Denmark, Holland, Belgium etc. Today the languages from the colonial masters become the dominant languages or lingua franca in the colonized states-languages of diversity. Therefore, language diversity depends on the usage and applicability on the group. To the Americans, language diversity refers to the number of languages spoken in the United States and the number of people who speak them (Rumbaut & Massey, 2013). Perhaps this is applicable to other peoples the world over.

5. Language Diversity and Globalization of Economies

Historically, language diversity and globalization of economies are not really new phenomena as many people would want to see today. Major languages or international languages and their diversities are products of colonization. Different European powers such as Portugal, Spain, England, Holland, Denmark, France, Belgium, Italy etc. spilled over to other lands since the 15-20 centuries, initially for discovery and ultimately ended up in colonization. The colonized people had or still have their languages, but for the colonial masters to be relevant with the colonized people, they needed to force them to accept their languages. This was so because firstly, they were linked to international commerce and secondly for internal and external administration of the states colonized. The only way the colonial masters would derive the economics of scale was for them to force the indigenous people to adopt their language in education, business or commerce and for other aspects of social interactions. Thus, these become a dominant force for language diversity. Since the age of colonization till date those different colonial states adopt the language of their masters in business, education, social interaction, and behold a lingua franca for them. Although in some states indigenous languages are still being used, but in government business, the alien or colonial language is the parameter. For instance, in Nigeria it is the English language because we were colonized by the British whose language is English. Ivory Coast uses French because France colonized the Ivoirians. This is the latitude of language diversity irrespective of people and culture.

In the area of globalization of economies, historically globalization is not a new phenomenon after all. Globalization is a process of historical change rather than a specific condition. Since the discovery of West Indies by Christopher Columbus and his crew in 1492 and subsequent sailing around the world by Ferdinand Magellan before the end of the 15th century, the world was globalized. These early explorers were able to change their merchandise from Europe with the Chinese goods in the Far East merchandise from America were found in Europe and vice versa, Africa were able to exchange their ivory, gold, 'ostriched' feathers, hides and skin, and in turn accept textiles, spear, gun and gun power, and rum from Europeans across North Africa (Stride & Ifeka, O'Brien & Williams, 2011).

However, since globalization partly means to a large extent integration of world economy, it means there was integration of world economy even before the 20th century. So, what is being seen today as globalization is perhaps the second wave and facilitated with changes in

international system driven by improvement in science and technology. It is agreed historically that before the present time, there was science and technology that was the reason the early explorers were able to construct sailing ships, were able to invent compass, able to brew drinks, manufacture gun and gun power, by the time changes came since no nation is static, and man continues to improve as new knowledge also emerges or increases (Strike & Ifeka O'Brien & Williams, 2010).

Conversely, the first wave to global economic integration was possible and easy as a result of the introduction of their language by the colonial masters of the indigenous people or the subject people. Their language facilitated commerce because it was easy for the subject peoples to interact since they learnt the language of their masters. It means the language was the means of communication and communication enlarge the coast of commerce and absorption of the new culture.

It should be known that in the first wave of globalization the indigenous people who were integrated into the global market economy did not benefit much from that integration: firstly, the prices of their merchandise or goods and services were fixed by their masters; and most of their exports were primary products and the price were fixed by the same colonial masters, the finished products brought back, the prices were also fixed by them. Secondly, the subject people were literally new to the system, which is international trade and its challenges, hence were on the disadvantaged in nearly all perspectives. Of course the situation has not change much today and if there are changes they are merely cosmetic.

Towards the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century came the second wave of globalization of economies. This second wave is facilitate by the improvement in science and technology, again this improvement emerged from the colonial powers from western Europe, America and other advanced industrial economies. The phenomenon again is about economic integration. For the integration to be meaningful, globalization has to encompass many trends, such as expanded international trade, telecommunication monetary coordination, multinational corporations, technical and scientific cooperation, cultural exchanges of new types and scales, migration and refugees flows, and relations between the worlds' rich and poor nations (Goldstein Pevehouse, 2008).The central issue here is language and communication.

6. Language Diversity and Globalization of Economies in the 21st Century: The Chinese and Developing Economies Perspectives

China before the beginning of Cold War in 1945 was in a nebulous state because her economy would not support her large and increasing population. A large segment of Chinese population was poor with no Shelter and food. China was a poor country by all measures. She was being looked down by the Western nations of Europe that were ahead of her in the 1960s. However, she decided to close all 'doors' and protected herself against outsiders'. By outsiders, it meant she decided to develop her economy without heavy depended on other economies. The idea paid off and by the time she came out of the economic cocoon, things changed for her positively (O'Brien & Williams, 2010). Towards the close of the 20th century China bounced back and became a country to be reckoned with in many spheres of human development. It means Chinese economy altered and she became heavily industrialized, the subsistence she was known diminished. China became one of the World's industrial giants in car manufacture, textiles, household utensils, arms, printed materials, chemicals, building materials etc. Towards the turn

of this century her economy opened itself to the outside world especially the developing economies of Africa. For instance, Nigerian entrepreneurs flocked into China to participate in Chinese business by either buying or selling or directing the Chinese on the way out of producing goods that would suit Nigeria according to economic or spending capacity. The most important aspect of economic interaction is communication or the use of language. The business or partnership between Nigeria entrepreneurs Chinese counterparts would not grow well except they are able to relate adequately through the use of language. Perhaps, Chinese language is difficult to learn, so also is English language to many entrepreneurs. It has become necessary to learn each other's' language.

On another perspective, Chinese is an economic super power, the second largest economy next to the United States, she would not be able to benefit from the global market structure except she liberalize her economy and open her borders. That she did by joining the World Trade Organization. World Trade Organization is an international organization established in 1995 to replace General Agreement on Trade and Tariff that aimed to expand free-trade concession equally to all members; establishing freer global trade with fewer barriers; making trade more predictable through established rules etc. Chinese entry into WTO is highly advantages to them, firstly she is an enterprising economy and secondly she has a large population translating to mean large market. However, she cannot compete with other economic powers such as the USA, France, and Britain except she adopts her language. Global market today thrives through language diversification - in the process the relationship become a win-win-all.

Indeed, since China returned to the liberal economy and by being part of the World Trade Organization (WTO) much is expected from her globally. Without understanding of the menedain, it would be difficult to deal with them. In this connection, Chinese language becomes a sine qua non for her trading partners to learn and vice versa. Understanding international languages today is a plus to the development of economies, because globalization of economies means give and take, although some countries such as those in Africa and some in Caribbean have nothing to offer; this is done through language communication. Globalization by other means, means that every country must participate in the global economy. A country is either a donor through export of goods and services, human capacity through export of labour or import of goods and services or import of human capacity through labour or indeed a balancing of import and export of the components mentioned above. It is known that most of the developing countries especially African countries are only receiving those components' for their development and by extension do not really benefit from the globalization mantra. This is not to say that African nations do not export goods, but the value of their exports and gains cannot be equitably compared to those of advanced economies. Take for example, the products needed by the emerging economies range from industrial products to food, electronics of different kinds, cars spare parts, ships, railway components, arms, etc. Every home in the emerging economies relies heavily on goods from China. On the other hand, Chinese engineers and manufacturers are spilling over to other countries especially to African countries. They are engaging in the construction, establishment of small and medium scale industries. For instance CCEC construction companies are based here in some states in Nigeria, helping to fix our economy through construction. Again some Chinese companies are into food production, the producers of nodules products, a brand of food highly sort for in nearly every home in Nigeria and beyond. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the language of the producers and construction and vice

versa since much of their needs for exports and imports would be done through the use of language.

7. Chinese and World Economy: The Language Perspective

As earlier discussed, China is the second largest economy with an enterprising population made up of youths. She is next to the United States in industrial ladder. China, with her heavy industrial base, she has produced much goods and services needed globally especially from the emerging economies. Her export base to these countries (African, Latin America, Asia) is perhaps, command respect and wider acceptability than even those from the west in some instances. Since China now is a world factory, which produced all types of goods for virtually all countries of the world, thus in exporting their manufactured goods, China also takes advantage of the situation in exporting its language and culture. However, a lot have been said about China and how she is trying to dominate the world economically especially the emerging economies. They have offered loans, provision of infrastructures such as building of Ports, Airports as in Uganda etc. Whatever is the ulterior motive, there is no way anyone can learn their language without benefitting from their civilization and technology. Learning the Chinese language will in a long run facilitate interactions with China in the area of business, commerce, tourism and industry, diplomacy, entertainment etc. all revolves a sound communication through exchange of languages, and by extension language diversity.

8. Language Diversity: The American Perspective

The United States is known as the melting pot of nations or ethnicities. By extrapolation is also a melting pot of languages. There are over 350 languages spoken in America. However, our purpose here is not to look at these languages as they are but in the areas of world economy and its diversity. But in the overall, the commonest language or lingua France in the USA is English. In spite of the fact that the US government as a policy is encouraging the study of minor languages even those of the African descent, this is done particularly for the preservation of the people's culture and tradition. This is because when a people's language is lost the people are lost. Indeed, in the United States, English is regarded as the language of the mass media, language for the education of Americans, language for doing government business, language for interactional relations, language of diplomacy. In this connection, English language occupies a privilege position in America. This acquisition opens many doors for job opportunities for non-English speaking people to learn if they must be relevant in the American environment. This also extends to doing business in America and vice versa.

In the area of commerce and World economy, since the advent of China in the world economic sphere much changes have been made. The Americans especially the entrepreneurs are effervescently learning Chinese language. There is heavy competition between the Chinese and the United States in the areas of industrialization and trade. Of recent there was a trade war between the US and China under Trump's administration. These were facilitated through communication using the language in which the Chinese would understand and vice versa. The US is industrial power so also is China, but the competition would only make sense if communication would be understood by both parties. The economic competition have made it that a lot of Chinese students want to study in the United States, not necessarily for American civilization but for American language that is English so as to assist China balance economically in commerce and industry, tourism and indeed solidify their dominance. It is of note that since the entry of the Chinese in World Trade Organization, America has become a little cautious on

the Chinese relationship-vis-à-vis trade and diplomacy. Very many Americans are admitted into the Chinese Universities to read and protect American interest to counter the perceived domination of China. Again Chinese studies and indeed language is receiving much attention in highbrow Universities in North America. All these competitions are done to balance the economic power of these nations. One understands that America had been a domineering power in the world since the end of the Second World War, in 1945. That political barometer and economic latitude is what she still want to offer to the world - the opposing 'train' has come and that is China - only communication through diversity can conger it. That indeed has been established between them and the rest of the world.

9. Conclusion

Language diversity refers to the number of languages spoken in a country or domain and perhaps the number of people who speak them. There are very many languages in the world today; some are seen as major while others are regarded as minor. A major language refers to the number of people who speak a particular language say English or French or Spanish. To understand the concept of major language, one therefore must understand the root of colonization by European powers from the 19th -20th centuries.

However language diversity and globalization deal with global economy as the new trend in exchange relations predicts. That globalization is a buzz word and people interpret it the way they deem fit. It means the world becoming a global village as a result in improvement in communication caused by advancement in science and technology. Language diversity and globalization of economies is explained in terms of exchange relation and without understanding of one's language especially those of the super economic powers, one may be kilometers away from enjoying the benefits of globalization of economies. Using China and America as illustrations – these are two giant economies with diverse languages – how does the world integrate without them. Globalization implies give and take; hence countries who want to benefit need to key in and learn the languages in order to benefit from the new world trade.

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Compounding in Igbo Community Names: The Case of Mbase Community Names

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Abstract

Community and place names are cultural and linguistic artefacts which can be studied and preserved. This study focuses on compounding in Igbo community names, using data from Mbase dialect of the Igbo language spoken in Imo State, Nigeria. The study highlights the productivity of compounding as a morphological process in deriving Mbase community names and also sheds light on the etymology of the village names. The study uses a descriptive approach in analyzing the data based on toponomastics and anthroponomastics which are two aspects of onomastics. Data for the research were generated mainly through oral interview and existing written sources. It is observed that two or more words are combined to form the community names. The syntactic ordering of the place names is head-initial and right branching with very few exceptions. Some of the community names are etymologically traceable to events, professions, market days and names of deities which reflect the cultural identities of the people. It is also observed that most of the names originated as male forenames. In this way, the names of the forefathers are immortalized for posterity. It is noted however, that names of women were not used in naming the communities. This reflects the patriarchal nature of the Igbo society. The study further recommends a comprehensive and extensive documentation of the community names in Mbase for posterity.

Keywords: morphology, semantics, compounding, Mbase, community

1. Introduction

The definition of Morphology as the study of internal structure of words has two very different senses. On the one hand, they are made up of sequences of sounds, that is, they have internal phonological structure. For example, the English word 'boys' [bɔɪz] has four sounds or phonological segments. The words *goats* and *fowls* share not only phonological segment (the final [s]), but also a semantic component; they are all animals. In a morphological analysis according to Haspelmath and Sims (2010), the final[s] of *goats* and *fowls* expresses plural meaning when it occurs at the end of a noun. But the final[s] in *news* does not express plurality.

Following the analysis above, morphological analysis typically consists of the identification of parts of words or better technically, constituents of words. Morphological patterns can be concatenative or non-concatenative. Concatenative morphology deals with affixation and compounding while other processes are non-concatenative. Affixation is the process of adding a morpheme – or affix – to a word to create either a different form of that word or a new word with a different meaning (Norquist, 2018). The thrust of this paper is on compounding.

1.1 Compounding

Compounding is another concatenation pattern of word formation. It is a morphological process of combining two or more words to form a new word. For example:

1. rain + coat → raincoat
2. heart + beat → heartbeat

Compounding, according to Norquist (2018), is the process of combining two words (free morphemes) to create a new word. A compound therefore is a complex lexeme combining two or more base lexemes or compound members (Haspelmath & Sims, 2010). The new word is known as a compound word. Compounds can be written as a single word, for example, bitterleaf, pickpocket or as two words separated by a hyphen such as bad-tempered, long-term; or two separate words such as summer school, water bottle, hit man and so on. Compounding may involve the combination of string of words equivalent to the sentence to form compounds (Aziza & Utulu, 2018, P. 25). They further note that the “combinations may involve a noun with another noun, a verb with another verb, a noun with an adjective and so on” (p.25). English allows several types of combinations of different word-classes (N, Adj, V) but not all such combinations are possible (Haspelmath & Sims, 2010). For example,

3. N + N Earring (Ear N + ring N)
4. Adj + N Whitehouse (white Adj + house N)
5. V + N Drawbacks (draw V + backs N)
6. N + V backwash (back N + wash V)
7. Adj + Adj bitter-sweet (bitter Adj + sweet Adj)

Igbo also allows free combination of different word classes. In essence, the two different words that form the compound word may belong to different parts of speech.

1.2 Types of Compounding

There are different forms of compounding among which include root compounds or primary compounds and synthetic compounds. “A root compound is a compound construction in which the head element is not derived from a verb. Root compounds are made up of free morphemes” (Norquist, 2017). He gives the examples of hairnet or mosquito net (Noun-Noun compounds). He further observes that the right hand noun is not derived from a verb. On the other hand, “a synthetic compound is a type of compound that parallels a verbal construction, with the head derived from a verb and the other element functioning as an object (Norquist, 2018). He lists the following examples:

- | | | | |
|-----|-------------------------------------|-----|-------------------------------|
| 8a. | house + keep-ing
N + verb-ing | 9a. | dish + wash-er
N + verb-er |
| 8b. | city + plan-(n)ing
N + Verb- ing | 9b. | taxi + driv-er
N + verb-er |

Spencer (1991) defines a synthetic compound as a “compound whose head is derived by affixation from a verb”. He gave the example of *truck driver* in which *truck* is an argument of the verb or stem *driver*. Another type of compounds are endocentric and exocentric compounds. Aronoff and Fuderman (2011), define an endocentric compound as “one that has a head. The head expresses the core meaning of the compound and it belongs to the same lexical category as the compound as a whole” (p. 114). They gave the example of *goldfish*, where ‘*fish*’ is the head

and determines both the meaning and the lexical category (Noun) of the entire compound. On the other hand, exocentric compounds are those “compounds whose lexical category or meaning are not determinable from the head” (Aronoff & Fuderman, 2011, p. 114). According to them *figurehead* is an exocentric compound because “it is not a type of head” and the lexical category is not determined from the head. An exocentric compound lacks a clear head.

1.3 The Head

By way of definition, a head is a word in a syntactic construction or a morpheme in a morphological construction that determines the grammatical function or meaning of the construction as a whole (Aronoff & Fuderman, 2011, p. 264). Ndimele (1992, p. 5) stresses that a head is “concerned with the relative position of the head of a construction vis-à-vis its complement or specifier”. The head parameter according to Ndimele (1992, p.5) “is a word order parameter”. Different languages have different word orders in constructions. Some languages can be head initial and complement final or head final and complement initial. For instance, the head of a compound noun *football* is *ball* since a *football* is a *ball*, not a *foot*. *Foot* modifies the head and therefore it is dependent on the head. *Foot* is the complement of *ball*. In this case, the compound word is right headed. Heads are important to establish the direction of branching. Head initial phrases are right branching, head final phrases are left branching and head-medial phrases combine left and right branching. “The asymmetry between left branching condition (LBC) and right branching condition (RBC) rests essentially on the binary distinction between head final and head initial languages (Ndimele 1992, p.148).

1.4 Literature Review

This section reviews some works on compounding. Aziza & Utulu (2018) studied compounding in Ewulu and Urhobo languages and attempts to explore the various procedures by which both languages adopt in deriving compounds. Ewulu and Urhobo are minority languages spoken in the southern and northern parts of Delta State, Nigeria, respectively.

The analysis of the result revealed that most compounds in the two languages are derived by combining two free morphemes either from the same or different grammatical classes. Content words such as nouns, verbs, adjectives were largely used to form compounds in both languages. In the analysis, noun – noun compounds function as full words of their own. In Ewulu, nominal compounds are derived by combining nouns with adjectives. According to them, such “a combination may describe a state that portrays emotions, positive or negative feelings. Aziza & Utulu (2018) gave the following examples:

Isi + ike isiike
 N Adj.
 Head + hard stubbornness

enya + ukwu enyaukwu
 N Adj.
 eye + big greed

In both languages, forenames and numerals are formed through compounding. These could be combination of several words ranging from three to four words. The paper reveals that Ewulu and Urhobo, though two different Nigerian languages, exploit nearly the same morphological

patterns of compounding to create new words for the purpose of expanding the vocabulary. The paper concludes by recommending that the indigenous African/Nigerian languages particularly the small ones should be rigorously researched to pave way for their continuous description and documentation. Beur & Renouf (2001) did a study of word formation patterns in words from a large corpus of British Newspaper English. The study considers new compound formations. The paper examines the headedness rule and its exceptions. Beur & Renouf (2001) note that one of the basic principles of compounding in English is that English compounds are right headed. In essence, English is a head initial language. They gave an example of god child, in which the right hand element is child. From the analysis, it is a child and not a type of god. *God* modifies *child* and the two words are in the same grammatical category.

However, there are exceptions provided by exocentric compounds. Some phrasal items are overtly left headed, for instance, lady-in-waiting, mother-in-law. They mark plural on the first element. Again the compounds pass-by and passer-by are also left headed because they take inflections on the left hand element and are hyponyms of their left hand element (Beur & Renouf, 2001). Mmadike, Eme & Mbagwu (2018) studied Noun – Noun compounds in the Igbo language based on the conceptual blending theory. The study does not depend on the juxtaposition of nouns to form a new word; rather it relies on the integration of the conceptual structures provided by the mental spaces in the input structures. The conceptual structures from the input spaces are selectively projected into the blended space where they undergo the processes of composition, completion and elaboration to derive an emergent structure which constitutes the N – N compounds (Mmadike *et al*, 2018).

Maduagwu (2010) studied the morphology and semantics of personal names in the Ogbahu dialect of Igbo. The research reveals that Igbo personal names consist of both underived and derived lexical items, especially compound names. The study also discovered that personal names are not just labels for identification rather they constitute a special class of noun compounds, derived by a concatenation of words of at least two components. The names have socio-cultural and semantic implications.

The review indicates that most compounds are formed from content words such as nouns, verbs and adjectives. Such compound words may belong to the same word class or different word classes. The review further reveals that although English compounds are right headed, there are also left headed constructions in English. Mmadike, Eme & Mbagwu adopted the conceptual blending approach in accounting for N+N compounds in the Igbo language. The review also showed that some compound names are forenames and they have cultural and semantic implications.

No field of language study is indispensable. The interface of levels of language study is evidenced between morphology and semantics. A word form for example, ‘teach’ is a sequence of sounds that expresses the combination of a lexeme and of grammatical meanings (or grammatical functions) appropriate to that lexeme. In essence, no detailed morphological analysis is concluded without reference to meaning. Such meanings are overtly or covertly expressed. Semantics is a branch of linguistic study that deals with meaning. Saeed (2003) defines Semantics as “the study of meanings of words and sentences” (p.3).

Although some works have been done on compounding in the Igbo Language (Oha, 2015, Aziza & Utulu, 2018, Mmadike, Eme & Mbagwu, 2018, Mba, 2019, etc), no work known to the researcher has examined compounding and meanings of place names in the Mbaise community. Most authors wrote on the history of Mbaise and the communities that make up Mbaise village (Osuji 2013, Jamike 2013 etc). The present study examines the nexus between morphological and semantic processes involved in compounding of certain names of communities in Mbaise, Imo State, Nigeria. This work therefore aims at examining the productivity of compounding as a morphological process in certain names of villages and communities in Mbaise town, bearing in mind the fact that every name has an origin (history). This is for posterity, so that the children and the unborn generation can understand the etymology and meaning of those names. Furthermore, the documentation of the etymology of those names is very sparse. This work is to add to what has been done already. The research is useful to lexicologist and toponymists (experts that study meanings, structure, origin and area of distribution) in building a dictionary of Mbaise place names. Hence the research is timely.

2. Historical and Geo-political Background of Mbaise Town

Mbaise is an Igboland found in the South Eastern part of Nigeria. The language spoken at Mbaise is the Mbaise dialect of the Igbo language. The population of Mbaise is 611,204 people as at 2006 census (Real Jamike, 2013). The name Mbaise was suggested by Mr. JamikeIwunna in 1946 (Wikipedia). Mbaise was derived from five clans, namely, Agbaja, Ahiara, Ekwereazu, Ezinihitte and OkeUvuru (Osuji, 2013). Mbaise is made up of three Local Government Areas which are Ahiazu (derived from merging Ahiara and Ekwereazu, for administrative convenience), Aboh and Ezinihitte. The three local government areas make up 404km², as follows – Ahiazu 111km², Aboh 185km² and Ezinihitte 108km². Agbaja is made up of five communities. Ahiara is historically called Ahiarafoiri which means Ahiara of ten scepters. Each scepter represents a village in Ahiara. It is divided into two sections, namely Ihitte and Ikenga. Each of them consists of five villages, giving a total of ten villages. Ekwerezu has six communities. Ezinihitte is made up of 13 communities while Oke-Uvuru consists of 4 communities (Source: Interview). At the Local Government level, Ahiazu is made up of 14 communities, Abo, 29 autonomous communities and Ezinihitte 13 communities. As indicated earlier, each of them has other communities under them (Wikipedia).

3. Theoretical Consideration

The work is based on descriptivist approach to language study using data from Mbaise community names, Imo State, Nigeria, West Africa. The theoretical consideration is Anthoponomastics and Toponomastics. Onomastics is the study of names generally. The branch of Onomastics that studies personal names is called Anthoponomastics while the other aspect that focuses on place names - their meanings, origin, structure and area of distribution is known as Toponomastics. The theory (Onomasiology) was propounded by Milos Dokulil in 1962 and further developed in 1997 (Stekauer, 2019). This research adopts both Anthoponomastics and Toponomastics. The reason is that many place names are derived from personal names. Place names are indigenous and tied to a particular area (Franceschini). Toponymy is an important research tool in historical lexicology, dialectology and etymology (Encyclopaedia, 1979). It helps to locate the former cultural and economic centres and trade routes (Encyclopaedia, 1979). Place names are often maintained with great stubbornness inspite of a change of the population. They do not disappear with such a change. Although their meanings may not be understood, they are kept and integrated into the new language and they continue to exist just like fossils

(Franceschini, n.d). Many of them are difficult to analyse due to old age. Based on this framework, the study examines the etymology (meaning and origin) of Igbo community names, using data from Mbaïse community place names. The forenames used in naming some of the villages reflect the cultural values of the people. The research using the descriptive approach, examines the system of compounding of the community names.

4. Methodology

Data were collected through oral interview of some Mbaïse indigenes, and secondary data sources. The town, Mbaïse, has been chosen for this study because it is in the heart of Igboland, with several villages and communities, whose names are compounded. The researcher embarked on a trip to the villages and communities to interview the natives. Field notes were taken which formed most of the data. The data collected were analysed qualitatively. Morphological properties of compounds and their semantic interpretations were carried out. The etymology of the compounds was also analysed.

5. Compounding of Mbaïse Community Names

The compound names of villages and communities observed in Mbaïse town are presented below. Few names of some communities are not compounded such as Ife, Itu, Udo (under Ezinihitte). These communities that do not bear compound names are not within the focus of the present study. The meaning of each town is translated literally and contextually. The compounds are grouped into endocentric and exocentric compounds following Aronoff & Fudeman (2011) classification. An endocentric compound has a head and the head expresses the core meaning of the compound. It belongs to the same lexical category of the compound. An exocentric compound is that compound whose lexical category or meaning is not determined from the head (Aronoff & Fudeman, 2011). English language is right headed and left branching, with some exceptions while Igbo is mostly left headed (head initial) and right branching. Because Igbo is an SVO (Subject, Verb, Object) and head initial language, genitives quantifiers, demonstratives and some adjectives follow the noun. Some adjectives precede the noun (Gutman & Avanzati, 2013). In the syntactic ordering of Mbaïse place names, the compounds are head initial and right branching with very few exceptions, as seen in data (20), (24), (34) and (38). The compounds are formed using two or more morphemes with the exception of (31) that has five morphemes because names of two villages were combined to form the compound. Tonal changes are also observed in some of the morphemes when they become compounds. The analysis is done below.

5.1 Endocentric Compounds

- | | | |
|-----|---|--|
| 10 | Ókwú+àtó → Ókwúātō
N + N
Tripod+ three stand | ‘Symbolizing three brothers’ |
| 11. | Ényì+ ògwùgwù → Ényī+ ògwùgwù
N + N
Friend + god (domicile) | ‘Friend of a deity called
‘Ogwugwu’ |
| 12. | Úmù + óhía + ágū → Úmùóhíágū
Children + bush + lion | ‘Children of lion’s bush’ |

In the data 10- 11, some processes can be identified. First, we notice the metaphorical use of *ókwú* (dialectal variation, meaning *tripod*). *Ókwúno* longer has any link to *tripod stand* which is normally a three legged stand used for cooking. *Okwu* (tripod) is the head of that phrase while *ato* (three) is the complement. The tones in *ato* change from low, high to step tone when it became a compound word – *Ókwúātō*. The explicit meaning is three *brothers* that agree with each other. There is also disharmony in the formation of the word *Ókwúātō*. [o] and [u] are -ATR while [ɔ] is +ATR (mixed

set of vowels). Vowel harmony is a process where a vowel harmonizes with another vowel it occurs with, which may be distant to it (Udoh, 2012, p. 144). Where a vowel does not harmonize with another vowel it occurs with, then there is disharmony. One can also observe reduplication and prefixation in (11) as illustrated below:

ò- gwùgwù
prefixation+ reduplication

Enyi is the head of the compound. In (11), there is vowel assimilation. Vowel assimilation refers to the influence of one segment on another, such that the second sound becomes more like the other (Udoh, 2012, p. 143). Following this definition, *Úmùóhíáagū* becomes *Úmùóhíágū* in pronunciation. The compound words in (10 - 12) are from the same grammatical class, Noun. The name, *Úmùóhíágū*, is also historical depicting an event. It was alleged that a lion was seen in the bush close to the community and that earned the inhabitants of that area the name *Úmùóhíágū* (meaning children of the lion's bush). (12) appears to be a head medial phrase, *ohia* (bush) is the head while *umu* and *agu* are the specifiers or complements.

- | | | |
|-----|---|--------------------------------------|
| 13. | + ‘village of darkness’
village + night/darkness | |
| 14. | Ágū+nà + ÉzèÁgúnà + Ézè
N conj N | ‘lion and king’ |
| 15. | Úmù + nà + áamáÚmùnámā
N prep N | ‘children in front of the community’ |

In (13) *obodo* (village or nation) is the head of the phrase while *ujichi* (darkness is the complement or specifier. The name (land of darkness), is not a positive name. Darkness represents evil. There is something in a name. The compound word in (13) is from different grammatical class – N + Adj. To derive (14), there is an infixation of a conjunction *nà* (meaning and) in between two nouns *Agu... eze*. The compound is formed from two forenames, namely *Úmùágū* and *Úmùèzè* (children of Agu and children of Eze). In (15), the *na* in *Úmùnámā* (Children in front of the community) does not appear to be a conjunction rather it is a preposition; *úmù+ námā* derived by a process of deletion. *Umu* (children) is the head of the phrase while *ama* (compound) is the complement. Deletion is the omission of sound segments in certain environments in connected speech. It is also sometimes referred to as *elision* (Crystal, 1991: 119, as cited by Udoh, 2012, p133).

16. Èzí+ Údó Èzíūdō ‘compound of peace’
 N Adj
 compound+ peace
- 17 Chókó + nà + ézè Chókónàézè ‘... and king’
 N + Conj + N

In (16), the compound is formed using two different grammatical classes – N Adj. The head of the construction is *Ezi* (compound) while the complement is *udo* (peace). In (17) there is a conjunction *na* linking the two nouns *choko... eze*. The compound word is formed from two fore names *Umuchoko* and *Umueze*. The word *Choko* appears to have lost meaning due to old age. The rule of vowel harmony is obeyed in (16 – 17) apart from the conjunction.

- 18 Úmù + ézè Úmūézè ‘children of king’
 N N
- 19 Mpàm + ísí + èké mpàm Ísíēkē ‘An animal that is head of Eke market’
 N N N
 Animal + head + market

18 - 19 are all NN compounds. Disharmony is observed in all the compounds (that is, mixture of vowels from different vowel groups). The vowels in the following words: *eze*, *isi* and *eke* are all -ATR while the vowels in *úmù*, *mpàm* are from + ATR group. Item (18) is a fore name derived from ‘the children of Eze’. The head is *Umu*, the complement is *Eze*. In (19) ‘mpam’ is deduced to be a foolish animal. ‘Èké is one of the Igbo market days. The use of names of market days in the formation of place names in Mbaise shows the cultural value of the market days in Igbo land.

20. Óké – Ùvùrù Óké – Ùvùrù ‘A male tree’
 N N
 Male + tree
21. Àlà + órjī Lórjī ‘Land of kolanut’
 N N
 Land + kolanut
22. Ámá + úzū Ámúzū ‘Community of blacksmith’
 N N
 community + blacksmith
23. Ámá + íshī Ámíshī ‘Community of six’
 N N
 community + Numeral
24. Ndí + ìgbò Ndígbò ‘Igbo people’
 N N
 People + Igbo

In (20), *Ùvùrù* (tree) is the head, *Óké* (male) is the complement. This is an exception to the right branching of Igbo phrasal pattern. In examining the etymology (origin and history) of the village names, it has been observed that most of the names are forenames. For instance, *Óké –Ùvùrù* (20) (meaning male tree) gave birth to Uvuru, Mbutu, Lorji, Amuzu. Then Uvuru in turn gave birth to Ogbor, Egbelu, Amaishii, Ndigbo and Imee (children of imee formed Umuimee), Ogbor gave birth to Eke Ugo (Umuekeugo), Osike (Umuosike), Naru (Umunaru) and Ocham (Umuocham) and so on. These are all names of villages and communities in Mbaise. Some of them were not presented because either they are not compound words, which is beyond the focus of this work or their meanings have been lost due to old age. By naming some of the villages after forenames, the names of the fore fathers are preserved (immortalized) for future generation. It was noticed that no community was named after a woman. The assumption is that generations are produced through men and not women, even in the bible. It also shows the patriarchal culture of the Igbo people.

In (21) *ala* (land) is the head, *oji* (kolanut) is the complement. There is the process of clipping. Clipping is the word formation process in which a word is reduced or shortened without changing the meaning of the word (Kosur, 2019). In view of the above definition, Lorji is a clipped word, derived from *Ala orji* (land of kolanut). The word is also anglicized in its spelling. Igbo words do not permit consonant clustering (CCC) rather the structure is often vowel consonant vowel (VCV). The correct spelling should have been *oji* (VCV). In (22), *Ama* (community) is the head *uzu* (blacksmith) is the complement. The compound reflects regressive vowel assimilation. This is when a speech sound affects the sound preceding it or the first segment sound changes to become like the second. In the compound *Ama + uzu*, [a] changes to become like [u], giving rise to *Amuzu*. The name *Amuzu* also has a historical background. It was believed that migrants from Awka in Anambra State, Nigeria, settled among the inhabitants and taught them blacksmithing (source: oral interview) and that gave them that name. In (23), *Ama* is the head, while *ishii* (dialectal variation for six) is the complement. Six communities came together and formed a community. In (24), *Igbo* is the head. *Ndi* is the plural marker. Igbo language does not mark plural like English. Igbo makes use of *ndi* or *umu* to indicate plurality.

- | | | | | |
|-----|---|---|----------------------|----------------------------------|
| 25. | <i>Ámá + óhúrū</i>
N Adj
community + new | → | <i>Ámóhúrū</i> | ‘New community’ |
| 26. | <i>Ézí + àlà</i>
Adj N
Good + Land | → | <i>Ézíàlà</i> | ‘Good land’ |
| 27. | <i>Ngùrú + nwá + àfòr</i>
N N N
child + afo market | → | <i>Ngùrú Nwéàfòr</i> | ‘Ngùrú child of
Àfò market’ |
| 28. | <i>Ama + asaa + uvuru</i>
N N N
compound + seven + tree | → | <i>Amasaa Uvuru</i> | ‘Seven communities of a
tree’ |

29. Ibo + etiti → Ibo etiti ‘Middle door’
 N Adj
 Door + middle
30. Umu + nne + ato → Umunneato ‘Three siblings’
 N N N
 Children + mother + three
31. Ama + ishii + ndi + Igbo + Uvuru → Amaishii ndi Igbo Uvuru ‘Six communities of Igbo people of (a) ‘tree’
 N Nominal N N
32. Umu + amadi → Umuamadi ‘Children of god of thunder’
 N N
 children god of thunder

In (25), *Ama* is the head, *ohuru* (new) is the complement. There is regressive assimilation. The second [a] changes to become [ɔ], giving Amohuru. In (26) *ala* is the head of the construction, *ezi* (good) is the complement. The phrase is head final and left branching which is also an exception to Igbo syntactic ordering. (27) indicates the use of a market day *afo* to form a compound – *Nguru nweafor*. The spelling is also anglicized as [r] is added to *afo*. Igbo words do not end in consonants except they are syllabic nasals- [m] and [n]. *Ama* is the head in (28). *Asaa* (seven) and *uvuru* (tree) are the complement. The construction is head initial and right branching. In (30), one can observe literarily, the use of *three siblings* to form a compound name. The phrase is head initial and right branching. In (31) two semantic heads namely *ama* (community) and *Igbo* (people) are observed. In (32), the word *amadi* was deduced to be the short form of *Amadioha* (God of thunder). The formation of village names using the names of certain gods reflects the traditional Igbo belief in these deities.

33. Afor + Oru → Afor – Oru ‘Servant of Afo market’
 N N
 Afo market + servant
34. Umu + Opara → Umuopara ‘Children of first son’
 N N
 children + first son
35. Umu + dike → Umudike ‘Strong children’
 N Adj
 children + strong
36. Umu + ele + na + Eze + ala → Umuelena ezeala ‘Children of antelope and king of the land’
 N N Conj N N
 Children+Antelope+and+king+land

In (33), *oru* (servant) is the head while *afo* is the complement. It is head final and left branching. (33) also shows the loyalty of the people to their market days. Here the name depicts servants of afo market. For (34 and 35), *Umu* (children) is the head while *opara* (first son) and *dike* (strong) respectively function as the complement. Forenames were combined to form the compound name. The rule of vowel harmony is not obeyed in (33). The rule of vowel harmony is obeyed in (34). There is disharmony in (35) and (36).

37. Ama + umara → Amumara ‘The community of paddlers’
 N V
 Community + paddle

38. Nna + mere Nnamere → ‘Father did it’
 N V
 Father + did

39. Okpo + nkume → Okponkume ‘Stone breakers’ or ‘stone carvers’
 N N

In (37), *Ama* (community) is the head of the construction, *umara* (paddle) is the complement. In (38), *nna* (father) is the head, *mere* (did) is the complement. In (39), *nkume* (stone) is the head, *okpo* (the breaker) is the complement. (39) has an agentive marker which shows the performer of an action (37) and (39) have historical background. The natives of Amumara live close to Imo River. As a result, they paddle canoes and that gave them the name *Amaumara* (compound of paddlers). In (39), the occupation of the inhabitants is stone breaking. The name of the village is therefore derived from their occupation.

5.2 Exocentric compounds

The second classification of compounds following Aronoff & Fudeman (2011) is the exocentric compound. In an exocentric compound, the meaning is not determined from the head. The example is as shown below:

40. Óbù + Óhía → Óbòhía ‘Heart of bush’
 N N
 Heart + bush

The head of the phrase in (40) is *Óbù* (dialectal variation, meaning heart). While the complement is *Óhía*. It is an exocentric compound because *Óbù* (heart) is not a type of community neither is *Óhía* (bush). Vowel assimilation is also observed in (40), [u] is assimilated by [ɔ].

From the data generally, it is observed that only a very small number of prepositions form compounds. Most of the compound words are derived from nouns. The data also illustrate that many of the compound names of Mbaise villages are endocentric compounds. Only *Óbù + Óhía* *Óbòhía* is identified as an exocentric compound. The findings in this study corroborate the result of some other studies such as Aziza & Utulu (2018) and Maduagwu (2010). Aziza & Utulu (2018), for instance note that the morphemes that form the compound words are mostly content words from different word classes. This is in line with the finding of this research. Maduagwu (2010) discovered that names are not just labels; they have socio-cultural and semantic

implications. From the findings of this study, the composition of the names reflects the cultural values of the Mbaise people.

6. Conclusion

This study has examined the productivity of compounding as a morphological process in the formation of Mbaise community names. The research was also done to reveal the etymology of those village names. The compound names were classified into endocentric and exocentric compounds following Aronoff & Fudeman (2011). The study revealed that the compound names of villages in Mbaise are more of endocentric compounds than exocentric compounds. The syntactic ordering of Mbaise place names is head initial and right branching. The research also revealed that words from different parts of speech particularly content words are combined to derive the compound names of the villages. Some names are formed from events and professions of the inhabitants. Again, the four market days in Igbo land, namely: Eke, Orie, Afor and Nkwo are integral parts of the formation of the village names. This brings to the fore, the cultural value of the market days in Igbo land. Names of some gods were also used in forming compounds to indicate their belief in these gods.

On the etymology of the community names, the study revealed that many of them are male fore names. This helps in the preservation of the names of the forefathers. In this way, the children and the future generation will understand that those men existed in the past. It was also observed that only names of men are used in naming communities. Names of women are not included. According to some villagers, generations are produced through men. It also shows the patriarchal culture of the Igbo people; women are less important in the Igbo society.

We recommend further documentation of the morphological processes and etymology of the community names and villages in Mbaise for posterity. We also recommend a change of some negative names to positive ones, given the general belief in Igbo that negative names have negative effect on their bearers.

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Affixation in Kolokuma

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Abstract

This study examines affixation, reduplication and compounding as word formation processes in Kolokuma. The types and functions of affixes found in Kolokuma are discussed. This study uses a basic descriptive approach in the analysis of the data. Interviews and observation were used as instruments of data collection. This study reveals that affixation and compounding are more productive morphological processes of word formation in Kolokuma.

Keywords: morphology, morpheme, affix, root, affixation

1. Introduction

Yul-Ifode (2008) describes language as the greatest asset of man. Language is most commonly described as a medium of communication and seen as a code used by humans, basically. The branch of linguistics that studies the formation of words in languages is known as morphology. Morphology is also interested in how users of a particular language form and understand complex words and invents new lexical items. Morphologica

l constructions can be derived from affixation, compounding and reduplication, which are elements in human language. Affixation is one of the word formation processes generally, in languages. In Kolokuma, like most languages, there are affixes which are bound morphemes that become meaningful only when added to a root or a base. Affixation is a very potent word formation process in Kolokuma. Some of the affixes in Kolokuma are inflectional which only function to signal grammatical relations, marking tense, aspects, number, gender, case, negation, etc, while others perform derivational role. Against this backdrop, the paper discusses affixation, compounding and reduplication in Kolokuma, a language belonging to the Ijoid sub-group of the Niger Congo family of languages, according to Yul-Ifode (2008). Morphology, according to Haspelmath (2002), is the study of the internal structure of words. Morphological analysis typically consists of the identification of parts of words or more technically, constituents of words. Word-forms in an inflectional paradigm generally share (at least) one longer morpheme with a concrete meaning and are distinguished from each other in that they in addition, contain different shorter morphemes with an abstract meaning. Such short morphemes with an abstract meaning are called affixes. Affixes are bound morphemes.

Affixation is a morphological process of attaching an affix (usually a bound morpheme) to the root or base of a word in order to derive other forms. Affixes are classified based on two criteria. The first criterion is the position in which the affix occurs relative to the location of the root of the word, while the second is the function an affix performs when it is attached to the root of a word.

In Kolokuma, for instance, affixation presents itself in form of suffixation, interfixation and suprafixation. In what follows these manifestations shall be discussed extensively.

2. Purpose of the Study

Kolokuma is a dialect of Izon language. Following the linguistic genre classification, it is described as an Ijoid language under the Niger Congo language family which covers most of Sub-Saharan Africa.

The purpose of this study is to expose Kolokuma to thorough linguistic investigation and documentation as it focuses on the morphology of the language, discussing the affixes in Kolokuma. Thus, the study seeks to: identify affixes in the language, describe the classes of affixes in the language, discuss the functions of affixes and determine the productivity of affixes in the language. Data was collected from interviews and our intuition, as members of the speech communities when consulted as well.

3. Theoretical Framework

The study uses the morpheme-based morphology (item (I) and arrangement approach (A)) theory on the analysis of the data. The morpheme based morphology or IA model treats word forms as arrangements of morphemes. They see them as morphemes put together like beads on a string to form words. The item-and-arrangement model proceeds from a picture of each language as a set of elements and the patterns in which those elements occur. It is believed to have grown out of structuralists' preoccupation with word analysis involving the technique of breaking down words into their component morphemes, which they call items. This is why morphological analysis here is centered on the morpheme.

4. Conceptual Analysis

Some concepts related to the topic shall be discussed in what follows.

4.1 Morphology

Fromkin and Rodman (2007) assert that morphology is the study of the internal structure of words and the rules by which words are formed. Harmer (2006) sees morphology and syntax as essentials to successful communication whether in writing or speech. This means that items that make up words in a language is the major preoccupation of morphology. Crystal (1997) posits that morphology is the branch of linguistics which studies the structure or forms of words primarily through the use of morphemes. Ejele (1996) describes morphology as the level of grammar which studies the internal structure or forms of words, primarily through the use of the morpheme concept as well as the rules by which words are formed. The definitions are all similar as they express one notion, the formation of words through the use of the morpheme that are rule governed.

4.2 Morpheme

The morpheme is seemingly one of the controversial concepts or phenomena in morphology. Before the emergence of morphemes, words were considered the least grammatical units and as such, the basic unit of morphological analysis. However, upon the discovery, certain words could further disintegrate into smaller meaningful linguistic grammatical units.

Katamba (1993:20) posits that "morpheme is used to refer to the smallest, indivisible units of semantic content or grammatical function which words are made up of". While Ejele (1996) asserts that morpheme is the smallest (minimum) meaningful unit of grammar. She added that a single word may be made up of one or more morphemes. Ndimele (2003:9) supports Ejele's claim that the morpheme is the smallest meaningful unit of an utterance which may not,

however, exist in isolation. From the various definitions, we gather that a morpheme is the smallest linguistic unit that has a semantic content which may or may not exist independently.

There are two types of morphemes; free and bound morphemes. A free morpheme can stand alone and convey meaning. A free morpheme is a word which may be lexical or functional. Bound morphemes on the other hand cannot stand on their own as words. They must be attached to a root to be meaningful. That is they do not occur in isolation.

4.2.1 Affix

An affix is a bound morpheme which is always attached to the base or root of a word, Ndimele (1999:13). Affixes do not have independent existence. Katamba (1993:14) opines that “an affix is a morpheme which only occurs when attached to some other morpheme or morphemes such as root or stem or base”. Ejele (1996) puts it that affixes are meaningful units added to the root that cannot exist independently of the root. Affixes therefore are bound morphemes that cannot exist independently but are meaningful that needs to be added to a host.

4.2.2 Root

Katamba (1993:4) defines a root as “the irreducible core of a word with absolutely nothing else attached to it”. That is, a root is the part of the word that carries the core meaning of the word that remains when all affixes or other word modifiers have been removed.

Ndimele (1999) describes the root as that part of the word that remains after every other element has been removed. He added that the root is usually the heart of the word which cannot be further divided into smaller meaningful units.

4.3 Affixation

Affixation, according to Ndimele (1999:83) is a ‘morphological process of attaching an affix to the root or base of a word’. In other words, the morphological process involving the addition of an affix (usually a bound morpheme) to roots or bases in order to derive other forms is affixation. There are different types of affixes classified either by position or function. Positional affixes are defined according to the position they assume in relation to the roots or bases to which they are allocated.

Prefixes are affixes which occur before the root or base of a word. Suffixes occur after the root of a word and infixes are inserted inside the root of a word. They interrupt the sequence of a root.

Interfixes are affixes which occur between two usually identical roots. Circumfixes on the other hand, are affixes which surround the root of a word. A circumfix is more or less a simultaneous combination of prefixes and suffixes to express a single meaning.

Superfixes or suprafixes are non-segmental affixes in the form of tone or stress marks which make meaning difference when placed over a word.

4.3.1 Affixation in Kolokuma

In what follows is the morpho-syntactic analysis of affixation, compounding and reduplication in Kolokuma. Two functional categories of affixes, which are inflectional and derivational affixes are examined.

4.3.2 Tense and Aspect Markers in Kolokuma

According to Ndimele (2007:113), tense is a grammatical category which determines the form of the verb in a sentence with respect to changes in time. He explained further that it is the

grammaticalisation of time reference, often using three basic categories of ‘before now’(the past), ‘now’ (the present) and ‘after now’ (the future).Aspect on the other hand has been described as the different ways of viewing the internal temporal constituency of a situation. The data shows tense and aspect markers in Kolokuma.

Table: 1

Verb root	Gloss	Suffix	Derived form	Gloss	Function of affix
bo	come	-yemi	boyemi	coming	progressive
bo	come	-mì	bomì	came	past tense
mu	go	-dọ	mudọ	Has gone	perfect tense
bo	come	-tjimi	botjimi	was coming	imperfect tense
bo	come	-ngimi	bongimi	will come	future tense

4.3.3 The Progressive Aspect

The progressive in Kolokuma is expressed or marked by attaching the suffix–**yemi** to the root verb.

Bo “come” **boyemi** “is/are coming”

Mu “go” **muyemi** “is/are going”

Koru “wait” **koruyemi** “is/are waiting”

1. Ebioweiboyemi.

Ebiwei come + pre progressive.

Ebiwei is coming.

2. Erideriyemi.

He laugh + pre progressive

He is laughing.

3. Ebierewarighomuyemi.

Ebiere house go + pre progressive

Ebiere is going home.

4. Qwqumqzoruyemi.

Children the play + pre progressive

The children are playing.

5. Arifun gooyemi.

I book read + pre progressive

I am reading a book.

6. Peter sukulubuyemi.

Peter school go + pre progressive

Peter is going to school

7. Eriarukoruyemi

He car wait + pre progressive
He is waiting for a car.

4.3.4 Past Tense

In Kolokuma, the past tense is formed by attaching the suffix **-mi** to after the verb root.

kulé	“greet”	kulé mi	greeted
bo	“come”	bo mi	came
suru	“wash”	suru mi	washed

8. Ari dada kulémi
I father greet + past.
I greeted daddy.

9. Tɔ̀bɔ̀ɔ̀bi alalamɔ̀sɔ̀rumi****
Child the plate+pl.marker wash + past.
The child washed the plates.

10. Ɔ̀wɔ̀ɔ̀mɔ̀bomi
Children the come + past
The children came.

11. Eri ma fulɔ̀tɔ̀mi****
Woman the soup cook + past
The woman cooked soup

-mi is also used to show present state (with adjectival verbs) or conditions of the subject of the sentence

Aku	“bitter”	aku mi	(it) is	bitter
imbele	“delicious”	imbele mi	(it) is	delicious
Uku	“heavy”	uku mi	(it) is	heavy

12. Diribiakumi
Medicine the bitter + be.
The medicine is bitter.

13. Fulɔ̀biimbelemi
Soup the delicious + be.
The soup is delicious.

14. Ekpɛtibikumi
Box the heavy + be.
The box is heavy.

15. Benibiɔfirimi

Water the hot + be.
The water is hot.

4.3.5 Perfect Tense

The present perfect tense is formed by adding the suffix **-dɔ** to the end of the verb root.

Tuɔ “cook” tuɔ**dɔ** “has/have cooked”

Miɛ “do” miɛ**dɔ** “has/have done/prepared”

Fɛɛ “buy” fɛɛ**dɔ** “has/have bought”

16. Ina fɛlɔtɔ**dɔ**

Grandmother soup cook + pft tense.
Grandmother has cooked soup

17. Tarigarimɛ**dɔ**

Tarigarriprepare + pft tense.
Tari has prepared garri.

18. John ayaaru**fɛɛdɔ**

John new car buy + pft tense.
John has bought a new car.

19. Ebierepa**adɔ**

Ebierego + pft tense.
Ebiere has gone out.

4.3.6 Imperfect Aspect

The imperfect aspect is marked by the suffix **-tɛmi** attached to the verb root. We noticed that the emphazier is always used with the imperfect aspect.

Fii**tɛmi** “was/were eating”

Tuɔ**tɛmi** “was/were cooking”

20. Dada fɛ yaikifi**tiimi**.

Daddy food emphz eat + impft.
Daddy was eating.

21. Eri**funkigotɛmi**arɛbomi

He book emphz. read impft I came
He was reading a book when I came.

22. Ina fūlqūkitūq̄t̄j̄midada paami
Grandmother soup emphz cook impft daddy went out
Grandmother was cooking soup when daddy went out.

4.3.7 Future Tense

The future tense is formed by adding the suffix **-ngimi** to the end of the verb root.

F̄ēngimi “will buy”
Baangimi ”will kill”

23. Timioborib̄baangimi.
Timigoatthe kill + future
Timi will kill the goat.

24. John ayaarūf̄ēngimi
John new carbuy + future.
John will buy a new car.

25. Mary indib̄f̄ē!nngimi
Mary fish the roast + future.
Mary will roast the fish.

4.3.8 Number, Article and Gender Markers

Jackson (2007:44) posits that number is a grammatical category that is associated with nouns, pronouns and adjectives that express count distinctions. In Kolokuma, number is marked via inflection.

Word root	Gloss	Suffix	Derived word	Gloss	Function of affix
t̄qb̄q̄	boy	-b̄i	t̄qb̄q̄b̄i	the boy	masc. sing.
t̄qb̄q̄	girl	-ma	t̄qb̄q̄ma	the girl	fem. sing.
w̄ari	house	-m̄q̄	w̄arim̄q̄	the houses	def. pl.
w̄ari	house	-ama	w̄ariama	houses	indef. pl.
Firi	Work	-out	Firiotu	Workers	Irreg. pl. (for grp of pple)
Eré	Woman	-am̄inj̄	Eréam̄inj̄	Women	Irreg. pl. (for grp of pple)

The definite article markers are suffixed to the nouns to show gender, number and definiteness. In English, the definite article ‘**the**’ has only one form which is used with any noun, whether masculine or feminine, singular or plural. E.g.

The boy	the boys	the girl	the girls
The man	the men	the bags	the bags

In Kolokuma, the form of the definite article varies according to the gender and the number of noun it introduces. In other words, the gender or number of noun determines the form of the definite article that goes with it.

The inflectional suffixes **-bi**, **-ma**, **-mɔ**, **-ama**, **-amɪni**, **-otu**, etc are affixed to the noun. These are bound morphemes and have no independent meaning except when they are attached to the root or a free morpheme.

- A. -bi** is an inflectional suffix that marks the definite singular article but restricted to masculine nouns. Examples

Tɔbɔɔ**bi**“the boy” daub**i**“the father” burub**i**“the yam”

- B. -ma** is an inflectional suffix that marks only definite feminine singular article in nouns. It is used for only animate beings. Examples

Eré**ma**“the woman” tɔbɔɔ**ma**“the girl” taá**ma**“the wife”

-mɔ is the definite article that indicates plural form and it is used with both masculine and feminine. Examples

Eréɔwɔɔ**mɔ**“the girls” oweiɔwɔɔ**mɔ**“the boys”

Fun**mɔ**“the books” angam**mɔ**“the eggs”

- C. -amɪni** is an irregular inflectional suffix that marks plurality and it is restricted to humans only. Other nouns form a regular plural by adding **-ama**, the indefinite plural marker which is like the plural **-s** or **-es**, in English. Examples

fun ‘book’	fun- ama	‘books’
obiri ‘dog’	obiri- ama	‘dogs’
eré ‘woman’	eré amɪni	‘women’
owéi ‘man’	owéi amɪni	‘men’
eré ma ‘the woman’	ere amɪni mɔ	‘the women’
Owéibi ‘the man’	owéi amɪni mo	‘the men’

The suffix **-amɪni** is an indefinite plural marker. The indefinite singular article is not overtly marked in Kolokuma, whenever a noun occurs without the definite article marker, it automatically takes the covert indefinite marker (e.g. **tɔbɔɔ** “a boy”, **fun** “a book”).

- D. -otu** is another inflectional suffix that marks plurality. It indicates group of people. Examples

dau	father	dau- otu	parents/fathers
yengi	mother	yengi- otu	parents/mothers
firiweni	to work	firi-weni otu	workers

The difference between **-ama** and **-otu** is that, **-ama** can only be attached to nouns whereas **-otu** can be attached to both nouns and verbs.

5. Negation in Kolokuma

Negative constructions or statements are used to express denial or opposition, also to prove or claim that a theory or statement is false

There are two common ways to mark negotiation in Kolokuma. These are by attaching the suffix **-gha** (meaning not) and **-kumɔ** (meaning don't) to the verb root. The negative operator **-ghais** used for expressing the negation of declarative and interrogative sentences, while the suffix **-kumɔis** used to express the negation of imperative.

5.1 Simple Present Negative Marker

Table: 3

Positive	Gloss	Negative	Gloss
boyemi	coming/ comes	bogha	not coming/ doesn't,
muyemi	going/ goes	mugha	not going/ doesn't go
deriyemi	laughing/ laughs	derigha	not laughing/ doesn't laugh

26. Erɪboyemi

He come tense
He is coming or he comes.

27. Erɪbogha

He come neg.mrkr
He is not coming or he doesn't come.

28. Arɪmuyemi

I go tense
I am going or I go.

29. Arɪmugha

I go neg.mrkr.
I am not going or I won't go.

30. Timidɛɪyemi

Timi laugh tense
Timi is laughing or Timi laughs.

31. Timidɛɪgha

Timilaughneg.mrkr
Timi is not laughing or Timi doesn't laugh.

5.2 Simple Past (negative marker)

Table: 4

Positive	Gloss	Negative	Gloss
bom̩	came	bogha	didn't come
mum̩	went	mugha	didn't go
se̩m̩	danced	se̩gha	didn't dance

5.3 Perfect tense

In the perfect tense, **-gha** also replaces the perfect tense marker **-d̩q̩**, but **naa** meaning 'not yet' is introduced.

32. Yengif̩l̩q̩t̩q̩d̩q̩

Mummy soup cook perfective
"Mummy has cooked soup".

33. Inanaaf̩l̩q̩t̩q̩q̩gha

Grandmother not yet soupcook+neg.mrkr.
Grandmother has not yet cooked soup.

34. Preye w̩ar̩ ghomud̩q̩.

Preye house go + perfective
Preyehas gone home.

35. Preye **naa** wari ghomugha

Preye not yet house go +neg.mrkr.
Preye hasn't gone home yet.

5.4 Negative Commands

In commands, verbs are used in their simple root form e.g. **bo!** "come" **mu!** "go" **dii!** "look". The suffix **-k̩m̩q̩**, meaning 'do not' is always used to negate imperative sentences such as commands, orders and directives.

Y̩q̩	"paddle"	y̩q̩k̩m̩q̩	"don't paddle"
Bo	"come"	bok̩m̩q̩	"don't come"
Mu	"go"	muk̩m̩q̩	"don't go"
ql̩q̩	"cough"	ql̩q̩k̩m̩q̩	"don't cough"
Paa	"go out"	paak̩m̩q̩	"don't go out"

Fari “play music” farikũmɔ “don’t play”

36. Kala aruyɔkũmɔ.
Small canoe paddle not.
“Don’t paddle a small canoe”e.

37. Owigiri duma farikũmɔ
Owigirimusic play not.
“Don’t play owigiri music”.

38. Kĩmĩtiripaakũmɔ
Man outside go out not
“Nobody should go outside”.

5.5 Comparison of Adjectives

The form for the comparison degree and for the superlative degree is usually marked by affixing **-de!n** to the positive degree i.e. the simple form of the adjective as shown in the following examples.

Duba	“big”	dubade!n	“bigger/larger”
Kũrɔ	“strong”	kũrɔde!n	“stronger”
Ebi	“good/beautiful”	ebide!n	“better”

39. JohnkũrɔMikedē!nnimi.
John strong Mike surpass
John is stronger than Mike.

40. Amasewowárikidubade!nnimi
Whole village his house emphz surpass
His house is the largest in the village.

41. Arĩdangaininebinaoweide!nnimi
I tall my brother surpass
I am taller than my brother.

In the first sentence above, two persons are compared as to strength. According to the sentence, John possesses a quality to a greater degree than Mike. Here the affix **-de!n** is the equivalent of **-er** in English. In the second sentence, more than two houses are being compared. The superlative degree of the adjective large is used to show this fact. However, there is no clear morphological difference between the comparative and superlative affixes. There is no overt superlative degree in Kolokuma. In the comparative degree, **-de!n** is used when a comparison is

made between two persons or things. –**dɛ!n** is also used when more than two persons or things are compared. The superlative degree is understood from the semantic content of the sentences.

6. Interfixation

Interfixation is another morphological process that is evident in Kolokuma. An interfix is an affix which occurs between two identical or sometimes non-identical roots. The affix –**ki** which is an emphazier, is inserted in between an identical root. As in:

Dubakiduba
 Dubakiduba
 Big emphz big
 ‘Really big’
 Zorukizoru
 Play emphz play
 Play indeed.

7. Suprafixation

In kolokuma, the non-segmental affix also manifest, as derivation is achieved through suprafixation, which is a process where a variation in the pitch of the voice causes a change in meaning. Works done by some scholars like Ekuigbo and Ayunku (2018), deny the existence of suprafixes in Izon generally. The examples given in their study were cases of homonyms. Consider the following examples.

é řę ‘talk’	ę řę ‘name’
eri ‘he’	éri ‘dry/chinmey’
dú ma ‘song’	duma ‘hair’
dú ‘story’	dụ ‘collusion/jam’
ari ‘I’, ‘me’	ári ‘you’
ụ kụmọ ‘only him’	ụkụmọ ‘private parts’

8. Derivational affixes (class changing)

In Kolokuma, derivational affixes are added to the root or base of a word in order to produce a new word which may either belong to the same or different word classes, Blench and Williamson (2015).

8.1 Verb to Noun

When the bound morpheme –**bq** is suffixed to the verb root, it changes the lexical meaning of the base as well as the word-class.

Table: 5

Verb (root)	Gloss	Suffix	Derived words (Noun)	Gloss
kọrimọ	drive	bq	kọrimọ bq	driver
dawai	learn	bq	dawai bq	learner
sẹi	dance	bq	sẹi bq	dancer

8.2 Noun to Verb

The suffix **-mɔ** is attached to the base of nouns to derive new words. Like the bound morpheme **-bɔ**, **-mɔ** changes both the word-class and the lexical meaning of the base.

Table: 6

Noun	Gloss	Suffix	Derived word (verb)	Gloss
firi	work	mɔ	firimɔ	to send
indou	breast	mɔ	indoumɔ	to breast feed
uyá	suffer(ing)	mɔ	uyámɔ	to suffer

8.3 Adjective to Verb

When **-mɔ** is attached to an adjective, the derived word is a verb which is a different part of speech. It also changes the lexical meaning of the root verb as shown in the table that follows.

Table: 7

Adjective	Gloss	Suffix	Derived word (verb)	Gloss
buru	rotten	mɔ	burumɔ	cause to rot
duba	big	mɔ	dubamɔ	to make big
ofiri	hot	mɔ	ofirimɔ	to warm

8.4 Derivational affixes (class maintaining): Class maintaining or non-class changing derivational affixes maintain the grammatical class of the word from which a new word is derived. They only modify the lexical meaning of the base word without changing the part of speech.

8.4.1 Verb to Verb

This affix **-mɔ** is suffixed to a verb to derive another verb. However, the meanings are modified while the word-class is maintained. In the table below, both base words and the derived words are verbs with slight difference in meaning.

Table: 8

Verb	Gloss	Suffix	Verb	Gloss
deri	laugh	mɔ	derimɔ	make laugh
wɛɲɪ	walk	mɔ	wɛɲimɔ	make walk
ukie	remember	mɔ	ukiemɔ	remind

8.4.2 Adjective to Adjective

The affix **-gha** is a negative indicator and when it is suffixed to the adjective the derived word is also an adjective. In the table below, the words in the two columns are all adjectives but with opposite meanings

Table: 9

Adjective	Gloss	Suffix	Adjective	Gloss
sei	bad	gha	seigha	not bad
ebi	good	gha	ebigha	not good
pina	ripe	gha	pinagha	not ripe

9. Verbal Extensions in Kolokuma

This part of the work discusses verbal extensions in Kolokuma. It may be restated that verbal extensions are class-maintaining derivational affixes which affect only the lexical meaning of the base word (verb) to which they are attached. They merely alter the meaning of their host or extend or modify the meaning of the base verb. Verbs in Kolokuma can take suffixes which extend their meaning and modify the syntax of the sentence. Verbal extensions that have been identified in Kolokuma (Izon) are self-action, reciprocal, causative, directional and extended directional.

9.1 Extensional suffixes in Kolokuma

Table: 10

Suffix	Meaning	Base form	Output(v)
-i	self action	sani (v.t.) melt	sanii (v.s.) melt (by itself)
-i	reciprocal	tari (v.t.) love	tarii (v. recip.) love each other
-mɔ	directional	weni (v.i.) walk	wenimo (v.dir.) walk towards
-mɔ	causative	bunu (v.i.) sleep	bunumo (v.c.s.) make sleep

9.2 Self-action verbs

Self-action verbs express actions that come about by themselves. They are extended from certain transitive verbs but are not transitive in themselves. In other words, self-action verbs do not necessarily have any agent that generates the action they express. Self-action verbs are formed in two ways.

- a. Adding the suffix –i (-i)
- b. By dropping the original subject and making the original object into the subject position.

The data below illustrates self-action verbs. In the example, ‘simple’ means ‘simple verb’ and ‘extended’ means ‘extended verb’ brought about by an extension affix.

A. Simple: sanj “melt” (something)

42. Aripulousaniji
I oil melted
“I melted the oil”
Extended: Sanj (v.s.) melt (by itself) without an agent
43. Pulou bi saniji.
Oil the melted
“The oil melted”.

B. Simple: terj (v.t.) close (a container with a lid or to shut a door).

44. Eriogabiteriji
He door the shut
“He shut the door”.
Extended: Terj (v.s.) closed (by itself) or shut e.g. a pot, door etc.
45. Ogugabiteriji.
Door the closed
“The door got shut”.

C. Simple: kja (v.t.) filter (something liquid)

46. Ari beni bi kiami
I water the filtered
“I filtered the water”.
Extended: kiaj (v.s.) ooze out (water oozing out and dried)
47. Benibikiaimi.
Water the drained off
“The water drained off”.

D. Simple: katj (v.t.) pluck

48. Erialalaindakati
He orangeplucked
“He plucked an orange”.
Extended: katj (v.s.) fell (by itself)

49. Alalaindakatiimi
Orange fell (by itself)
The orange fell
“The orange fell by itself”.

E. Simple: kpeki (v.t.) gather

50. Kimi bi ɔ̀tɔ̀kɔ̀kpekimi
Man the mud gathered
“The man gathered the mud”.
Extended: kpekii(v.s.) gather

51. Òtɔ̀kɔ̀mɔ̀warìbùbòkpekimii
Mud the+pl door the gathered
“The mud gathered in front of the door”.

In the first sentences each of the examples above, the verbs: *sani*, *teri*, *kia*, *kati* and *kpeti* are used as transitive verbs (v.t.). This means that the sentence has a subject and an object. In other words, it has an agent who causes or initiates the action represented by the verb and a patient which receives or suffers the actions of the syntactic agent. However, by adding the verbal extensions to the root verbs, not only do the morphology of the roots change but their meanings are also modified. The verbal extension effectively removes the value of transitivity from the verbs and makes them intransitive. Consequently, in the (b) sentences of the examples above using VEs, the grammatical object and complement of the verb (the patient) becomes the grammatical subject but still maintains its semantic role as the patient and not the agent. By adding or suffixing –ì to their verb roots: *saniì*, *teriì*, *kjaiì*, *katiì*, and *kpetiì* their meanings are modified, thus, making or changing them into self-action verbs. These are illustrated in the second (b) sentences (extended) example (1) to (5) above. Significantly, as has been mentioned earlier, in spite of the morphological and semantic changes of the verbs, the category or class of the derived words remain unchanged.

9. 3 Reciprocal verbs

Reciprocal verb extensions (v. recip.) express action done by two or more (persons) to each other. Reciprocal verbs (v. recip.) are extended from simple transitive verbs in which the subject and the object can be reversed by:

- a. Adding the suffix –ì (-ì)
- b. Combining the subject and object into plural subject.

Data for reciprocal verbs provided below

F. Simple: gbɔ̀lɔ̀(v.t.) box; to give a blow on someone

52. Preye, Timigbɔ̀lɔ̀mi.
Preye, Timi boxed
Preye boxed Timi.
Extended: gbolìj (v. recip.) to box each other.

When the affix ‘-i’ is attached to the base verb **gbolu**, a new word ‘**gboli**’ is derived. These new words remain a verb. The affix is a verbal extension that creates a new meaning different from the base. This is illustrated in the sentence below.

53. PreyemṛTimimṛgbṛlṛiṛi.
Preye and Timi and boxed (each other).
Preye and Timi fought.

G. Simple: tari (v.t.) love

54. EbioweiEbieretarṛiṛi.
EbioweiEbiere loved.
Ebiowei loves Ebiere.
Extended: tarii (v. recip.) love each other.

55. EbioweimoEbieremotarṛiṛiṛi
Ebiowei and Ebiere and love each other.
Ebiowei and Ebiere love each other.

H. Simple: kpotu (v.t.) chase

56. Preye, Timikpotumi.
Preye, Timi chased
Preye chased Timi.
Extended: kpotui (v. recip.) chase each other

57. PreyemṛTimimṛkṛpotṛuiṛi.
Preye and Timi and chased
Preye and Timi chased each other.

I. Simple: laba (v.t.) embrace

58. Preye, Timilabami.
Preye, Timi embraced
Preye embraced Timi.
Extended: labai (v. recip.) embrace each other

59. PreyemṛTimimṛlabaiṛiṛi.
Preye and Timi and embraced
Preye and Timi embraced each other.

There are some reciprocal verbs that possess the ‘-i’ suffix that creates the extended meaning but do not necessarily have a root verb from which the extension is derived. These verbs seem to be the base words in themselves. It may even be contemplated that the reciprocal verb extensions borrowed the meaning production patterns of these verbs. The following verbs are few examples.

J. Ololaj (v. recip.) compatible; have a good relationship

60. Beitaamoyeimṣolalajmĩ
This wife and husband are compatible
This husband and wife are compatible

K. Galabaj (v. recip.) be in disagreement (as husband and wife) or friends; be on bad terms

61. Beitaamoyeimogalabajdṣu
This wife and husband and scattered
This husband and wife have scattered.

L. Gbelei (v. recip.) meet (each other)

62. Beiikiatumoowikiritirikṣgbeleimi
These friends dance floor on met (each other)
These friends met each other on the dance floor.

10. Compounding

This is a process of joining two or more formerly independent roots to form a single word. A word formed in this manner is called a compound. Compounding is a very productive morphological process in most languages. It does not only involve stringing together of words to form a word class but words from different word classes can also be combined to form compounds.

10.1 Noun + Noun

Two formerly independent nouns can combine to form a compound word as illustrated in the table.

Table: 11

Noun	Gloss	Noun	Gloss	Compound word	Gloss
kiri	ground	wári	house	kiriwári	bungalow
ogṣṣ	up	wári	house	ogṣṣwári	story building
ogṣṣ	up	toru	eye	ogṣṣtoru	sky

10.2 Verb + Noun

Another type of compound is that of stringing together words from different word-classes, that is a verb + noun to form a compound word.

Table: 12

Verb	Gloss	Noun	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
sùu	fight	kìmjì	person	sùukìmjì	soldier
tolumọ	teach	oweì	man	tolumo- oweì	teacher
fin	fly	arụ	boat	fin arụ	Aeroplane

10.3 Adjective + Noun

An adjectival based compound is another category which consists of an adjective and a noun. Adjectival based compounds are fixed. When the structure is reversed, it is meaningless.

Table: 13

Adjective	Gloss	Noun	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
pẹrẹ	rich	kìmjì	person	pẹrẹkìmjì	rich man
gọmụ	straight	kìmjì	person	gọmụkìmjì	honest person
ebi	good	egbéri	news	ebi-egbéri	good news

10.4 Noun + Adjective

The following compounds (noun + adjective) have nouns as their head words, however, the new words formed are semantically adjectives.

Table: 14

Noun	Gloss	Adjective	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
bolou	mind	ebi	good	bolouebi	kind-hearted
bolou	mind	kụrọ	strong	boloukụrọ	be brave
tubo	price	kụrọ	stong	tubokụrọ	expensive

10.5 Noun + Verb

We also have the noun as the head in this combination (noun + verb) but the compound words formed are verbs.

Table: 15

Noun	Gloss	Verb	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
wárij	house	bọun	roof	wárijbọun	roof a house
bụu	pound	sai	bail	Bụusai	bail pound
mọun	hunger	kọrụ	wait	mọunkọrụ	fast

10.6 Noun + Verb + Noun

These are compounds involving the joining together of three formerly independent roots to form a single word.

Table: 16

Noun	Verb	Noun	Compound	Gloss
náma meat	kọrí catch	obiri dog	námakori-obiri	hunter dog
okoba money	kokou keep	wárij house	okobakokouwárij	bank
bìbì mouth	gba say	wárij house	bìbìgbawárij	court

From the above examples, it can be observed that compounding is a very productive morphological process in Kolokuma and it plays a crucial role in the lexicon of Izq̄n language. Compounding enriches the language and enhances communication in terms of the expression of new ideas and new concepts, for language development.

11. Summary and Conclusion

In the course of this study, we have been able to provide a description of word formation processes in Kolokuma. We found out that suffixation is very productive. Suffixes perform inflectional, derivational and extensional functions by:

- (a) modifying the meaning of the base to which they are attached.
- (b) changing the word-class to which a base belongs and
- (c) marking singular-plural contrasts in nouns, contrasts between tenses in verbs, comparative and superlative contrast in adjectives and gender and number in nouns etc.

Article markers are suffixed to the noun to show gender, number, and definiteness. The form of the definite article varies according to the gender and number of the noun it introduces. We also found out that the indefinite singular article is not marked in Kolokuma. Whenever a noun occurs without the definite article marker, it automatically takes the covert indefinite marker. The suffix **-m̄q̄** is a multi-purpose suffix. (a) It is a definite plural marker. (b) It serves as a class changing affix when suffixed to a noun or an adjective and a class maintaining affix when suffixed to a verb. The study reveals that interfixation and suprafixation are evident in Kolokuma as well. Negation in Kolokuma is marked by attaching the suffixes **-gha** (meaning not) and **-kum̄q̄** (meaning do not) to the verb root. We also observed that compounding in Kolokuma involves joining together words from the same word-class as well as words from different word-classes.

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Itu Mbon Uso Personal Names: A Morphological Analysis

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Abstract

This paper examines the morphological structure and morphological processes in Itu Mbon Uso personal names. Data for the study were elicited from six adult native speakers of Itu Mbon Uso selected through stratification. The theoretical framework adopted was eclectic in nature, combining Item-and-Arrangement (IA) model of morphological-based theory and Head Feature Convention (HFC) theory. The findings showed that Itu Mbon Uso personal names have rich morphological structure which provides grammatical information about the morphemic components that make up the names. It is also observed that the morphological processes involved in the formation of the names are mainly derivational in nature and accord with the structure of the language.

Keywords: morphology, onomastics, language, processes, names

1. Introduction

Language is a dynamic phenomenon, which exhibits different degrees of creativity to serve the communication needs of its users. It takes bits of sound (syllables) and morphemes to create lexical items (words) (Mbah, 2012). Words are part of speech (i.e. property of morphology), which form the fundamental building block of a language. A word is composed of morphemes, which perform grammatical operations in human languages as well as modify it into various functions to create meaning. According to Benjamin (2019:31), derivational morphology is a process, which involves “the segmentation of words to create new words from an existing word. It may combine two lexical items together to form new words and new meanings”. Thus, derivational morphology creates new words and meaning into a language from time to time. The meaning of many words is a function of the morphemes that compose them; just as the meaning of a phrase or a sentence is partially a function of the meanings of the words it contains (Fromkin, Rodman & Hyam, 2007).

Names reflect language in use; they contain the lexicon of any language (Essien, 1986). Personal names (anthroponomastics) are formed from words, which constitute the internal structures of words. Through names, we can identify where a person comes from, hence, they (names) reflect both the linguistic and cultural identity of the bearer (Mbarachi & Igwenyi, 2018). According to Essien (1986:5) “Naming in Ibibio is not an arbitrary affair: it is at once a mental, emotional, linguistic and cultural matter”. This assertion, by extension applies to Itu Mbon Uso as a language of the Lower Cross group, where the Ibibio language belongs. Thus, names in Itu Mbon Uso undertake some processes which can be classified on the basis of its morphological form. The morphological structural analysis is an attempt made to capture the structure of language at the word level or concerned with the ‘forms of words’ (Matthew, 2000).

However, scholars as Ude (2010) and Enang (2010) have contributed to the socio-cultural importance of names and the philosophy of the people of Itu Mbon Uso but not much insight has

been given to the morphological aspect of Itu Mbon Uso personal names. This study, therefore, seeks to add another dimension to the study of names using the morphological patterns which agglutinate with affixes and other words to perform grammatical functions as a means of learning the grammar of the language. It aims to identify the morphological structure of Itu Mbon Uso personal names as well as discuss the morphological processes that constitute the names through the process of word formation. Invariably, naming is an aspect of a language, where new words and meanings are formed for posterity. However, one of the factors of language classification is genetics. Genetically, Itu Mbon Uso is classified as a Lower Cross Language of the Benue Congo sub family of the Niger Congo family of languages according to Greenberg (1963). It is a language which belongs to the Lower Cross Languages, which Ibibio, Efik, Ukwu also belong and form a cluster of languages. Itu Mbon Uso is a language as well as the people of the speech community. According to Ude (2010:26), “The people of Itu Mbon Uso can intelligibly speak the Ibibio and the Efik languages without learning them”. Itu Mbon Uso is a name of the people living in a distinct clan which comprises 12 communities and is situated in Ini Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, South-South geopolitical zone in Nigeria.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted was eclectic in nature, combining Morphological-Based Theory with Head Feature Convention theory for the morphological analyses. The morphology-based theory is a framework formulated by Charles Hockett in (1954). Hockett (1958:177) defines morphology as “the stock of segmented morphemes and the ways in which words are built out of them”. In morphology-based theory, words are divided into two classes viz: Item-and-Arrangement (IA) and Item-and-Process (IP). The type of classification crucial to this study is the Item-and-Arrangement theory (IA). The theory treats morpheme as the underlying unit of a word (Lieber, 1981, Di Sciullo & Williams, 1987). The theory segments roots (words) in a linear sequence into morphs. IA arranges morphemes and allomorphs in relation to each other as meaning elements to produce complex structures.

The Head Feature Convention (HFC) is a grammatical framework formulated within the Generalised Phrase Structure Grammar (GPSG) theory by Gazdar, Klein, Pullum & Sag, (1985) as an alternative to Transformational Grammar. HFC is a lexicalised or unification-based theory that has hetero-categorical heads and being a universal set of framework has only one level of syntactic description (constraint) that percolates from the head node (mother) to the subcategorisation node (daughter) (Benjamin, 2017). The theory describes category as sets of feature-value pairs combined with their complements to account for structures.

3. Methodology

This study is a qualitative descriptive design which describes the morphological and socio-linguistic nature of Itu Mbon Uso personal names. The population of this study was drawn from speakers of Itu Mbon Uso. Selected names for both males and females were chosen as data using purposive sample method. The research instruments employed included oral interview and participant observation with the researchers’ residual knowledge.

4. Discussion and Results

In this section, the data are specified based on the morphological constructs that constitute naming in Itu Mbon Uso. The data are analysed using the Item-and-Arrangement (IA) model of morphology-based theory and the Head Feature Convention (HFC) theory. The morphological

structure and processes which are productive in Itu Mbon Uso personal names are analysed below:

4.1 Affixation

This is a situation in which bound morphemes are added to the root word to either change or extend the function of the words (Benjamin, 2019). The personal naming process in Itu Mbon Uso indicates the position in which the affix occurs to the root word either as a prefix or a suffix to create a name. This can be explicated in the following ways:

4.1.1 Prefixation

This is a grammatical device or a word component which is attached as a bound morpheme before the root word to create new words as names such as:

1	Prefix	Verb root	Derivation (Name)	Gloss
a.	Í	bìóm -carry	Íbìóm	Eagle
b.	Ú	Úbòn - produce	Úbòn	Family
c.	È	dù - live	Èdù	Character

It could be deduced from example 1 that the prefixes attached to the root words are class changing. They change the categories of the basic forms (verbs) to derive nouns as names. The item-and-Arrangement (IA) theory relates the prefixes (morphemes) to the root words, which are segmented in a linear sequence to produce complex structures as names in Itu Mbon Uso. The examples can be illustrated using the Head Feature Convention as shown in the diagram below:

Fig. 1: Íbìóm ‘Eagle’

In Fig 1, the principle of the Head Feature convention theory illustrates the percolation process that results from the combination of the head node prefix ‘í’- and its subcategory ‘bìóm’ to derive a grammatical category noun Ibìóm as a name in Itu Mbon Uso.

Fig. 2: Úbòn 'Family'

In Fig 2, the diagram illustrates the head category 'ú' which percolates to the feature of the complement node (root word) 'bòn', to derive a noun as name Úbòn.

Fig. 3: Èdù 'Character'

From the diagram, Fig.3 demonstrates a percolation process where the head category 'È' - and the feature of the complement 'dù', merge to derive 'Èdù' as a name.

4.1.2 Circumfixation

This is a morphological process in which a discontinuous affix comprising two dissimilar parts surrounds an otherwise free morpheme (Mbah, 2012). It adds an affix to both sides of a host morpheme (verb root).

This can be considered below:

2. Prefix	Verb root	suffix	Derivation(Name)	Gloss
a. \acute{N}	dárá ‘rejoice’	ké	\acute{N} daráké	I am not rejoicing.
b. \acute{N}	sémé ‘lament’	ké	\acute{N} séméké	I am not lamenting.
C \acute{N}	dí ‘come’	yó	\acute{N} diyó	I come to wander.

From example 2, the verb roots are attached to the discontinuous affixes. The first marker of the circumfix is marked with the prefix ‘ \acute{N} ’, while the suffix takes variable negative markers, depending on the verb root. Using the Item-and-Arrangement model of morpheme-based theory, it could be deduced that the verbal derivands ‘dárá, sémé, dí’ are governed by the circumfixes to emerge a grammatical category as names. The examples can be diagrammatically represented using the Head Feature Convention (HFC) as:

Fig. 4: \acute{N} daráké ‘I am not rejoicing’

From the diagram, the verbal derivand ‘dára’ on which the features of the circumfixes percolate; intersect with the circumfixes ‘ \acute{N} -/ké’ to derive ‘ \acute{N} daráké’ as a name.

Fig. 5: \acute{N} séméké ‘I am not lamenting’

In Fig.5, the diagram illustrates the head category ‘ \acute{N} séméké’ as a consequence of the percolation of the features of the verb root ‘sémé and the features of the complement ‘ \acute{N} -/ké’ to derive

‘ \bar{N} séméké’, a grammatical category.

Fig. 6: \bar{N} díyó ‘I have come to wander’

The diagram demonstrates the percolation process between morphological forms. This means that the derivand ‘dí’ on which the features of the circumfixes percolate intersect with the circumfixes ‘ \bar{N} -/ké’ to derive a name, \bar{N} díyó.

4.2 Reduplication

This is a morphological process, which occurs partly as a full reduplication and as a partial reduplication. The addition of affixes is determined wholly or partly by the root word (base). It attaches an affix to the base through the copying of the full base or part of the base. It performs grammatical and semantic contrasts, e.g.:

3	N1	+	N2	Derivation (Name)	Gloss
a.	Tí ‘remember’	+	Tí ‘remember’	Títí	Remember.
b.	Àkpán ‘first son’	+	Àkpán ‘first son’	Ákpàkpán	First son.
c.	Ákán ‘victory’	+	Ákán ‘victory’	Ákákán	Victory.

It could be observed that the Item-and-Arrangement theory merges the first and the second noun into a noun + noun construction, which functions as names. There is a full reduplication in 3 (a), where the reduplicant copies the entire root word (CV) such that the derived form has two forms of combinations; the half of the base and the half of the reduplicant which functions to show intensity. There is a modification of the first noun through a deletion process in example 3 (b-c) based on the rule of the language. However, there is no semantic change to the structure of the constructions. The examples can be illustrated using the Head Feature Convention theory as:

Fig. 7: Títí ‘Remember’

From the illustration, there is a full reduplication. The reduplicant ‘Tí’ percolates to extend the root ‘Tí’ so as to derive a name ‘Títí’ at the same level of compatibility.

Fig. 8: Ákpàkpán ‘First son’

In Fig.8, it could be observed that the head category (reduplicant) ‘Ákpàn’ percolates to the second noun root ‘Ákpàn’ to derive a reduplicated form of a name ‘Ákpàkpán’.

Fig 9: Ákákán ‘Victory’

Here, the two free head features enter into a percolation process to produce a name as a grammatical category. This means that the head category reduplicant noun ‘Ákán’ percolates to the root ‘Ákán’ to emerge a name ‘Ákákán’- Victory.

4.3. Compounding

Compounding is a process of joining two independent root words to form a single word with a new meaning. It can be explicated in two forms as Adjective + noun and Noun +Noun as the following examples show:

4.3.1 Adjective + Noun Construction

This is a nominalization process whereby two root words (adjective and noun) are combined to form new words as names, e.g.

4	Adjective	+	Noun	Derivation (Name)	Gloss
a.	Étí ‘good’	+	Ídó	Étídó	Good Character
b.	Útíbè ‘miracle’	+	Ímá	Útíbímá	Marvellous love
c.	Ákwá ‘big’	+	Ímá	Ákwáímá	Great Love

In the examples above, there is a vowel height constraint which permits deletion on either side of the word boundary. Thus, in example 4(a-b) the vowels of the adjective get deleted because they are non-high vowels, while in example 4(c), the low vowel ‘á’ follows the high vowel ‘í’ at the word boundary without any deletion because of the presence of the identical tones on the contiguous vowels.

The IA theory combines two root words in a construction (Adjective + Noun) with independent meanings to form compound words (names) as its derivation. The examples can be represented on a tree diagram using the Head Feature Convention theory as follows:

Fig. 10: Étídó ‘Good character’

Fig.10 shows a percolation process that resulted from the combination of the head node ‘Étí’ and the subcategory node ‘ídó’ to generate a derivative as a name, ‘Étídó’.

Fig. 11: Útíbímá ‘Marvellous love’

From the diagram, it could be observed that there is compatibility between the feature of the head node and that of the subcategory. The adjective ‘Útíbè’ percolates to the noun ‘Ímá’ to emerge a derivative as a name, ‘Útíbímá’.

Fig. 12: Ákwáímá ‘Great love’

Here, the head node ‘Ákwá’ percolates to the complement (subcategory) ‘Ímá’ at the same level to derive a compound word as a name ‘Ákwáímá’.

4.3.2 Noun + Noun Construction

This is a nominalization process whereby two root words (noun and noun) attach to each other to form new words as names. E.g.

5	Noun	Noun	Derivation	Gloss
a.	Étté ‘father’	Ówó ‘Person’	Éttéwó	Someone’s father
b.	Ímé ‘patience’	Éyén ‘child’	Íméyén	A patient child
c.	Úbóñ ‘glory’	Ábásí ‘God’	Úbóñábásí	God’s glory

From example 5(a-c), it could be observed that two root words (noun and noun), which have independent meanings combine to form a single word as names in Itu Mbon Uso language. The Item-and-Arrangement theory shows the sequential arrangement of the morphemes to form the structure of names. The examples can be illustrated on diagrams thus:

Fig. 13: Éttéwó ‘Someone’s father’

Fig.13 demonstrates the percolation process that results from combining the head node ‘Étté’ and the complement ‘Ówó’ to produce ‘Éttéwó’ as a name.

Fig.14: Íméyén ‘A patient child’

Here, the two free head features enter into a percolation process to produce a grammatical category. This means that the first noun ‘Ímé’ percolates the second noun ‘Éyén’ to derive ‘Íméyén’.

Fig. 15: Úbóñábásí ‘God’s glory’

From the diagram, it could be observed that there is compatibility between the feature of the head category and that of the complement. The N1 ‘Úbóñ’ percolates to the N2 ‘Ábásí’ to emerge a derivative- ‘Úbóñábásí’.

4.4 Clipping or Truncation

This is a word formation process which involves a systematic shortening or deletion of a defined portion of the base words. It is a non-changing category derivation with the same semantic and grammatical content. It is exemplified in the following examples as:

6	Root word	Clipped word	Gloss
a.	Áffíóñmá	Áffí	A female child born on Áffíóñ day.
b.	Ñyáúdó	Ñyá	One who is endowed to sing.
c.	Ádàísóñ	Ísóñ	He, who owns the soil.

From example 6, it is observed that the root words undergo the process of shortening some syllables to have but a clipped form without any grammatical contrasts. This clipped form has been accepted in general usage of Itu Mbon Uso words (names). The Item-and-Arrangement theory shows the sequential arrangement of the morphemes constituted to derive names of noun grammatical category in the Itu Mbon Uso language. The examples can be represented on diagrams using the Head Feature Convention theory as:

Fig. 16: Áffí ‘A female born on Áffíóñ-day’

In Fig. 16, the feature of the head node ‘Áffíóñmá’ is the noun root, which is clipped through a percolation process to the feature of the clipped node ‘Áffí’ with the same class category and meaning.

Fig. 17: Ñyá ‘One who is endowed to sing’

From the illustration, there is a percolation process where ‘**N**yaúdí’ becomes clipped through a percolation process to derive ‘**N**ya’ with the same class category and meaning.

Fig. 18: Ísòñ ‘He, who owns the soil’

From the diagram, it could be observed that the head category ‘Ádàísòñ’ becomes shortened to the feature of the clipped node ‘Ísòñ’ through a percolation process with the same meaning and functions.

5. Conclusion

This study has shown that naming is part of the grammar of a language. It described the morphological components that constitute the structure of Itu Mbon Uso personal names. The morphological processes predominant in the names are derivational in nature which include affixation, reduplication, compounding and clipping. It was observed that although clipped names have the same grammatical and semantic information; they actually intensify the degree of intimacy between the bearer and the parents. The lexical categories like verbs, adjectives and nouns constitute the root words which form the names. There is an instance of phonological process, deletion which occurs in compounding as a result of vowel height at the word boundary. The Item-and-Arrangement (IA) was used as a tool to segment root words in a linear sequence into morphs to derive names as part of the grammar of Itu Mbon Uso. The Head Feature Convention theory was used to analyse heads as obligatory elements, which merge to generate names. Consequently, the analysis of the morphological structure of Itu Mbon Uso personal names has provided insights into the historical background of the Itu Mbon Uso people.

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Substitutional Cohesion and Problem of Usage in ESL Environment: Insights from Ika and English Languages

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Abstract

Language is a highly structured phenomenon and languages can differ in their internal structural patterning. The differences in language structures may likely create problems for second language learners. It is in this light, that the present study compared the substitution cohesive system in English and Ika. Ika is an Igbooid language spoken by the Ika people of Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. The study was carried out with the aim of improving the learning of English text translation and English as a second language by Ika speakers. The study generated English sentences with different types of substitution which were then translated into the Ika language. Findings from the study among others, revealed that the main problem Ika learners of English as second language encountered was in the verbal substitution; the main problem being that the Ika speakers of English were not able to know how and when to use the different morphological realisations of the English verbal element *do* and its variant forms (*does, did, doing, done*). This is because, in the Ika language, there is only a verbal element *meh* which translates to the English *do* which does not have any other morphological realisations.

Keywords: cohesion, substitution, teaching environment, insight

1. Introduction

Cohesion, in language study, borders on the internal connectivity that exists in a language which enables language users to join different strands of utterances in order to communicate or to make meaning. Cohesion aids the language users to tie what has been said to what is being said and also makes what would be said relevant. The cohesive system, like most language systems and features usually, differ from language to language. The differences create problems for the second language learners. For ESL learners and users, the first language and the cohesive system that are obtainable in the system usually interfere with the English language. It is therefore the duty of language scholars and teachers to properly interpret the cohesive systems in different languages and contrast same with other languages to see points of convergence and divergence. It is on this basis therefore that the current study investigates the substitutional cohesion in the Ika and English languages.

The English language today is a powerful tool for communication not just within inter-ethnic Nigerians but with those outside the shores of the nation. In the views of Elizabeth Erling and Tom Bartlett 'English has come to be commonly known as the global lingua franca. The language is noted for its international use and for the fact that non-native speakers of English outnumber native speakers three to one' (70 qtd. in Nkem Okoh 27). Due to the high demand on the English language, there is a great need to learn and use the language properly. Many are approaching the learning of the language after acquiring a first language. The Ika people who use

the Ika language in the Northern part of Delta State and some parts of Edo State, Nigeria belong to this category. The Ika speakers need to use the English language to communicate to other persons of different ethnic origins and others outside the nation. Hence, there is a need to learn the English language. Also, there is a great need to translate texts to and fro both languages. There is a great need to study the two languages in a contrastive sense to ensure smooth translations. On this basis the study is very significant.

1.1 Objectives

The main objectives of the study are to:

- a. identify the nature of substitutional cohesion in both the Ika and English languages
- b. examine the differences of substitutional cohesion in both languages
- c. examine the similarities in substitutional cohesion in both languages
- d. predict possible areas of problem for ESL users of Ika extraction.

1.2 Research Questions

- a. What is the nature of substitution cohesion in the Ika and English languages?
- b. To what extent is the substitutional cohesion in the Ika language different from the one in the English language?
- c. To what extent is the substitutional cohesion in the Ika language similar to the one in the English language?
- d. What are the possible areas the Ika language ESL user would face difficulties in using the English substitutional cohesion?

2. Halliday's Cohesion in Language

Cohesion in language study borders on the internal connectivity that exists in a language which enables language users to join different strands of utterances. Cohesion aids the language users to tie what has been said to what is being said and also makes what would be said relevant. In a larger sense, cohesion moves beyond the lexical items and the grammatical rules in a language though they contribute largely in making a language meaningful. Cohesion can be done pragmatically, where the context enables the language users to tie the different strands of utterances in order to be semantically relevant to the users.

According to Elizabeth Traugott and Mary Pratt, the earliest study of cohesion in English was conducted by Roman Jakobson, who analyzed the syntactic structure and parallelism in literary texts with reference to poetry (21). In 1964, it was Michael Halliday who first divided cohesion into grammatical cohesion and lexical cohesion. Later, Hasan made a detailed exploration into grammatical cohesion. Before the publication of Michael Halliday and Ruquiyatu Hasan's *Cohesion in English*, a number of other relevant cohesion studies became available. The method by which cohesion works in English are well exposed in the literature as we said earlier. (cf Halliday and Hassan, Henry Widdowson, Patricia Carrel, Michael Fulcher, Chinedu Emezue, Kim Ballard, Chun-Chun Yeh, Sanna-Kaisa Taskanen, Kerstin Kunz and Ekaterina Lapshinova-Koltunski, Destiny Idegbekwe, *cohesion...Obama's speeches* Destiny Idegbekwe, *cohesion...in the English and Ika languages* and others).

Halliday and Hassan identified five resources with which languages users cohere their speech. These resources include: reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction and the lexical cohesion (which include). The present study focuses on a comparison of substitution in English and Ika languages.

3. What is Substitution?

Substitution is the second cohesive device identified by Halliday and Hassan as part of four others (reference, ellipsis, conjunction and lexical cohesion) used in text connectivity. In the simplest way of defining substitution, one can say that it is the act of replacing a word with another or replacing an item with another. The major difference between substitution and reference is that substitution is a relationship that exists in the words whereas the reference exists in the meaning or semantics. In reference, one item is used in interpreting another. In substitution, an item is used in place of another. According to Halliday and Hassan:

Substitution is a relation between linguistic items, such as words, phrases; whereas reference is a relation between meanings. In terms of the linguistic system, reference is a relation on the semantic level, whereas substitution is a relation on the lexicalgrammatical level, the level of grammar and vocabulary, or linguistic ‘form.’ (89)

To further explicate the place of substitution in the linguistic level and to establish the difference between reference and substitution in the linguistic level, Halliday and Hassan (89) presents the table below for illustration:

Type of cohesive relationship	Linguistic level
Reference	Semantic
Substitution (including Ellipsis)	Grammatical

Generally speaking, there are three types of substitution- the nominal, verbal and the clausal substitution. The nominal substitution is the type of substitution used in replacing the head of a nominal group. There are three major nominal substitution examples in the English language and they include: *one, ones, same*. Just as the nominal substitution replaces the head of a nominal group, the verbal substitution replaces the head of a verbal group and can replace the other items in the group unlike the nominal substitution. The clausal substitution occurs in instances where a word replaces an entire clause. In the English language, two forms are usually possible for verbal substitution- so for the positive form and not for the negative form. The focus in this study is to examine if the substitution system in English is similar to the one in the Ika language. If there are differences, what possible problems would they pose for the Ika ESL learner/user?

4. Review of Literature

Many studies have not been carried out on the contrast between Ika and English in the area of substitution in a contrastive sense. However, there are available studies which dwell on the comparison of both languages but in different linguistic levels. These studies are reviewed in this section. Daniel Ogum and Destiny Idegbekwe pay attention to the differences and similarities existing between the English language and the Ika language in the area of reference as a cohesion marker. The study uses the Lexical and Grammatical cohesion Model proposed by Halliday and Hassan, and Andrew Chesterman’s Contrastive Functional Analysis (CFA) as the theoretical frameworks. The study establishes the similarities and differences in the functions and layout of referencing cohesive elements in the English language and Ika language. The study presents amongst other findings that the use of cataphoric reference in English and Ika are only similar if the referencing items are in the same clause. While the Ika language can only make cataphoric reference within the clause, the English language can make cataphoric reference within and outside clause boundaries.

In similar study, Destiny Idegbekwe and Lynda Ambrose focus on the contrast between English and Ika in the use of ellipsis as a cohesion marker in both languages. The study is done in order to determine the possible differences in the two languages in the area of ellipsis cohesion that would cause problems for second language learning of English. The study examines a total of fourteen sentences in both languages and concludes that the three types of ellipsis cohesion (nominal, verbal and clausal) are all possible in the two languages. However, the main difference which Idegbekwe and Ambrose note stems from the fact that the Ika language cannot use the verbal and clausal ellipsis in a negative clause and in clauses where the main verb is in the present form, the Ika language tend to repeat the main verb without ellipting any element. This study is of the opinion that this difference would not cause any serious problem to ESL of Ika extraction as they can decide to use the repeated forms which is permissible in English too.

The two cited works above are somewhat similar to what is done in the present study. The main difference however stems from the fact that the focus here is on substitution instead of reference cohesion which Ogum and Idegbekwe investigate or ellipsis cohesion which is the focus of Idegbekwe and Ambrose. The overall idea here is to account in separate studies, the differences and similarities of the cohesive devices in the two languages with the idea of improving the learning of English as a second language through a comparison of the L1 of the potential learner/user and the target L2.

In another study, Rosemary Chiedu examines the syntactic interference of Ika on English usage of Ika native L1 using thenoun phrase (NP) structure of both languages in focus. The study reveals that Ika and English NP structures at the simple noun phrase level have glaring differences which can cause interference LI (first language) on L2 (second language) and if not properly addressed, native speakers of Ika are likely to encounter problems whenever they want to use the noun phrase to make sentences in English Language.

In another study, Joy Uguru (*Nasal vowels in Ika Igbo*) investigates the low rise and high rise intonation in English and Ika using the PRAAT system of acoustic analysis. In carrying out the study, monosyllabic, disyllabic and short utterances made in two rising intonation patterns in English and Ika – Low Rise and High Rise - were recorded from two male native speakers of Ika and one native speaker of English. These were analysed using the PRAAT system. Findings from Uguru's study show that the curves of the two tunes in Ika, a predominantly tone language, and English an intonation language, are generally similar. This confirms that Ika manifests intonation thus revealing that a tone language can, to a large degree, manifest features typically associated with intonation languages.

Lastly, Uguru (*Harmonics to noise ratio in Ika Igbo and English utterances: Implications and inferences*) focuses on the harmonics to noise ratio in Ika and English utterances with emphasis on interferences. In the study, sixteen utterances comprising eight Ika utterances and eight English utterances were produced and fed into the computer. The cross-correlation method of analysis is used to obtain their harmonics to noise ratios. The analysis reveals that generally, the English utterances have higher harmonicity values than those of Ika with the difference being more marked in some intonation patterns than the others. Furthermore, the only Ika utterance with higher harmonicity value had more nasal sound than its English counterpart.

While the study of Chiedu and that of Uguru are similar because they compare the Ika and English languages in order to improve the learning of English in an ESL sense, they are different

from the present study because they do not cover what the differences and similarities are in the areas of substitutional cohesion.

5. Methodology

The research design which this study adopts is the descriptive design. A descriptive study is one in which information is collected without changing the environment (not manipulating the data). We are adopting this type of design because descriptive studies are mainly conducted to demonstrate associations or relationships between two entities. In this case, there is an attempt to look at the relationship between the substitution system in the English language and that of the Ika language to see if they are similar or different. Sixteen (16) English sentences containing substitutional cohesion were generated by the researcher. These sentences were then given to Ten (10) teachers who are competent in both languages to translate into the Ika language. This was done to increase objectivity. The English sentences and the translated forms serve as the primary data for the study. In analysing the data in this research, the researcher presented sentences where substitution is used in the English language then, contrasted with the translated forms in the Ika language to see if they are present in the Ika form. To properly show the differences and similarities between the two languages in the course of the analysis, the researcher drew up a template known as the Ika-English Cohesive Contrastive Template (IECCT). The template works in such a way that it enables the study to place English sentences containing the resource of substitution identified by Halliday and Hassan for cohesion in the English language and in turn, show the translated sentences in the Ika language reflecting the cohesive items in both languages. In the sentences where the resource is not available in the Ika language, the template shows the equivalent construction in the Ika language which shows a similar meaning in the English language. This is done because there are possibilities that all the substitution strategies and resources in the English language are not available in the Ika language.

6. Presentation of Data and Analysis

There are three types of substitution as identified by Halliday and Hassan. They include the nominal, verbal and clausal substitution. We are going to look at the three types of substitution in the two languages under comparison here using the IECCT to see the extent to which they are similar or different.

6.1 Nominal Substitution

Table 1: showing the IECCT for English-Ika nominal substitution contrast

S/no	English Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Items	Translated Ika Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Item
1	Emeka bought four <u>balls</u> and, two green <u>ones</u> and two blue <u>ones</u>	Nominal Substitution	Balls, ones	Emeka ghon <u>bolu</u> eno: <u>nke</u> ogi ebwo le <u>nke</u> ocha ebwo	Nominal Substitution	Bollu, nke
2	I thought I was through with my <u>job</u> . You did not tell me of <u>this one</u>	Nominal Substitution	Job, this one	Nte ro ni arun gwo m <u>orun</u> m. ye gwa nim <u>hun</u> ni	Nominal Substitution	Orun, hun ni

3	I like your hair <u>style</u> . I will make the <u>same</u> for myself tomorrow	Nominal Substitution	Style, same	Ishi imeme swo mu swo. Nke me <u>hun ni</u> ekile	Nominal Substitution	Ishi, hun ni
4	We do not have big <u>onions</u> here; only small <u>ones</u>	Nominal Substitution	Onions, ones	Enyi e wen <u>arabasi</u> ihie ogbe ebeni; <u>nke</u> chukpe chukpe swo	Nominal substitution	Arabasi, nke

The nominal substitution is the type of substitution used in replacing the head of a nominal group. There are three major nominal substitution examples in the English language and they include: *one*, *ones* and *same*. They function as heads of a nominal group and they can only replace a head of a nominal group. The nominal substitution in English as we can see above from the template makes use of *ones*, *one* and *same* while the Ika language makes use of *nke* and *hunni*. The only difference is in the fact that there is no different word for same and ones in the Ika language. Instead, *nke* is used for both situations.

The main question is: it possible for the nominal group to be substituted in the two languages, the answer is yes. In Table 1, sentence 1 uses *balls/bollu* which is the head of the nominal group is substituted by *ones/nke* ‘twice’ in the sentence and as such, the new item becomes the head of the nominal group without the other qualifying elements. One can interpret *ball/bollu* with *ones/nke*. In sentence 2, *this one/hun ni* substitutes *job* and they can be interpreted as the same. It is difficult to use one without a modifier because *one* requires at any point in time to be defined properly. So, in the English language *this*, *the*, *a new one* can be used while the Ika language introduces *ni* after *hun*. In the real sense, *one* is the main substituting item in the sentence replacing *job* which is the head of the nominal group. In sentence 3, *same/hun ni* replaces *style/ishi* but in the Ika language *hun ni* literarily means *this one* which makes the means for nominal substitution in the language to be two *nke* and *hun ni* unlike the English *one*, *ones*, *same*.

6.2 Verbal Substitution

Just as the nominal substitution replaces the head of a nominal group, the verbal substitution replaces the head of a verbal group and can replace the other items in the group unlike the nominal substitution. To investigate the differences and similarities of this type of cohesive device in the English language, we would use sentences from the the IECCT for illustration.

Table 2: showing the IECCT for English-Ika verb substitution contrast

S/no	English Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Items	Translated Ika Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Item
5	They did not come the way they usually <u>do</u>	Verbal substitution	Do	Abia ni wey ki wey gi e <u>meh</u>	Verbal substitution	Meh
6	Does your mother look for you every time? She can't <u>do</u> in the morning.	Verbal substitution	Do	Nne yi achor yi owehile? Oseka <u>meh</u> ozo ototun	Verbal substitution	Meh
7	Isioma talked the whole day; the way he usually <u>does</u>	Verbal substitution	Does	Isioma kwu oku owehile ki oge <u>meh</u>	Verbal substitution	Meh
8	The lady comes here every night. Really, she <u>does</u> ?	Verbal substitution	Does	Okpoho ahun abia ebeni imu uhien ile. Ezioku, o <u>meh</u> ?	Verbal substitution	Meh

From the template above, it is obvious that the main verbal substitute in the English language is *do* and its different morphological realizations. On the other hand, the verbal substitute in the Ika language is *meh*. *Meh* plays the role of all the morphological realizations of the *do* primary auxiliary verb and does not inflect for number unlike the English verbal substitute *do*.

Just as the nominal substitution replaces the head of a nominal group, the verbal substitution replaces the head of a verbal group and can replace the other items in the group unlike the nominal substitution. In Table 2, sentence 5, the *do/meh* verbal substitute replaces *come/bia* which is the head of the verbal group in the sentence. Though *meh* can act as a verbal substitute in the Ika language, there is another way of saying it which is more frequent or more likely to come from the speakers. It involves the repetition of the verb itself to read as: *Abia ni wey ki wey gi abia (they did not come the way they usually come)*. In the case of the above, there is no verbal substitution. It is a case of verbal repetition. One might wonder why we are using the other form in the template. The form in the template comes from translated sentences from the respondents we used for translating sentences. They likely transformed the sentences according to what is in the English sentences before them (aiming for conformity perhaps) and we must state that the translated is not wrong in itself but not the most common way of saying it. The most common way of saying sentence 7 (*Isioma talked the whole day; the way he usually does*) in the English language is by replacing the verbal group with the substitute *does*. If it is said the other way round such as: *Isioma talked the whole day; the way he usually talks the whole day*, it is not wrong or meaningless in the English either. In the Ika language, the most common of saying it is without the verbal substitute and it requires verbal repetition. Using the verbal substitute in the Ika language is possible, grammatical and meaningful. This duality in verbal repetition and

substitution is not possible in the Ika language with the clausal substitution that involves *not* which we would see very soon. So, we can agree that there is verbal substitution in the Ika language just as it is in the English language. But again we must state that the Ika language does not have different morphological realizations like the English *do* (*does, did, doing, done*). *Meh* is the only item in the Ika language.

6.3 Clausal Substitution

The clausal substitution occurs in instances where a word replaces an entire clause. In the English language, two forms are usually possible for verbal substitution- *so* for the positive form and *not* for the negative form. We would contrast sentences from the English language and the Ika language to investigate the possibility of this phenomenon on both languages.

Table 3: showing the IECCT for English-Ika clausal substitution contrast

S/no	English Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Items	Translated Ika Sentence	Cohesive Type	Cohesive Item
9	I believe Emeka would be in the church now. Do you believe <u>so</u> ?	Clausal substitution	So	M kweri ni Emeka ka ri ime oka. Ye kweri <u>erira</u> ?	Clausal substitution	Erira
10	He is out there in the forest. I think <u>so</u> .	Clausal substitution	So	O ri ime egboko. M ro <u>erira</u> .	Clausal substitution	Erira
11	Whether you voted for me or <u>not</u> , I will perform.	Clausal substitution	Not	Ki itwu ye nim ya tu ye nim, m ke me ohunma	None	None
12	Whether Emeka would play or <u>not</u> is a serious question.	Clausal substitution	Not	Ke Emeka ka gba ogba ni wu oken ajuju	None	None

The clausal substitute involving the positive form using *so/erira* is possible in both languages without any significant difference. This can be seen in sentences 9 and 10 while the clauses with negation are not possible in the Ika language which is evident in sentences 11 and 12. A clear demonstration of the clausal substitution in both languages is in Table 3, in sentences 9 and 10 where the word *so/erira* replaces the clausal element *that Emeka would be in church/ kweri ni Emeka ka ri ime oka* in the second clause in sentence 9. In sentence 10, *so/erira* also replaces the clausal element *that he is in the forest/o ri ime egboko* in the second clause. In both languages, there are no changes in the meaning as the second clause contains *so/erira* is interpreted from the first clause. Where the difference lies is in the negative clausal substitution in the two languages. The negation system in the Ika language does not permit the occurrence of only the negating item without the word or action it is negating. In the English language *not* is a major negating item and while performing as a clausal substitute, it can occur alone standing in for the clause as

we can see in sentence 11: *whether you vote for me or not...* the word *not* substitutes the clause: *you did not vote for me* and it performs the ‘substitutional’ function without repeating the lexical verb in the previous clause. In the Ika language however, the negating item *ni* cannot function alone without the action. Translating sentence 11 in the Ika language would generate: *ki tu ye ni m ya tu ye ni m* where the main verb *tu* (*vote*) is repeated in the second clause instead of being substituted just like the English form. The same thing occurs in sentence 12. In the English sentence, *not* replaces the clause: *whether Emeka would not play* without repeating the word *play*. In the Ika language, sentence 12 would read as *ko ogba o gba ni* where the verb *gba* (*play*) is repeated in the second clause that should have been substituted in the first. So, it would be very strange to say there is clausal substitution in the Ika language as what is in the language from the analysis shows no evidence of such. Instead, a case of lexical cohesion through repetition or conjunctive use which may require further investigation. As a way of summarizing our analysis on substitution, it is right to say that substitution is present in the Ika language and the English language. But in the Ika language only the nominal substitution and the verbal substitution are possible though that of the verbal substitution is rare in the language but it is a possible and meaningful construction in the language. What is different here between the English language and the Ika language is in the area of clausal substitution. It exists in the English language but not in the Ika language.

7. Possible Problems in the Use of Substitution for the Ika ESL User

Substitution is the use of a word in place of another without affecting the meaning or causing confusion. From our analysis, it is possible in both languages. The Ika speaker might find the use of substitution easy especially the nominal and verbal substitution because they are similar in both languages. However, the main problem the English as second language learner with L1 in Ika would encounter in the use of verbal substitution is the problem of navigating and when to use the different morphological realizations of the English verbal substituting item *do* (*does, did, doing, done*) since in the Ika language, there is only an item *meh*. This is more revealing in the table below:

Table 4: showing the IECCT for English-Ika substitution system contrast

s/no.	English sentence	Cohesive type	Cohesive items	Translated Ika sentences	Cohesive type	Cohesive items
13	I smiled the way he <u>smiles</u>	Substitution	smiles	M mu ko gia <u>mu</u>	Substitution	Mu
14	I sang the way he <u>does</u>	Substitution	Does	M bu ko gia <u>bu</u>	Verbal repetition	*bu (sings)
15	John wrote the way they <u>did</u>	Substitution	Did	Joni dey ki we gia <u>dey</u>	Verbal repetition	*dey (writes)
16	The children were talking the way he <u>was</u> .	Substitution	Was	Nmudu ahun re ku ke we gia <u>ku</u>	Verbal repetition	*Ku (talk)

In the table above, it can be seen that the Ika language equivalent of items substituted in English is a repetition of the verbal items in the second clause which would definitely sound redundant in English. There is no different verb realisation for *do*, *does*, *doing*, *did*, *done* and *didn't*. What we see in Ika is the main verb being used not even alone but with other items in the initial clause. If the main verb is used alone in the Ika language, it would be very awkward and the meaning would be lost. This could lead to generating sentences such as:

I sang the way he sang

The children were talking the way he was talking

John wrote the way they wrote

Also, the Ika ESL learner/user might generate sentences with the wrong morphological forms. Some of the sentences can be any of the ones below showing negative transfer:

I slept yesterday the way they do

**I slept yesterday the way he do*

**I slept yesterday the way he has always do*

** I slept yesterday the way he has been do*

For an advanced learner or user of English, this type of sentence formation might sound strange and unimaginable but for a new learner there is a confusion as to when to use any other form apart from *do* which is like a gloss or surface substitute for *meh* in the Ika language.

The other aspect we would consider in terms of problems is in the use of clausal substitution but we would focus primarily on the use of negation. The negation system in the Ika language does not allow the use of the negating elements alone to substitute for the clause earlier used. Instead, the clause or the verbal part of the clause would come up again to complete the expression. Due to this systemic difference the Ika native speaker who is learning the English language might not be able to use the clausal form efficiently without repeating the verb just like the native Ika language. It might be a problem of stylistic or variation uses but repeating the verbal form can still communicate though it might sound redundant.

8. Conclusion and Recommendation

Our focus in this study has been to contrast the substitution cohesion in both English and Ika to see if the differences would bring possible problems for the ESL of Ika extraction. The study concludes that the main difference lies in the verb substitution of the *do support* system of English and all the morphological realisations that are not in the Ika language. This possibly can create problems for the ESL as there is an extra effort to learn or determine when to use the various morphological forms. The inability to understand this would lead to the usage of sentences with the wrong morphological form of the verbal substitute *do*. The study hence recommends that ESL teachers teaching those with Ika as L1 should read up or study the verb system of the Ika language in order to gain more insight before teaching.

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Language Ideology and Language Choice in the Oṛo Community: A Report from Fieldwork

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Abstract

This study investigated language ideology as a factor which influences language choices in multilingual discourses in the Oṛo community. Ten events were attended in the community which also accompanied the distribution of fifty questionnaires to members of the community. Using SPSS for collation and interpretation of data, it was discovered that 82 percent of the study population made language choices based on importance played by that language as well as the intended outcome of the conversation. 10 percent chose language randomly and 8 percent thought that it did not matter choosing any language during interaction.

Keywords: language, choice, ideology, policy, discourse

1. Introduction

This paper focuses on the influence of language ideology on choices made by members of the community in interactions. Being a sort of a steady multilingual community induced by many factors, members of this community employ more than two different languages or varieties in a single conversation. Although I am a community member who speaks in the community and beyond, never has it crossed my mind that certain decisions I make daily in my interactions were simply ideologically motivated until I looked at my data. I had included some questions which could trigger issues pertaining to peoples' ideas about the languages in the community and language attitude in the questionnaire (see appendix). It was until I started the collation and keying in of the responses on my laptop that I understood certain things I have always regarded as normal.

Language ideologies have been key factors in any language study in Nigeria and Africa. Ideology can be seen as a set of opinions or beliefs of a group or an individual. Very often *ideology* refers to a set of political beliefs or a set of ideas that characterise a particular culture. Language is a medium of ideological forces. Ideologies form the basis of the belief systems or social representations of specific groups. Gal (1992 p. 445-446) observes that "Ideology is conceptualized - implicitly or explicitly - not only as systematic ideas, cultural constructions, commonsense notions, and representations, but also as the everyday practices in which such notions are enacted; the structured and experienced social relations through which humans act upon the world".

In describing language ideology, Silverstein (1979) states that "ideologies about language, or linguistic ideologies, are any sets of beliefs about language articulated by the users as a rationalization or justification of perceived language structure and use". This is particularly true where members of a given language group believe in the use of a particular language without questioning why it has to be so. See Milroy (2001) on the belief of Standard English as the "purest" form of language.

Wolff observes that Africa is highly ideologised in terms of two main positions. This ideology stem from several factors which range from mental effects of colonial languages to language policies and individual preferences. This paper argues that language choices and use in the Oyo community are affected positively and negatively by the community's perception of language. Some of the questions that beg for answers are: what has caused these language perceptions? Why are some languages granted official recognition and others not? Could some of these perceptions be politically laced? Based on what follows, I shall attempt to answer the questions by looking at what has been said and done through the eyes of an insider.

2. Language Perception/Language Attitude

Whichever position a language user adopts in Nigeria is as a result of how the language(s) adopted is perceived. Several factors are responsible for these perceptions about languages in Nigeria. As a multilingual nation, Nigeria has over 500 languages and 380 ethnic groups. Out of these languages, the government in an attempt to select an indigenous national language made a policy that recognizes three languages as major languages of the country in addition to English which is the official language. This was done using such criteria as speaker number, level of development- i.e. in terms of orthography and texts. This move by government was seen as unpatriotic by the speakers of the so called "minority languages" and therefore makes the speakers of these languages feel their languages are inferior. Under this sub heading, I shall pursue my argument by examining the perceptions along certain named languages in and conditions in Nigeria.

3. Language Ideology Based on Prestige

Ayeomoni (2012 p. 2) observes that the functions assigned to a language or languages enhance the prestige of such languages. In Nigeria, for instance, languages like Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo and English have such elevated and prestigious statuses than other over four hundred remaining languages. Ability to use some or all of these languages gives people some added advantage in the nation, especially when applying for jobs. At the state level, various languages are assigned distinct functional roles at several hierarchical levels of usage, that is, each of the languages has domains of use different from the others. They are assigned roles based on their prestige and status. For a better understanding of this argument, I will consider some of the languages which concern this research in their different domains.

4. English Language Ideology

The English language is Nigeria's official language as well as the language of the colonialists. It serves as a second language to most Nigerians and just recently as first language to some children whose parents are very highly educated and perhaps also occupy a high status in government as can be seen in the questionnaire and participant observation reports. A lot of research work has been done on the role of English in Nigeria. It is very clear that English language remains the language of instruction in school, administration, business, politics, and even in learning a trade. This has made the role of English indispensable in Nigeria as Nigerians struggle against all odds to acquire as much English as is possible. This is much more the truth as English holds the key to any higher institution of learning in the country Nigeria. Not only is English valid in the mentioned environments but is seen as the key to success in business and in securing a good job in future. This disposition of English has led to so many ills in the country as everyone scrambles to secure a credit pass in English language sometimes at all cost. This position was also observed by Igboanusi and Peter (2005 p. 18). Most people see English as 'an important resource for self-enhancement, social and political empowerment and access to

educational and job opportunities'. Consequently, several literate and semi-literate parents prefer exposing their children to the language even before they start school.

The sad thing about the English language saga is that it is spoken by a low percentage of the population, most of whom are highly educated. It is even sadder to see good speakers of NPE claiming to speak English as they do not seem to have a demarcation between English and NPE. Apart from a few elites, large numbers of those who claim to speak English actually speak it the same way they speak their indigenous languages. Their version is completely different from the Received Pronunciation by all standards. The elevated position of English has caused many people chose to speak or report English as their language irrespective of the way they speak it.

Recently, politicians have “hijacked” English idioms to season their speech. Even when majority of their audience are people with a low level of education, they still prefer to speak English not because they are not familiar with the indigenous languages, but because they want to show off their superiority and suitability to their opponents. This is so as the knowledge of English is synonymous with intelligence or advancement in education in Nigeria. This research discovers that due to the importance attached to some languages like English, many parents opt to speak this language to their wards at home and also prefer the choice of schools where English is spoken as a default language for their children. When asked why parents chose to interact with children at home using the English language, the response was usually a chorus of *we want them to do well at school*. The understanding of the parents is that having a good communication skill in English helps the children to perform well academically. The quest for a ‘credit pass’ in English language pushes some parents to seek assistance from a negative angle of either paying to influence the scores of their wards or bribing their way to the higher institutions. In spite of the seeming invasion or overwhelming influence of English over other languages in Nigeria, the truth remains that the language is ‘firmly entrenched’ in the psyche of most Nigerians as a language of prestige (Igboanusi 2008 p. 266).

5. Language Policy

The other thing that has led to ideology and language attitude in Nigeria as well as the community is the “less” effective language policy by the federal government of Nigeria. Provisions in language policy could have an impact on the choices of language and use. The consequences of language policy extend to families, schools and the general public. Besides, it is a known fact that prevailing language policy and ideology have impacts on the scope of multilingualism in society as well as how various languages and dialects are valued and used. Igboanusi (2008 p. 253) observes that “Societal choices in multilingual contexts are varied and may include language policy decisions on an official language, national language, language of education, the parliament, law court, commerce, media, etc”. As I have stated earlier the upgrade status of some languages into major and minor and regional languages has caused speakers to choose to speak a language which will make them more relevant than the local or regional languages. For instance, majority of people who ascend the throne of power in Nigeria are basically Hausa speakers from the Northern angle of the country. Today, it is not uncommon to see some daring politicians code-switch into Hausa to gain support from the ruling majority. Aside from the politicians, business people see this as an avenue to get more customers to patronize them which of course will result in more gain. Although the learning and or acquisition of any language to me is positive, yet the pronouncement of these languages, the promotion and government role are absolutely considered a negative influence over other languages.

6. Grouping the Country into Geopolitical Zones

Aghehisi (1984) observes that the sub division of the country into regions like the North, South, East and West has contributed to some attitudes to language. For instance, in the North, so many other ethnic groups which are not Hausa are being forced to learn Hausa which is a language associated with power. Since this is the case, if people are asked to choose which language they speak or like, their best bet might be Hausa. Aside from this, it is very likely that one could get a job as Hausa, Igbo or Yoruba graduate teacher because these languages are included in the policy and also taught in institutions like the universities. The case is not the same as far as minority languages are concerned. Given the rate of unemployment in Nigeria, people are forced to learn one of these languages to the detriment of the many others.

7. Ideologies Associated with Ethnic Languages

Adegbija (1997) points out that Nigeria has over 250 ethnic nationalities and about 400 indigenous languages in addition to English, French and NPE. There is often a misunderstanding and misinterpretation of language and ethnicity as there appears to be no clear dichotomy between the two in Nigeria. In view of this statement, Igboanusi (2008: 258) asserts that a “strong motivating factor for language choice is ethnic identification. People from the same ethnic group are usually elated to use their language for identification outside their “MT homeland”. Citing Adegbija (2004 p. 113) the author maintains that such ecstatic behaviour in language use is not restricted to Nigeria. However, when placed within the African context, this kind of language use becomes an extension of kinship relationships, which exist in this part of the world. Sometimes, this relationship is so extended that one who is only from the same ethnic group as the other person is perceived as his/her ‘brother’ or ‘sister’ simply because they speak the same language. They may not have come from the same state² or even to have known each other (Igboanusi 2008 p. 258).

A lot of people speak their ethnic languages because language truly is their identity. For instance in the Ọrọ community where a language is most times synonymous with place names, village people claim to speak the language that corresponds to the name of their village or clan names irrespective of what people think. The desire to preserve ethnic languages has not only promoted the languages but has actually influenced the way the people speak these languages which impinges on the choices they make.

Over the years, the Efik language and ethnicity have been claimed by the Ọrọ people despite the fact that geographical location places both people and languages at two different ends. The Efik is basically spoken by the Efik people of Cross River State on the other side of the Atlantic Ocean while the Ọrọ language is spoken by the Ọrọ people of Akwa Ibom State on the opposite side of the Atlantic. Rather than claim affinity and ethnicity with the Ibibio or Anaañ people who occupy the same state with them, the Ọrọ people chose to rather affiliate with the Efik. Even as this paper is being written, the Ọrọ people still write letters, court documents and other official matters which are not written in English in Efik. But I am yet to see any official document written in Ọrọ or Ibibio by the members of the Ọrọ community despite the fact that they are multilingual in all the languages within the region. The choice of Efik as a medium of writing and even the claim of ethnicity with Efik rather than Ibibio could simply be ideological.

8. Conclusion

This paper examined choices of about 50 participants in different speech events in the Ọrọ community. As a multilingual community faced with making different choices on daily interactions, members were observed to choose languages which best served their interest. For

instance, traders made choices depending on their customers' perceived language or ethnicity. Yet some others chose to code switch in as many languages as they deemed fit during conversations. One disturbing finding of this research was the fact that parents who do not have English in their repertoire forced themselves to speak some versions of English to their children when it was obvious they could do very well speaking Oro, Efik or Ibibio to these children. This situation would have been unnecessary had the government implemented the language provisions of the National Policy on Education where children were expected to learn in the language of the immediate environment in the first years of education. We, therefore call on the government to do more than just initiating a policy but rather enforce the policy which will make people appreciate their regional languages.

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On the History of the English Language: 400AD - 1600AD

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Abstract

English is a language that emerged out of the fusion of many related Germanic dialects. The objectives of this paper are: to highlight the various phases in the development of the English language, to demonstrate that Old Norse, under the Danish rule greatly enhanced the simplification of grammatical inflections in the English language. The framework under which this paper is discussed is historical revisionism. Historical Revisionism is a practice in historiography in with the intention is to recast the past activities in a particular academic field of study, with the purpose of re-appraising previous views or judgments in such a field. Data for this paper were collected from the library texts and the internet. Some of the findings of this paper are that: the English language is a product of the fusion of the West and North Germanic language families; Old English generated lexical items by the use of affixes; Old Norse facilitated the trimming of Old English grammatical cases; the Norman Conquest led to the introduction of French words in the English language; at a time, the English language that is used today was seen as a language of a socially depraved, illiterate and inferior people; some words in the English language are the result of the fusion of two languages (one supplying the stem and another the affix) ; the Celts are the aborigines of the British Isles. This paper recommends the study of the history of the English language in order to enable users of the language to better appreciate the language in its contemporary use.

Keywords: revisionism, history, traditional, scholars, phase

1. Introduction

History is a reflection of the past in order to give a better account of the present and to predict the future. The objective of this book is to help scholars appreciate the various phases that our dear English language has gone through to be what it is today.

2. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework that is used in this paper is; Historical Revisionism. According to Historical Revisionism (2018:1), “Historical revisionism is a practice in historiography in which a historian reinterprets traditional views of causes and effects, decisions and evidence”. Thus, the term historical revisionism is concerned with the re-interpretation of a historical record. It also means challenging the orthodox views held by professional scholars about a historical event, or introducing new evidence, or restating the motivations and decisions of past events in order to grasp a better view of the issue that is being discussed. In other words, historical revisionism is a recast of the past activities in a particular academic field of study, with the purpose to re-appraise past views or judgments in such a field. This is the background on which this paper is guided. Though, some have argued that the term ‘revisionism’ is used perjoratively by people who charge that revisionists are distorting the true historical records of a thing. Negationism is another term that is closely associated with historical revisionism. Negationism is a historical

attempt to debunk propaganda or a false report/image of an event or situation. This paper is set to state facts about the progressive developments in the English language and not to debunk anything about it. Below, this paper shows that there has been a continuous line of developments from the Old English period, Old Norse, Norman Conquest (or Middle English), and Modern English periods.

3. Roman Presence in Britain

According to Baugh and Cable (2013:1), "... the history of English is a history of cultures in contact...". This means that it must be borne in the mind of scholars and users of the English language that the formation of the English is a union of numerous languages and people of different linguistic and social-cultural background. Baugh and Cable (2013:41), report that: "the first people in England about whose language we have definite knowledge are the Celts". This implies that the original owners of the land known as England are the Celts. The two divisions of the Celtic language are: the Gaelic or Goidelic branch and the Brythonic branch. Before the arrivals of the Germans on the British Isles, Latin was spoken in Britain for a period of about 400 years. Latin was introduced into Britain when it became a province of the Roman empire. This was under the reign of Julius Caesar in 55BC. The intent of Julius Caesar was to dissuade the Celtic Britain from coming to help the Celts in the Gauls though the attacks of Julius Caesar on the British Isles were not without loss on the part of the Roman Soldiers because the Celts also fought back the Romans. In fact it was recorded that the Celts refused to pay the tribute exerted on them by Julius Caesar. It was in AD43 that Emperor Claudius conquered a larger part of the British Island. The military conquest of Britain should have been followed by the Romanization of the province. Where the Romans lived and ruled, the Roman ways of life were found. Four great highways soon spread. One was from London to the north, the northwest, the west and the southwest. A fifth cut across the island from Lincoln to the Severn. Numerous lesser roads connected important military or civil centers or branched off as spurs from the main highways. A score of small cities and more than a hundred towns, with their Roman houses and baths, temples and occasional theaters testifying to the introduction of Roman habits of life. The houses were equipped with heating apparatus and water supply. Their floors were paved in mosaic and their walls were of painted stucco- all as in their Italian counterparts. In Britain, Roman dress, Roman ornaments and utensils, Roman pottery and glassware seem to have been in general use. By the third century AD, Christianity had made some progress in the island and in AD 314, bishops from London and York attended a church in Gaul. Romanization of the British people progressed peacefully except that it was cut short in 500AD. The Romanization of Britain means that the Latin language was in use in Britain and it was the official language of Britain, though mainly by well-to-do class after much resistance by the Britons unlike the Celtic Gauls who willingly spoke Latin as their official language.

With the withdrawal of the Roman legions in 410AD, the use of Latin began to reduce and became less officially functional.

4. The Germanic Tribes

During the Roman Empire, most of the Germanic tribes of northern Europe were not under the rule of the Romans except the south western parts. Irrespective of this situation, some German soldiers served in the Roman military and troops from Germanic tribes such as Tungri, Batavi and Frisii served in Britain under the Roman Command. With this situation at hand, Germanic settlement and domination took a toll during the Migration Period which occurred in the 5th to 7th century AD as a result of the collapse of the Roman Empire. About 449AD, Vortigern, king of

the Britons (Celtic king), invited the popular *Angle Kin*, led by the Germanic brothers: Hengist and Horsa to help fight the Picts who were attacking the British Isles. Vortigern in turn promised to give the *Angle Kins* lands on the Isle of Thanet Southeastern part of Britain for settlement. When the German soldiers saw that the land was comfortable, they expanded their territory by bringing the British Isle, more of their people. This wave of settlement led to the establishment of seven kingdoms called the *heptarchy*. The Saxons were settled in Essex, Wessex and Sussex; the Angles in East Anglia, Mercia and Northumbria; and the Jutes in Kent. The evidence of their settlement can be found in the number of place names throughout England ending with the Anglo-Saxon –ing suffix meaning people of, such as: Worthing, Reading, Hastings, the –ton suffix meaning enclosure or village such as: Tauton, Burton, Luton, the suffix –ford meaning a river crossing, in words like: Ashford, Bradford, Watford, the suffix –ham meaning farm in words like: Nottingham, Birmingham, Grantham, and suffix –stead, meaning a site as in Hampstead. The Germanic invasion of the British Isles began with the withdrawal of the Roman power from Britain. For more than a hundred year, bands of conquerors and settlers migrated from their continental homes in regions of Denmark and the Low Countries who came to establish themselves in the south and east of the island. This settlement gradually extended to the area of the highlands in the west and north. Bede in his Ecclesiastical History of the English People, which was completed in 731AD, reports that the Germanic tribes that conquered England were the Jutes, Saxons and Angles. From Bede, it seems possible that the Jutes and Angles had their home in the Danish peninsular; the Jutes in the northern part of Britain while the Angles in the south, in Schleswig Holstein and perhaps in small areas at the base. The Saxons were settled in the south and west of the Angles, roughly between the Elbe and Ems possibly as far as the Rhine. The Frisians occupied a narrow strip along the coast of Weser to the Rhine including the islands in that area. The Jutes lived near the Weser and were in contact with the Frisians and the Saxons. The Picts and Scots were in the North and were constantly at war with the German tribes on the British Isles, but the German tribes constantly fought back at them. According to Baugh and Cable (2013:45), “The Jutes who had not been softened by contact with the Roman’s civilization were fully a match for the Picts and Scots. In time, the Celts found out that the German tribes they invited to help them ward off their constant enemies –the Picts and the Scots had another terrible plan for them, and this plan was to completely dispossess them of their land by driving them away. To accomplish this, the German tribes invited other invaders who were also of the Germanic tribe to come into the British Isle. Under this situation, the Celts who were not strong enough to fight back their enemies were driven away to the Wales and Cornwall, while some migrated to Brittany.

The Presence of the German tribes brought about an abrupt end to the existing functional Roman civilization of the Celtic people who are the original owners of the British Island. The urban life established by the Roman for the Celtic people was destroyed and the people went back to farming, fishing and hunting. The minimum active unit in the society was the family and class distinction was made between the rich people called *eorls* and the low income persons called *ceorls* who were also called simple freemen. In the society, there were local assemblies by which justice was administered and punishment and fines were equally placed on culprits. These Germanic tribes having come to settle in Britain needed to communicate with one another. According to Gramley (2012:25), “It is not clear how distinct the differences among the four tribal groups of: Angles, Saxons Jutes, and Frisians may have been. They probably came as uncoordinated bands. ... However this may have been, it is unlikely that there were any major linguistic differences; all of the newcomers were speakers of North Sea Germanic, sometimes

also known as Ingvaenic”. In other words, Gramley notes that all the Germanic tribes were from the same linguistic group, hence spoke variants of the same language. This common utilization of regional dialectal differences enhanced communication since there was mutual intelligibility. Moreover, the common linguistic background of the invaders enhanced fraternity against the aborigines of the land. Despite regional dialectal differences, the language spoken by the four groups of the invaders of the British Isles was uniformly called *Englisc* which later was changed to English in conformity to Modern English orthography. This name of the new speech form in Britain was to show the shared culture and identity of amongst the invaders. The settlement of the Germans in Britain led to the formation of a hybrid culture of British –Saxon people. The new Anglo-Saxon nation, once known in antiquity as Albion and the Britannia under the Romans, nevertheless became known as *Anglaland* or *Englaland* (the land of the Angles), later became shortened to England, and its emerging language as *Englisc/Angliscor Anglo-Saxon* or sometimes called *Anglo-Frisian* (.cf. Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia). Irrespective of the hybrid culture, the conquered and the conqueror were still able to identify themselves. The Celts called their Germanic conquerors, Saxons because they had their first contact with the Germanic peoples through the Saxon raids on the coast. The invaders called the Celts *Weales* which means slaves or foreigners. But it is strange that an invader will call an aborigine a slave on his own land. This goes on to establish the extent to which the Celts were oppressed by the Germanic tribes. Over time *Angli* and *Anglia* became the usual names for all the Germanic tribes and which was used by Latin writers of that era. Prior to the Modern English era, the land and its people were called *Angelcynn*, Which means *Anglekin* or race of the Angles which continued to be used after the Danish rule. From about 1000AD, the word England which means land of the Angles began to be used instead of *Angelcynn* (*Anglekin/Angles*). A possible reason why the name England was taken from the Angle dialect or tribe of the German settlers because the Anglian kings were able to maintain their claim to be the kings of all the Germanic invaders now called the English people. cf. Baugh and Cable (2013: 44-45).

5. The Formation of the English Language

The history of the English language is divided into three periods. These divisions are based on the features which mark out each phase in the development of the language. The period from 450AD to 1150AD is called the Old English era. It is sometimes referred to as the phase or era of grammatical inflections. This is because the endings of nouns, adjectives and verbs were inflected for different grammatical notions. From 1150AD to 1500AD, is referred to as the Middle English. In this period much grammatical inflections were reduced. From 1500AD to 1600AD is known as the Modern English era. From 1500AD, the language had great vowel shifts and consonant changes. In Modern English, the large part of the grammatical inflections ceased to be functional. cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:48).

5.1 Old English

Old English is the form (type) of English spoken from 400AD -1150AD. According to Old English (2018:1), “Old English is one of the West Germanic languages, and its closest relatives are Old Frisian and Old Saxon. Like other old Germanic languages, it is very different from Modern English and difficult for Modern English speakers to understand without study. Old English grammar is quite similar to that of modern German: nouns, adjective, pronouns, and verbs have many inflectional endings and forms, and word order is freer. The oldest Old English inscriptions were written using a runic system, but about the 9th century this was replaced by a version of the Latin alphabet”. This tells one the English language has an original German

background with grammatical morphemes used to indicate different inflections of the language. The formation of the Old English language began with a fusion of languages or related dialects of Western Germanic origin between the Angles and the Saxons. This is why English language is said to have begun with the Anglo-Saxons. These Anglo-Saxons were a group of people who came from the Germanic tribes in the area of the: Netherlands, northern Germany, Dutch, Low German, Friesland, and Denmark, who spoke dialects of the whatof is called, West Germanic. The fact remains that before the arrival of the Anglo-Saxons, the original owners of the land who were the Celts, were already Romanized Celts who spoke Latin and their Celtic language (Welsh or Cornish). In spite of the presence of Latin and the Celtic language on the British Isles before the arrival of the Anglo-Saxons, they had no contribution on the formation of the English language and should therefore not be considered as the ancestors of the English language. The English language began as distinct language when the Anglo-Saxons broke off from their roots in Germany and other parts of Europe. One cannot deny the fact that the Celts had positive impact in the development of the English language. For instance it bequeathed its periphrastic structure to the language in the construction of the progressive or continuous aspect which is formed with a form of the verb *be*, and a present participle.

For example:

1a. I am going to the store.

As against the Germanic form

1b. I go to the store.

‘Ich gehe in den Laden’.

and not

1c. Ich bin gehende in den Laden’

‘I am going to the store’.

The Celts also influenced the English language in the use of the light or dummy verb, *do*, which is inserted where the subject-auxiliary verb inversion cannot hold. In the Germanic construction, one would have:

2a. Magst du Eis?

‘Like you ice cream?’

The English language form will insert a dummy verb *do*, to have;

b. ‘Do you like ice cream?’

cf. The Celts (2017: 1-5).

English is made up of four dialects: Northumbrian, Mercian, West Saxon and Kentish. The West Saxon dialect was the dialect of literature in the Old English era because the West Saxon kingdom was the domineering tribe. This domineering position was cut short by the Norman conquest which reduced all the dialects to a common level of unimportance. The pronunciation of Old English words is very difficult. This is because some of the characters used to represent sounds then are no longer in use in the present. The long vowels of Old English (OE), have changed and replaced with short vowels. For example: the Old English word *stān* is the same word as Modern English *stone*, but the vowel is different. This kind of change is found in the following words:

Table 1: Table illustrating Old English spellings

Old English	Modern English
3a. hālig	Holy
b. gān	Go
c. bān	Bone
d. rāp	Rope
e. hlāf	Loaf
f. bāt	Boat
g. fōt	Foot
h. cēne	Keen
i. mētan	Mete
j. fȳr	Fire
k. rīht	Ight
l. hū	How
m. hlūd	Loud
n. hēafod	Head
o. fōeger	Fair
p. sāwol	Soul

The changes in vowels resulted in changes in spelling. In Old English, the sound of ‘-th-’, was represented by the characters: *þ* (the thorn) and *ð* (the eth), as in the Old English word: *wiþ* (with) and *ðā* (then), which are no longer in use in contemporary English. The Old English, used digraph *æ* (ash) to represent the sound or letter *a*. But such strange characters are no longer in use in the present day English orthography. In Old English, the sound *sc* was used to represent the *sh* sound as in *sceap* (sheep), *scēotan* (shoot). The sound or letter *c* was used to represent *k* as in: *cynn* (kin), *nācod* (naked). *c* was also used for the affricates now spelled *ch* as in *sprōech* (speech), *eēg* (edge), *scip* (ship), *boec* (back), *benc* (bench) *þorn* (thorn) *þoet* (that) and so on. It has been observed that a major feature of Old English is “the rarity of those words derived from Latin and the absence of those from French which form so large a part of our present vocabulary”. This means that the vocabulary of Old English is almost purely Germanic. This is unlike what was obtained during the Norman Conquest, when the French brought into England, the French language as the language of the higher class, literature, the church, and law courts. On the grammatical markings of the language, the Old English grammar was an inflectional synthetic language. This is because it links the relationships in a construction mainly by grammatical morphemes attached to nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and verbs. An instance of such inflectional marking can be illustrated using the words below:

- 4a. murus ‘wall’
- b. muri ‘of the wall’
- c. muro ‘to the wall’

- d. murum ‘accusative’
cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:51-2).

The above grammatical inflection is typical of what is obtained in Modern German. The stem of the word is *mur-* to which the suffixes: *-us*, for the subjective/nominative case, *-i*, for the possessive case, *-o*, for the benefactive case, and *-um* for the objective case which have been attached to mark different grammatical forms of the noun *mur-* ‘wall’. Theoretically, the nouns and adjectives are inflected for four cases in the singular and four in the plural. In addition the adjective has separate forms for each of the three genders. The verb in Old English was inflected for different persons, number, tense and moods. In the Old English, the noun was inflected for case and singular and plural numbers. In the case system, there was no ablative, locative or instrumental case, these were all merged with the dative case. Examples of the four cases in Old English singular and plural nouns are given below:

Singular	Stone	Gift	Hunter
Nominative	5a. stān	6a. gief-u	7a. hunt-a
Genitive	b. stān-es	b. gief-e	b. hunt-an
Dative	c. stān-e	c. gief-e	c. hunt-an
Accusative	d. stān	d. gief-e	d. hunt-an
PLURAL			
Nominative	e. stān-as	e. gief-a	e. hunt-an
Genitive	f. stān-a	f. gief-a	f. hunt-ena
Dative	g. stān-un	g. gief-um	g. hunt-um
Accusative	h. stān-as	h. gief-a	h. hunt-an

Table 2: Table illustrating the singular plural case markings of English

5.2 Old English Gender

Old English also had grammatical gender which did not most times correspond to biological gender or to the nature of the thing that is marked. For examples:

- 8a. stān (stone, masculine)
- b. mōna (moon, masculine)
- c. sunne (sun, feminine)
- d. wefman (wife, masculine)
- e. mægden (girl, masculine)
- f. child (son, masculine).

The adjective in Old English had two different types of declensions: the strong and weak declensions. The strong declension is used with nouns when not accompanied by a definite article, a possessive or a demonstrative article. The weak declensions are used when the noun is preceded by a definite, possessive or demonstrative article. For example in Old English:

- 9a. gōd mann ‘good man’.
 b. sē gōda mann ‘the good man’.

The above, are forms of the nominative masculine in the strong and weak declensions respectively in (9a-b). In the examples below, strong and weak declensions of the adjective gōd ‘good’ in the various cases of: nominative, genitive, dative, and accusative cases are given:

Strong Declensions			
Singular	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Nominative	10a. gōd	11a. gōd	12a. gōd
Genitive	b. gōd-es	b. gōd-re	b. gōd-es
Dative	c. gōd-um	b. gōd-re	c. gōd-um
Accusative	d. gōd-ne	c. gōd-e	d. gōd
Instrumental	e. gōd-e		e. gōd-e

Table 3: Table illustrating the strong declensions in gender in the Old English

Weak Declensions			
Singular	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Nominative	13a. gōd-a	14a. gōd-e	15a. gōd-e
Genitive	b. gōd-an	b. gōd-an	b. gōd-an
Dative	c. gōd-an	c. gōd-an	c. gōd-an
Accusative	d. gōd-an	d. gōd-an	d. gōd-e

Table 4: Table illustrating the weak declensions in gender in the Old English

Plural Strong Declensions			
	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Nominative	16a. gōd-e	17a. gōd-a	18a. gōd
Genitive	b. gōd-ra	b. gōd-ra	b. gōd-ra
Dative	c. gōd-um	c. gōd-um	c. gōd-um
Accusative	d. gōd-e	d. gōd-a	d. gōd

Table 5: Table illustrating the strong declensions in the plural gender

Plural Weak Declensions			
	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Nominative	19a. gōd-an	20a. gōd-an	21a. gōd-an
Genitive	b. gōd-ena/ra	b. gōd-ena/ra	b. gōd-ena/ra
Dative	c. gōd-um	c. gōd-um	c. gōd-um
Accusative	d. gōd-an	d. gōd-an	d. gōd-an

Table 6: Table illustrating the weak declensions in the plural gender

The inflection of adjectives in the Old English is drastic difference of what is obtained in the contemporary English use. The definite article as a nominal grammatical category in the Old English was inflected for the markings of the masculine, feminine, neuter and a general gender form in the language. For example:

The Definite Article				
	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter	All Genders
Nominative	22a. <i>sē</i>	23a. <i>sēo</i>	24a. <i>ðæt</i>	25a. <i>ðā</i>
Genitive	b. <i>ðæs</i>	b. <i>ðære</i>	b. <i>ðæs</i>	b. <i>ðāra</i>
Dative	c. <i>ðæm</i>	c. <i>ðære</i>	c. <i>ðæm</i>	c. <i>ðæm</i>
Accusative	d. <i>ðone</i>	d. <i>ðā</i>	d. <i>ðæt</i>	d. <i>ðā</i>
Instrument	e. <i>ðȳ/ðon</i>	-	e. <i>ðȳ/ðon</i>	

Table 7: Table illustrating declensions of the definite article

Baugh and Cable (2013:55), note that: "... while the ordinary meaning of *sē*, *sēo*, and *ðæt*, is 'the', the word is really a demonstrative pronoun and survives in the modern English demonstrative 'that'. Its pronominal character appears in its use as a relative pronoun such as: *who*, *which*, *that* and as personal pronouns such as: *he*, *she* and *it*.

The Old English pronouns had distinctive forms for all genders, persons and cases. It also had a set of forms for two people or two things. This pronoun is called the dual number. Examples of the Old English pronouns are given in the table below.

Old English Singular Pronouns			
	First Person	Second Person	Third Person
Nominative	26a. <i>Ic</i>	27a. <i>ðu</i>	28a. <i>hē</i> (he) <i>hēo</i> (she) <i>hit</i> (it)
Genitive	b. <i>Mīn</i>	b. <i>ðin</i>	b. <i>his</i> , <i>hiere</i> , <i>his</i>
Dative	c. <i>mē</i>	c. <i>ðē</i>	c. <i>him</i> , <i>hiere</i> , <i>him</i>
Accusative	d. <i>mē</i> (<i>mec</i>)	d. <i>ðe</i> (<i>ðec</i>)	d. <i>hine</i> , <i>hie</i> , <i>hit</i>

Table 8: Table illustrating Old English singular pronouns

Old English Plural Pronouns			
	First person	Second Person	Third Person
Nominative	29a. <i>wē</i>	30a. <i>gē</i>	31a. <i>hīe</i>
Genitive	b. <i>ūser</i> (<i>ūre</i>)	b. <i>ēowes</i>	b. <i>hiera</i>
Dative	c. <i>ūs</i>	c. <i>ēow</i>	c. <i>him</i>
Accusative	d. <i>ūs</i> (<i>ūsic</i>)	d. <i>ēow</i> (<i>ēowic</i>)	d. <i>hīe</i>

Table 9: Table illustrating Old English plural nouns

Old English Dual Pronouns		
	First Person	Second Person
Nominative	32a. Wit (we two)	33a. git (ye two)
Genitive	b. uncer	b. incer
Dative	c. unc	c. inc
Accusative	d. unc	d. inc

Table 10: Table illustrating the Old English dual pronouns

cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:55).

5.3 Old English Verbal System

The Old English had two verb forms known as the strong and weak verbs. The strong verb form is called the irregular verb and weak verb form as the regular verb form. The irregular verbs were referred to as strong verbs because, the irregular verbs they could indicate the change of tense by a modification of their root vowel. An example of the irregular verb is: *sing, sang, sung*, while for the regular verb we have *play, played, played*. In the irregular verb form, the form of the verb is the same in the past tense and past participle. For example: *walk, walked, walked*, but in some others like: *take, took, taken*, the verb forms vary. In some others too, the verb form does not change at all as in: *bid, bid, bid*, or *put, put, put*. It distinguished only the past and present tense by grammatical inflections. It had no inflectional form for the passive form of the verb. The verbal system of the language at this time recognized: the indicative, the subjunctive and the imperative moods. The past tense in the Old English was formed by the addition of the suffix, *-ede, -ode, or -de* to the stem of the present tense, while past participle was formed by adding *-ed, -od, or -d* to the stem. For example:

Old English Simple Tense	Past Tense	Past Participle
34a. fremman (to perform)	35a. fremede	36a. gefremed
b. lufian (to love)	b. lufode	b. gelufod
c. libban (to live)	c. lifde	c. gelifd

Table 11: Table illustrating Old English simple past tense and past participle markers

5.4 Old English Vocabulary

The Old English vocabulary was very productive in nature. This is because in Old English a single root can be made to generate other words with extended meanings. For example the word *mōd* which means ‘mood’ (a mental state) which means ‘heart’, ‘mind’, ‘spirit’ ‘boldness’, courage, ‘pride’, and ‘haughtiness’. From it, by the addition of a common adjective ending *-ig*, was formed another word *mōdig* with a similar range of meanings such as: spirited, bold, high-minded, arrogant, stiff-necked. By another addition of the suffix *-lic*, which is also an adjective deriving suffix the word *mōdiglic* which means: magnanimous, with the suffix *-lice*, the adverb *mōglice* ‘boldly’ or ‘proudly’, with the suffix *-nes* the noun *mōdignes* is formed which means ‘magnanimity’, or ‘pride’. Another ending converted *mōdig* into a verb *mōdigian* meaning ‘to bear oneself proudly or exultantly or sometimes ‘to be indignant’ or to rage. Other forms

conveyed meaning whose relation to the root is easily perceived: *gemōdod* ‘disposed’, ‘minded’, *mōdfull* ‘haughty’, ‘and *mōdleas* ‘spiritless’. By combining the root with other words meaning ‘mind’ or thought, the idea of the word is intensified and one gets the words: *mōdsefa*, *mōdgeþarc*, *mōdgeþoht*, *mōdgehygd*, *mōdgemynd*, and *mōdhord* (the suffix *-hord* means treasure), all meaning ‘mind’, ‘thought’, ‘understanding’. Some sharpenings of the concept is obtained in *mōderæft* ‘intelligence’ and *mōderæftig* ‘intelligent’. Furthermore, the root *mōd* lent itself to the formation of other words by the combination of prefixes and suffixes. Some of these words include: *glædmōdnes* ‘kindness’, *mōdlufu* ‘affection’. The suffix *-lufu* means ‘love’. *unmōd* ‘despondency’, *mōdcaru* ‘sorrow’ The suffix *-caru* means ‘care’. *Mōdleast* ‘want of courage’, *madmōd* ‘folly’, *ofermōd* and *ofermōdigung* ‘pride’ *ofermōdig* ‘proud’, *hēamōd* ‘proud’, noble, and *mōdhetete* ‘hate’. The suffix *-hetete* means ‘hate’. *Micemōd* ‘magnanimous’, *swiþmōd* ‘great of soul. The suffix *-swiþ* means ‘strong’. *stifmōd* ‘resolute, obstinate’, *gufmōd* ‘warlike’, *torhtmōd* ‘glorious’. The suffix *-torht* means bright, and *mōdleof* ‘beloved’. The suffix *-leof* means ‘dear’. This generative capacity of the Old English words resulted in the presence of synonyms in the language. From this few example of the nature of the vocabulary of the Old English, one can see that it was more resourceful in utilizing its native words or stems than the Modern English which relies on the borrowing of words from other languages. Hence, in Old English ideas of any nature were easily expressed with ease.

5.5 Old English Syntax

The Old English syntactic structures had lexical items which served both as adverbs and conjunctions depending on the type of syntactic structure they attracted. If the sentence in which they occur is a simple one; that is paratactic in nature, then, it will be taken to be an adverb, but if it is a compound or complex sentence then it will be taken to be a conjunction, and the sentence will be taken to be hypotactic in nature. Thus, Old English *þa* at the beginning of a clause can be either an adverb translated ‘then’ and introducing an independent clause, or a subordinating conjunction translated ‘when’ and introducing a dependent clause. In the same vein *þær* can be translated as ‘there’ or where, *þonne* as ‘then’ or ‘when’, *swā* as ‘so’ or ‘as’, *æþ* as ‘formerly’, or ‘ere’, *siððan* as ‘afterwards’ or ‘since’, *nū* as ‘now’ or ‘now that’, *þeah* as ‘nevertheless’ or as ‘though’, and *forðām* as ‘therefore’ or ‘because’. In each pair, the first word is an adverb, and the style that results from choosing it is a choppy style with shorter sentences, whereas the choice of the second word, a conjunction, results in longer sentences with more embedded clauses. cf. Baugh and Cable (2013: 64).

5.6 Old English Literature

A wellknown literature in Old English is Beowulf. Beowulf is an epic poem of 3,000 lines. This poem is a reflection of the tradition of the early German settlers on the British Isles. The poem recounts of the heroic adventure relating how a young warrior, called Beowulf, fought a monster called Grendel, that was ravaging the land of king Hrothgar. Beowulf slew the monster and its mother, but years later, Beowulf met his death while riding his own country of a dragon that was spitting fire from its mouth. The theme of Beowulf centers on bravery and courage which depict the type of life that was lived in the Old English times. Other short poems of Old English literature talked of: war, exile, sea, ruined cities and of minstrel life. These all reflect the outlook and temper of the Germanic mind. According to Akmajian, Dermers, Farmer, and Harnish,

(2008, p. 339), “the English language has undergone extensive changes between the Old and Modern English periods”. Changes in grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary have made Old English no longer understandable to speakers of Modern English. Nonetheless, speakers of Modern English are able to recognize Old English as a relative of their familiar language”. This goes to sum up the fact that what is spoken today as English is quite different from what it used to be.

1.6 The Danish or Scandinavian Attacks and Settlement

The Danes are a group of people from Scandinavia. Their desire in search of greener pastures on the British Isles rose as a result of increase in population and availability of ammunition in their homeland Scandinavia. The time of their settlement on the British Isle, was also the same time when some of their counterparts were also settling in France, where they are referred to as Normans and their kingdom as Normandy. Some of them also settled in the: Hebrides, Orkney, the Faroe Islands, Ireland, Iceland, Greenland, the Balticum, Russia and Ukraine. They are also known as the Vikings. cf. Danelaw (2017:1-3). The Vikings were raiding warriors. The presence of the Danes (Scandinavians) on the British Isles began to be felt in 787AD-850AD. The early attacks of the Danes were characterized by cases looting and burning of towns and monasteries. The Danes carried away sacred vessels of gold and silver, jeweled shrines, costly robes, and valuables of all kinds from any place they raided. Though they were raiders, they did not participate in rape of any type as a genetic study conducted in 2015, showed that they never intermingled through marriage with the other groups on the British Isle as no children were proved to have their gene outside their group. Their presence on the British Isle brought hardship to the already settled Anglo-Saxons. The Danes made the English people (Anglo-Saxons) to be slaves. In 865AD instead of raiding, the Danes landed a large army in East Anglia with the intention of conquering the four Anglo-Saxon kingdoms of England (English speaking people occupied areas). This invasion was under the leadership of Halfdan, Ragnarsson and Ivar the Boneless who were the sons of the legendary Viking leader, Ragnar Lodbrok. These warriors from the Danes were referred to as the Great Heathen Army. After making peace with the local East Anglia king in return for horses, the Great Heathen Army moved north. In 867AD, they captured Northumbria and its capital, York. In this feat, Osberht and Ella who were kings of Northumbria were defeated and replaced with another Englishman called Ecgberht 1 of Northumbria as a mere puppet in the administration of the affairs of his kingdom. The amalgamation of Northumbria and East-Anglia (East England) under the Scandinavian or Danish rule is what is called *the Danelaw*. Most of the captured areas by the Danes were retaken under Edward the Elder in the early 10th century AD, although York and Northumbria were not permanently regained until the death of Eric Bloodaxe in 954AD.

The Scandinavians or Norsemen, spoke dialects of a North Germanic language known as Old Norse. The Anglo-Saxons and the Scandinavians (Danes) thus spoke related languages from different branches of the west and North Germanic language family. Many of their lexical roots were the same or similar, although their grammatical systems were more divergent. Many place-names of Scandinavian settlement ended in by the suffix *-by*. The long years of contact between Old English speakers and Old Norse speakers resulted in intermarriage due to the acceptance of Christianity by the Danes in 878AD. This continuous contact linguistically influenced the varieties of Old English spoken in their areas of contact. The fusion of Old English and Old Norse resulted in a mixed language or creole since there was a need for communication between the persons in contact in order to satisfy immediate mercantile and social requirements of their

society. The contact between these related speech forms brought about *diglossia* or *bilingualism* in the sociolinguistic milieu of the people during the rule of Cnut and other Danish kings in the first half of the 11th Century AD. Thus, the West Saxon literary language of Old English existed alongside the Old Norse which served as a *koine* or the spoken lingua franca with a lot of borrowings from Old Norse to Old English. Some examples of Norse words in the Old English era that exist up to today are: *anger, bag, both, hit, law, leg, same, skill, sky, take, window*, the pronouns *they, them*, and *their* the plural copular verb *are*, which replaced the Old English form *sind*. Old Norse influenced the loss of grammatical gender and explicitly marked case except in the pronouns: *he, she* and *it*. Scandinavian presence also enhanced the simplification of the many case endings in Old English which occurred earliest in the north and latest in the south-west, which are the areas farthest from the Viking influence. Old Norse and Old English resembled each other closely like cousins and some words in common, they speakers of the speech forms understood each other in time the inflections melted away and the analytic pattern emerged. It is important to note many words in Old English and Old Norse differed only in their inflectional morphemes. The body of the word was so nearly the same in the two dialects that only the inflectional markers could put a hindrance to the mutual understanding of speakers under the Danish rule. The eagerness of Vikings in the Danelaw to communicate with their southern Anglo-Saxon neighbours produced a friction that led to the erosion of complicated inflectional word-endings. This hastened the wearing away and leveling of grammatical forms which gradually spread from north to south. There was a gain in directness, in clarity and in strength. When the Anglo-Saxons saw that the speech was better used and learnt with less grammatical markings on the verbs, nouns and adjectives, they quickly adopted this feature of the Old Norse dialect. These simplifications were carried on to the Middle English era which set the pattern of what the present English language is. Old Norse and the Celtic language contributed to the spread of phrasal verbs. cf. Danelaw (2017: 1-5) and Celts (2017: 1-5). The Danes also introduced the use of the apostrophe 's to mark the third person singular subject and the suffix -s for the present indicative form of the verb in the English language. According to Old English (2017:3), "The strength of the Viking influence on Old English appears from the fact that the indispensable elements of the language- pronouns, modals, comparatives, pronominal adverbs (like 'hence' and 'together'), conjunction and prepositions show the most marked Danish influence ... " Thus one can see that the Scandinavians had a great input into shaping what spoken today in the English language. Some Scandinavian or Danish place names are: Grimsby, Derby, Rugby, Thornby. Place names that contain the suffix *-thorp* (village) are: Bishopthorpe, Gawthorpe, Linthorpe; *-thwaite* (isolated piece of land), Applethwaite, Braithwaite, Langthwaite, *-toft* (a piece of land or message), Brimtoft, Eastoft, Langtoft, *-son* (...), Johnson, Stevenson and so on. Danish (Scandinavian) rule came to a close (down) with the conquest of the Island by the Normans in 1066AD-1500AD.

5.7 The Norman Conquest: 1066AD-1500AD

According to The History of English (2017: 4), "Middle English is the form of English spoken roughly from the Norman Conquest in 1066AD until the end of the 15th century". This implies that era known as Middle English began with the invasion and settlement of the Normans on the British Isles. The Normans were a group of people who lived on the northern coast of France directly across from England. They were a group of northmen who settled in France in the 9th and 10th century AD. The Normans as has been mentioned in the previous section of this paper are Scandinavians from the northern part of Germany who settled in the northern part of France. These Scandinavians had a king called Rollo as their first Duke, with Charles the king of France

the overlord. In course of time, these Normans (Scandinavians or Danes) that settled in France, were able to adapt to the civilization of France, by merging their art and intellect into whatever invention they came in contact with. For instance they were polished their military skill by their contact with the French military arts. Overtime, they were able to form a formidable military front that could challenge any counter force against their capital in Sicily. They accepted Christianity and built cathedrals that are still a great wonder to modern architecture. They also developed a strong legal system. This gave a strong kingdom in Normandy. The Normans in France gave up their Scandinavian language for French. Thus at the time of the Norman Conquest, the civilization of the Normans was essentially French. This status, positioned them among the most civilized persons in the then Europe. Some years before the Norman Conquest, the relations between England and Normandy had been quite cordial. This because Ethelred the *Unready* had married a Norman wife and when he was driven into exile by the Danes took refuge with his brother-in-law, - duke of of Normandy. His son Edward, who was brought up in France, was more French than English due to his French upbringing. Ethelred died in exile but his son survived him. In 1042AD, the Danish line phased out and Edward the Confessor, son of Ethelred, was restored to his father's throne in England. His return to England pulled in many Frenchmen who were directly to him through his mother and his friends through his association with them. Edward the Confessor enriched them and gave them important places in his government. This means that the French subtly had a copious stand in England for the twenty-four years that he ruled England. In January 1066AD, Edward the Confessor died without a soul to replace him (cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:104). Thus, a gap was that needed to be filled was left in the kingdom. The battle therefore arose between Harold, a chief adviser to Edward the Confessor and William the duke of Normandy, who was a second cousin of Edward, whom he had promised to succeed him. In a bid to do this, William got a permit to do this from the Pope and the blessing of the church. In September, 1066AD, William landed at Pevensey, on the south coast of England with a very strong Army that could not be opposed by Harold. At the same time Harold was facing another invasion in North of England with the king of Norway and a brother of Harold's called Tostig, who was returning from exile. Hardly, had Harold, rejoiced in his victory over the king of Norway and his brother that word came to him of the invasion of William, duke of Normandy. The battle was a fierce one. At first, the English army seemed to have gained an upper hand, but the retreat strategy of William brought them victory and Harold was killed in the heat of the fight. The English had to surrender with burnings and plunderings of the southeast of England. Under this condition, William was crowned king of the English people in England on Christmas Day in 1066AD, being Norman. It was only in the southeast that he was highly accepted. Because he had Challenges from the Englishmen in the southwest, west and the north, he decided to wipe a many of the rich Englishmen. Thus, in 1072AD, only one of the twelve earls in England was and Englishman who was executed four years later. For several generations after the conquest, many important political posts were held by the Normans or other foreigners. The Englishmen were under great oppression and were not well treated by their Norman lords. They were not given any important political or ecclesiastical position because the Normans assumed them to be illiterates in so far as they could not speak the French language.

5.7.1 The Status of English under Norman Rule

With the passage of time some rich Englishmen who married the Norman women began to speak French and this also helped in the social and official spread of the French language. According to Baugh and Cable (2013:110), "for 200 years after the Norman Conquest, French remained the language of ordinary intercourse among the upper class in England". At first, those who spoke

French were those of Norman origin, but soon through intermarriage and association with the ruling class, numerous people of English must have found it to their advantage to learn the new language and before long the distinction between those who spoke French and those who spoke English was not ethnic but largely social". In essence, the acquisition and use of the French language was a ladder to a better political or social status under the Norman rule. William the Conqueror encouraged literature and learning to be conducted in the French language and Adela his daughter was a patron of poets. Most of these learnings were done in the court of Henry 1, who was a very learned person in the French language and was given the title *Beauclere*. In spite of the high status accorded the French language, the English language continued to be the language of the poor peasant masses. This situation was well described about the linguistic situation in England in 1300AD by the writer of a chronicle by the name Robert Gloucester in Baugh and Cable (2013:111) in the lines below:

37. þus com lo engelond in to normandies hond
 & þe normans ne couþe speke þo bote hor owe speche
 & speke French as hii dude atom, & hor children dude also teche;
 So þat heiemen of þis lond þat of hor blod come
 Holdep alle þulke spreche þat hii of hom nome
 Vor bote a man coone frens me telþ of him lut.
 Ac lowe men holdeþ to engliss & to hor owe speech zute.
 Ich wene þer ne beþ in al þe world cotreyes none
 þat ne holdeþ to hor owe speche bote engelond one.
 Ac wel me wot uor to cone boþe wel it is,
 Vor þe more þat a mon can, þe more wurþe he is.

The text above shows that the Normans came to England with their own speech, which is the French language. It is the language they and their children spoke. The Englishman could not speak French but it was an advantage to them if they could speak both French and English. This situation continued to be so because the Normans were hostile to the use of the English language and they treated the English language as a language of socially inferior, illiterate and depraved people. In the era Henry of Huntington considered it a disgrace to be called an Englishman. The Normans were haughty, and overbearing. But a contrary attitude came with the Chronicler Oderic Vitalis, who was the son of a Norman father and an English mother. He was brought up in Normandy, but irrespective of his upbringing and fatherhood, saw himself as an Englishman. William the Conqueror himself had tried to learn the English language in order to use it to settle disputes among his subjects, but due to his numerous campaigns (wars) in England, he could not achieve this desire of his. From 1200AD, the attitude towards the use of English became that of indifference. Over time the use of French declined in the courts, church, market, and every other place. This enhanced the use of the English language in the larger society and more of the population also used English.

5.7.2 The Fall of Norman Power

In 1204AD, King John lost Normandy to the Englishmen. The main cause of his fall was his unlawful marriage to the beautiful Isabel of Angoulême, who was formerly betrothed to Hugh of Lusignan, the head of a powerful ambitious family in Normandy. Hugh appealed to Philip, king of France. When John was called to the court of Philip in France, he failed to appear claiming

that he was not subject to the jurisdiction of the French court, but the king of France reminded him that he was subject to the court in France. In line with the assertion of John, he failed to appear before the court in France and his kingdom was taken from him in accordance to feudal law. Thus, Normandy was attacked and taken over by the French power, but John still had the English kingdom to rule. Since he said he was not obliged to the French power but to England, it also jeopardized the high status that French had enjoyed in the English territory. With the rift between Normandy and England, all English now looked to England for their stability. The social stratification in England under the Normans began to disintegrate. This encouraged the use of the English language in the upper class, court, church, school, market, and in every sphere of the society. The use of the French language became unpopular and those who used did poorly at it or in mockery of the language and its users. In this stand, there was a complete language shift from the use of French to an admirable use of the English language in England. By 1400AD, every effort to reinforce the learning and teaching of the language in schools and churches through the use of prescribed texts failed. It was only taken as a foreign language in England. The Englishmen saw the French language as the language of the hostile, oppressive enemy which was no longer wanted in England. The black Death of 1349AD which improved the lot of the labour class, made English to spread as it was now used by both the high and low. In 1362AD, the chancellor opened parliament for the first time with a speech in English. English, then, began to be used to keep records in place of French or Latin in court matters and the church. cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:136).

5.8 Middle English: 1150-1500AD

The Middle English era is the period of the Norman conquest and rule which spans from 1066AD-1500AD. Middle English has also been described as a kind of creole language resulting from contact between Old English and either Old Norse or Anglo-Norman. At the beginning of the Middle English era, the English language was studied as a foreign language, but at the end, it began to be native official language of the English people. It became shaped into what is today called the Modern English. The Middle English period was characterized by glaring changes in the language. These changes affected its phonological, grammatical and lexical inputs. The English language changed from a synthetic (inflectional) language to an analytic one. At the lexical level, more words were borrowed from the French and the Latin languages with a great loss of the Old English vocabulary. At the phonological level, some voiced sounds became voiceless and vice versa or were completely lost. Some of the spelling changes in the Middle English are:

Old English	Middle English
38a. swo	so
b. scip	ship
c. catte	cat
d. folc	folk
e. fȳr/fir	fire
f. boc/bōk	book
g. fif/fif	five
h. bryd/bṛīde	bride
i. bāt/bōt	boat
j. bān/bōn	bone

k. hūs	house
l. wha	who
m. āsken/āxian	ask

Table 12: Table illustrating the spelling forms in Old and Middle English

At the phonological level, *sc* became *sh* in Middle English. Thus *scip* became *ship*. The short vowel [æ], became [a], Thus *cræft* became *craft*. The long vowel [ā], changed to [ō]. The Old English diphthongs were all simplified. The Old English long vowels were shortened when followed by a double consonant or by most combinations of consonants. For example: *grētter*, which is a comparative of *grēt* of Old English *great*. On the other hand short vowels in open syllables were lengthened in Middle English. For example: Old English *bācan* became *bāken/bake* in Middle English, *ētan* became *ēten/eat*. These changes were of great importance because they determined the course of the phonetic quality in Modern English. In Middle English, there was a general reduction of the inflectional ending on verbs, nouns, and adjectives which marked the distinctions in number, case and gender (cf. History of English 2017:3-5 and Middle English 2017: 5-8).

In the Middle English era, only two methods of indicating the plural remained fairly distinctive: the *-s* or *-es*. Other suffixes used in the marking of plural in this period are: *-en*; as in *oxen*. In this period too, there was disappearance of grammatical gender and sex because the only factor in determining the gender of English nouns. The syntax of the Middle English changed from Verb subject Object (VSO) order to Subject Verb Object (SVO) order. In Old English the subordinate clauses had the finite verb in the final position of the sentence. In the lexical development of the Middle English, the French language played a very vital role in being the source from which the language borrowed a lot of words such as: *judge, restaurant, boutique, poultry, flower, court, appellation, cohort, beef, mutton, courageous, forest, liberty, mansion, pork, pacification*, and so on. The French that were borrowed into the Middle English language, became the base for the derivation of other words in the English language. English endings were added to them. For example: the adjective *gentle* can be compounded with an English noun to make a noun: *gentleman/gentlewoman*, or with the *-ly* suffix to derive *gently*, (others are: *courteously, eagerly, faithfully, feebly, peacefully* and so on); *-ness* to derive *gentleness*. These words, according to Baugh and Cable (2013:175), are “hybrid forms that have French root with English prefix or suffix, “fusion of two languages”. This shows the extent to which French words have been rooted in the English language. Many French words replaced Old English words such as:

Old English	Middle English
39a. ēam	uncle
b. anda	envy
c. œþele	noble/nobleman
d. dryten/frēa	prince
e. leod	people

Table 13: Table illustrating the use of French words in place of Old English words

Baugh and Cable (2013: 175).

The productive capacity of the Old English was transferred to the use of prefixes and suffixes. These borrowings weakened the English way of word formation. In spite of all these changes, the fact remained that the literature of Middle English was mainly written by French authors. Englishman thought, acted, played and sang in the English language. Baugh and Cable (2013:174), note that “the house they lived in, with its bower, room, windows, doors, floor, steps, gate, and so forth, reminds us that their language was basically, Germanic. Their, meat and drink, bread, butter, fish, milk, cheese, salt, pepper, wine, ale and beer were inherited from pre-conquest days, while they could not refer to their arms, legs, feet, hands, eyes, ears, head, nose, mouth, or any common part of the body without using English for the purpose ... the predominant features were those inherited from the Germanic tribes that settled in England in the fifth century AD”. Thus, English was basically Germanic. Another thing that must have happened in the Middle English period is that Latin was used by the Catholic church. This was also an opening by which some Latin words got into the English language. Some of these words are: adjacent, allegory, conspiracy, picture, rosary, rational, intellect, communion, cross, altar, sacrament, and so on. Unusual Latin words referred to as *aureate* terms in Latin, were brought into the language in the Middle English era by poets. Some of these aureate words are: *abusion, dispoine, dirune, equipolent, palestral, laureate, mediation, oriental, prolixity, and tenebrous*. These were mostly found in the literary work of the Middle English era. Most of their works were later translated into the English language. The translations of French texts into the English language paved the way for the entrance of many words from the French language into English. The presence of many words from different languages in the English language gave rise to synonyms in the language in the Middle age. Examples of these are given in the table below:

English	French	Latin
40a. rise	mount	ascend
b. ask	question	interrogation
c. goodness	virtue	probity
d. fast	firm	secure
e. fear	fervor	trepidation
f. fire	flame	conflagration
g. holy	sacred	consecration
h. time	age	epoch

Table 14: Table illustrating the use of several words for the reference of one thing

Baugh and Cable (2013:181)

In the Middle English era, there were many dialects of the language due to the absence of any literary standard. Each writer, wrote in the dialect of his locality and this brought about differences in spelling. However, these differences were reduced towards the end of the Middle English era because there was a general adoption of a standard written and later a standard spoken form. The East Midland district was chosen as the basis of the written Standard English form. The East Midland dialect is the dialect spoken in London. London is the centre of the northern and southern. London was also the centre of learning, hence it attracted many people. the London dialect shared the features of both the north and south dialects of the English language. London (the East Midland area), was also agrarian and quite populated. London was also a major political centre of this period. London was also the home of the two universities; Oxford and Cambridge University. The Cambridge University exerted a great force on transference and use of the East Midland dialect. London was also the commercial centre and the

capital of England. These various gave the London dialect influence, preference and dominance over the other dialects in the kingdom. With the development of printing in 1476AD, the spread of the East Midland dialect became an easy thing.

5.9 Modern English 1500-1650

The English people got tired of being told that their language was, inferior, barbaric or crude. From 1500AD, the English language began to be more stabilized than ever before. All the changes phonetic, lexical, morphological and grammatical changes that took place in the Middle English era were carried on to this phase of the English language. The [a] of Middle English changed to [æ] and [u] changed to [ʌ]. The spellings in the early Modern English era were irregular and chaotic. But overtime they became stabilized. Examples of some early Modern English spellings are shown in the table below:

Contemporary English Spelling	Early Modern English Spelling
41a. cunny	coni, cuny, cunnie, cony, conie, conny
b. been	bin, bene, beene
c. Greek	Greke, Greeke
d. fellow	fellow, feluwe, fellow, fallowe
e. where	wher, whear, wheare, whair, were
f. go	goe
g. tongue	tung, tonge
d. neighbour	neibor
e. their	theyr
f. think	thinke
g. living	living
h. mine	min, myne
i. chief	chiefe

Table 15: Table illustrating the difference in spelling between early Modern and Contemporary English.

cf. Baugh and Cable (2013:207-209)

When the spellings in the Modern English era became fixed in a way that the quality of the vowels changed, the spellings remained as they were. Thus, the sounds produced were not equivalent to the spelling of the words such that one has to learn the spellings of words and the phonetic quality of each word separately. For instance the *b* of *debt*, or the last *b* in *bomb* the *gh* of *light* or *sight*, the *ch* in *chemistry* and *school* are pronounced as [k], *ph* of *philosophy* is pronounced [f]. By 1650AD, these varied spellings became stabilized by having a uniform pattern of what is obtained in the present English orthography. A spelling rule was made that a final *e*, is used to show that vowel at word medial position is a diphthong as in *came* [keɪm], *make* [meɪk], *ride* [raɪd], *hope* [həʊp], etc. The use of the apostrophe was also introduced at this time into the language. The contracted form of the past participle was changed by the insertion of the vowel *e*. for example: *chanc't*, *authoriz'd*, were changed to *chanced* and *authorized* respectively. At the lexical level so much borrowing into the language from French, Latin and Greek continued to take place in the development and enlargement of the vocabulary. At the syntactic level, the subject, verb, object word order continued to be operative. In Modern English, this order became fixed. The SVO word order of Modern English is analytic. This is because it

makes use of prepositions and auxiliary verbs and also depends upon its word order to show numerous syntactic relations. With these linguistic features in place, the language continued to assume a very strong position in the Britain. Some of the factors that enhanced the use and spread of the English language are: the Norman Conquest which opened the way for borrowing from the French language, the Black Death also paved the way for the upper class to learn to use English with the low and middle class workers since they must communicate with the labour class, the spread of education in the early Modern English era facilitated the improved use and spread of the language, the emergence of self-consciousness about language and status made the Englishmen to be determined to use their language in all areas of life, the mercantile trade that existed in Britain and other continents of the world compelled businessmen in and out of the kingdom to learn to use the English language, the popular demand of the people after the renaissance to use the language in by all people in all areas of life, the protestant reformation removed the disparity between languages thus encouraging the use of languages like English in the preaching of the gospel, the market for the English books which was readily available also triggered the use and spread of the language, the annexation and colonization of other territories by the British government helped in the spread of the language, the development of the printing press in 1476AD by William Caxton helped in the development of literature in the language, these and many other factors are some of the reasons why the English language is used in all parts of the world. Thus, the English language continued to develop into what we have today.

6. Conclusion

This paper has tried to give a brief account of the developmental phases of the English language. Some of the findings of this paper are: that the Celts are the aborigines of Britain, that the English language is the result of the fusion of many related dialects of Germanic origin, that at the Old English era the language was limited in vocabulary and had free word order, that at the Middle English era some vowel changes took place which have been carried over into the Modern English era, that the English language has borrowed largely from the French during the Norman Conquest, that the changes in the Middle English era were carried over into the Contemporary English of today, and finally that the spread of the English language has been enhanced by the development of the printing press in 1476AD by William Caxton, the protestant reformation, the renaissance, self-consciousness /education and the colonization of foreign territories by the British government. This paper, thus encourages learners, users and teachers of the English language to be knowledgeable about the history of the language that has impact on everybody in the world today. According to O' Grady, Archibald, Aronoff, and Rees-Miller, (2001, p. 291), "All languages undergo change over time. English has undergone continuous and dramatic changes throughout its three periods: Old English (roughly from 450 to 1100), Middle English (from 1100 to 1500), and Modern English (from 1500 to the present)". In essence, change is a normal occurrence in every living language. The English language has witnessed very many obvious changes and may continue to witness more changes in time to come especially in this age of computer where a lot of things are undergoing changes.

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A Description of Reduplication in Obolo

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Abstract

This paper is a description of reduplication in Obolo. Obolo is a Lower Cross language belonging to the Benue Congo family of the Niger Congo phylum. Obolo is spoken in Andoni Local Government Area of Rivers State and Eastern Obolo in Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria. The data got through intuition and corroborated by competent Obolo speakers are described through the insights from reduplication and underspecification in CV-template morphology. The paper describes reduplication as a morphological process which performs inflectional and derivational functions in Obolo. For inflectional function, reduplication is used to express intensity. It is also used for aspectual marking. With tonal modification, reduplication is used for inquiry and focus expressions. For its derivational function, reduplication is used for the derivation of modifiers from nouns. Nominals also can be derived from verbs but through the additional strategy of affixation which is used to achieve wellformedness. In terms of directionality, a leftward directionality is observed in congruence with the typology of the language which is mainly a prefixing language.

Keywords: inflection, derivation, directionality, well-formedness

1. Introduction

Obolo is a Lower Cross language under the Niger Congo phylum. Obolo is an East Benue-Congo language in Bantoid-Cross. The languages of Cross River are bounded by Ijoid, Edoid, Igboid, Idomoid, Bantoid and Bantu speakers (Faraclas 1989). Obolo is spoken by more than 200,000 people who have their ancestral home in Eastern Obolo Local Government Area in Akwalbom State and Andoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The language can be differentiated into three main dialects: the Eastern Obolo dialect (Okoroete, IbotObolo), the Western Obolo dialect (Ataba, Asarama, Unyeada) and the Central dialect (Ngo). The geography of Obolo shows, the Ogoni, Ibibio, Okrika and Bonny are Oboloneighbours. The South of Obolo extends to the coast of the Atlantic Ocean. In relationship to other tribes, Enemugwem (2006) maintains that the Obolo are central to the peopling of the Niger Delta. He traced the peopling of eastern, central and western Niger Delta to Obolo. He traced the origins of the peopling of eastern, central and western Niger Delta to Obolo.

Reduplication is a morphological process. It is a word creation strategy that copies a part or whole of a word. Reduplication copies a part or whole of a word. Simply put, in reduplication, a part or the complete base of a word is copied and attached to the base (Haspelmath and Sims 2010). The result of reduplication is stem modification. Reduplication serves as a reoccurring theme in the subdisciplines of linguistics. Hence, they perform a variety of roles. For example, in some languages, reduplication distinguishes between singular and plural. In verbs, reduplication indicates continuation, frequency, repetition of an action (Katamba and Stonham 2006). Maduagwu (2012) explains that reduplication in many languages of the world is used to

express plurality, completion, emphasis, customary activity, continuance, intensity, and repetition.

Reduplication is either partial or full (Ndimele 2010). Partial reduplication copies a segment of a word. In full or complete reduplication, the whole segment in a word is copied. Two theories on reduplication examine reduplication in this study. They are the dual theory of reduplication and underspecification theory in CV-template morphology.

Inkelas (2008) posits that ‘the fundamental typological distinction pertaining to reduplication is that between phonological duplication and morphological doubling.’ Phonological duplication provides an onset for a word by fixing the features of a specified unit. Since phonological duplication is similar to phonological copying or assimilation, its target is minimal in size and also maximally proximal. Phonological duplication responds to phonological locality conditions, targets phonologically defined constituents and phonological markedness conditions. Phonological duplication differs from morphological doubling. Morphological doubling duplicates morphological units such as a root, stem or affix. Morphological doubling is multiple exponence.

Underspecification is a theory of reduplication that is similar to McCarthy’s CV-template morphology. By CV-template morphology, reduplication is seen as affixation wherein affixes that are phonologically underspecified copy adjacent segment to realize their full phonemic expression (Broselow and McCarthy 1983).

Morphemes have well defined specification: phonological, morphological, syntactic, and semantic features. In reduplication, the ‘copy’ morpheme is defective. Its features are not fully specified. The ‘copy’ morpheme is a CV-skeletal template is placed to the ‘source’. For a full expression of the copy morpheme, the consonant (C) and the vowel (V) slot of the copy morpheme is specified through a mapping of either segments or entire base of the source morpheme. A verbatim presentation of the modified version of the mapping principles proposed by Broselow and McCarthy is presented by Katamba and Stonham (2006).

This paper aims to describe reduplication in Obolo and specifically to examine the inflectional and derivational functions of reduplication as well as analyse the directionality of reduplication.

2. Empirical Review

Empirical review shows the form and functions of reduplication in the languages shown in the data presented below. As noted earlier, reduplication is either partial or complete. Partial reduplication is shown in 1 where reduplication performs the role of inflection by marking the plurality of nouns.

1. (a)	ulo	‘head’	ululo	‘heads’
(b)	dalan	‘road’	daldalan	‘roads’
(c)	biag	‘life’	bibiag	‘lives’
(d)	mula	‘plant’	mulmula	‘plants’

(Ilocana; Yule 2010)

Maduagwu (2012) provides examples of total reduplication of adjectives and nouns in Tiv for the derivation of adverbs and adjectives.

2.	Root Word (Adj)	New Word (Adv)	Gloss
(a)	fele	felefele	‘quickly’
(b)	ijen	ijenijen	‘hungrily’
(c)	poo	poopoo	‘to fill each to the brim’
(d)	chuku	chukuchuku	‘into small pieces’
3.	Root Word (Noun)	New Word (Adj)	Gloss
(a)	vue	vuevue	‘powdery’
(b)	atihi	atihatih	‘hips by hips’
(c)	kon	konkon	‘full of wood/wooden’
(d)	toho	tohotoho	‘full of grass’

(Tiv: Maduagwu 2012)

In Yoruba, reduplication can be total or partial as shown below.

4. (a)	firi (verb)	‘in a haste’	firifiri (adverbial)	‘hastily’
(b)	kia (verb)	‘quick’	kiakia (adverbial)	‘quickly’
(c)	peja (verb)	‘kill fish’	pejapeja (noun)	‘fisherman’
(d)	ile (noun)	‘house’	ilekile (noun)	‘houses’

(Yoruba: Ehineni 2017)

Sometimes, affixation and reduplication are combined in word formation. In Igbuzo, a dialect of Igbo, Emenanjo and Oweleke (2012) show how verb derivation through affixation and total or partial reduplication yield nominals. Some nominals are reproduced in the tables below.

Table 1: Prefixation and Total Reduplication in Igbuzo (Emenanjo and Oweleke 2012)

S/N	Verb Root	Gloss	Derivative Morpheme	Derived Nominal	Gloss
5.	-kwu	‘speak’	ò=	Òkwukwu	‘act of speaking’
6.	-bu	‘carry’	ò=	Òbubu	‘act of carrying’
7.	-li	‘eat’	ò=	Òlili	‘feasting’
8.	-zù	‘train’	ò=	òzùzù	‘training’
9.	-pù	‘leave’	ò=	òpùpù	‘leaving’

Table 2: Prefixation and Partial Reduplication in Igbuzo (Emenanjo and Oweleke 2012)

S/N	Verb Root	Gloss	Derivative Morpheme	Derived Nominal	Gloss
10.	-la	‘drink’	ò=	òlila	‘drinking; wining’
11.	-ta	‘chew’	ò=	òtita	‘chewing’
12.	-za	‘swell’	ò=	Òziza	‘swelling’
13.	-kè	‘create’	ò=	Òkikè	‘creation’
14.	-gbọ	‘boil’, of water	ò=	ògbugbọ	‘act of boiling’

3. Reduplication as an Inflectional Process

Reduplication is a form of stem modification that copies a part or whole of a word. Reduplication is a reoccurring theme in the subdisciplines of linguistics especially in phonology and morphology. Reduplication performs a variety of roles. For example, in some languages, reduplication distinguishes between singular and plural. In verbs, reduplication indicates continuation, frequency, repetition of an act (cf. Ikoru 1996, Katamba and Stonham 2006). Reduplication is either be partial or full (cf. Ndimele 2010, Kari 2015). Partial reduplication copies a segment of a word. In full or complete reduplication, the whole segment of a word is copied.

Reduplication as an inflectional process in Obolo can be used to mark intensity as shown in 15 and 16.

15. (a) áyá - new
(b) ílè- big
(c) sòntíík- small

These adjectives through reduplication can show the degree of quality by ‘very’.

16. (a) áyá – new > áyáyá ‘very new’
(b) ílè – big > ílílè ‘very big’
(c) sòntíík – small > sòntítíík ‘very small’

The partial reduplication observed in 16a and b is realised through initial syllable reduplication. The initial segments in the words are repeated before the root. However in 15c, the onset of the second syllable is reduplicated. The modifiers presented in 1 are reduplicated for intensity.

Reduplication in Obolo can be used for emphasis. For emphasis which may yield perfective aspect or completion, the morpheme **Ce** is copied to the root to yield past completion. **C** stands for the underspecified consonant that copies the first segment of the root. A paradigm of the some verbs with different subject markers in examples 17 and 18 interpreted through tonal modification produces a statement with a low tone or an inquiry through a high tone.

17. (a) ñ=rò
1SGSC-do (PAST)
I did.

In this example, the verb **rò** with an default meaning means an act performed in the past - ‘I did.’ The **r** in **rò** is reduplicated and vowel **e** is inserted to realise the morpheme **Ce** shown as (b) below.

- (b) ñ=rè-rò
1SGSC-RED-do (PAST)
I really did.

In the reduplicated form, ñ=rè-rò, there is emphasis to imply ‘I really did’ from ñ=rò which means ‘I did.’

- (b) ò=rè-rò
2SGSC=RED-do (PAST)
You(sg) really did.
- (c) ì=rè-rò
3SGSC-RED-do (PAST)
S/he really did.
- (d) è=rè-rò
3PL-RED-do (PAST)
They really did.

In example 17 a-d, there is partial reduplication of the verb root through the duplication of the initial consonant of the verb root. From ro, re is reduplicated before the placement of the subject marker. The difference between examples 4 is in tonal modification. A low tone on **e-re-ro** produces a statement while a high tone on **e-re-ro** produces an inquiry.

A high tone is used for inquiry.

- 18. (a) ñ=ré-ró
1SGSC=RED-do (PAST)
What did I do?
- (b) ó=ré-ró
2SGSC=RED-do (PAST)
What did you do?
- (c) í=ré-ró
3SGSC=RED-do (PAST)
What did s/he do?
- (d) é=ré-ró
3SGSC=RED-do (PAST)
What did s/he do?

The aspectual marking through reduplication has a sense of emphasis. Reduplication can show an act that was really done or completed as shown in 19.

- 19. (a) ñ=fáñâ
1SGSC=break PAST
I broke it.
- (b) ñ=fè-fáñâ
1SGSC=RED-break PAST
I really broke it.

Complete reduplication achieves continuous aspect (a,b) and focus (c).

20. Continuous (Aspect)

(a) èjìé=**kpókpo**-í-kí-gbàñ
1PL CONT listen
we are still listening

(a) èjìé=**kpókpo**-í-kí-gbàñ
1PL CONT listen
we are still listening

(b) èmàé=**kpókpo**-í-kí-gbàñ
3PL CONT listen
they are still listening

(b) èmàé=**kpókpo**-í-kí-gbàñ
3PL CONT listen
they are still listening

Focus (verb focus)

(c) N̄=**gêgè** íkpá
1SGSC=write letter
I WROTE a letter (instead of giving a verbal message).

(c) N̄=**gêgè** íkpá
1SGSC=write letter
I WROTE a letter (instead of giving a verbal message).

Complete reduplication and affixation (emboldened) can be combined to show continuous aspect.

21. (a) ñ=**kpôkpò**-í-kí-gbàñ
1SGSC=CONT-PROG-listen
I keep on listening 'I am still listening'

(b) ò=**kpôkpò**-í-kí-gbàñ
2SGSC=CONT-PROG-listen
You (sg) keep on listening 'You (sg) are still listening'

(c) ènyì é=**kpókò**-í-kí-gbàñ
2PL 2PLSC-CONT-PROG-listen
You (pl) keep on listening 'You (pl) are still listening'

The interrogative mood expresses inquiry or questions. For a simple question that demands either a yes or no response, a high toned subject clitic is used.

4.2 Reduplication and Prefixation

Some nominals are derived from the strategies of prefixation and reduplication of the verb with a complement.

	Root	Gloss	Prefixation	Reduplication + Verbal	Complement	Gloss
27.	jê	go	i	jè-jê	óyét	fornication
28.	síkî	bend	i	sì-síkì	lék	humility
29.	Verb Root	Gloss		Derived Nominal	Gloss	
	(a) kwù	die		é-kwú-kwú	spirit (invisible)	
	(b) tâ	finish		í-té-tá	lasting	
	(c) gbé	befit		ó-gbé-gbé	worthy	

The morphological processes of prefixation and partial reduplication are used for the derivation of nominals from verbs.

30.	Verb Root	Gloss	Derived Nominal	Gloss
(a)	fũk	count	ṃ-fũ-fũk	account (report)
(b)	fín	suck	ṃ-fĩ-fín	straw (drink)
(c)	tíĩn̄	gather	ṇ- tí -tíĩn̄	meeting
(d)	yíkí	swell	ì-yí-yíkì	swelling
(e)	wôp	cultivate	í-wò-wòp	cultivation
(f)	chíèèk	believe	í-ché-chíèèk	belief
(g)	jomo	jump	í-jé-jómó	jubilation

Prefixation strategy in these examples achieves well-formed nouns. Given the fact duplicated forms do not fit into the morphological forms of nouns. Through prefixation, a segment is added which makes these nouns to fit into the form of Obolo nouns.

The processes of prefixation and reduplication can derive some nominals from demonstrative pronouns. Whereas demonstrative pronouns act as modifiers, in their reduplicated forms, they are nominals.

31.	Demonstrative Pronoun (modifier)	Reduplicated Form (nominal)
(a)	yí <i>this</i> >	é-yî ‘this one’ > ê-yí-yì ‘this very one’
(b)	yá <i>that</i> >	é-yà ‘that one’ > ê-yá-yà ‘that very one’
(c)	chí <i>these</i> >	é-chî ‘these’ > ê-chí-chî ‘these’
(d)	chá <i>those</i> >	é-chà ‘those’ > ê-chá-chà ‘those’

4.3 Directionality in Reduplication

Observe the directionality of reduplication through the CV-templatic analysis.

32. (a) íjîjîbî (b) íwówòp (c) mfùfùk (d) ósùsùt (e) ékwúkwú

(a) Derivation of íjîjîbî

j î b î (input: underlying base form)
 | | | |
 c v c v

(ii) j î b î j î b î → j í j í b î (delete unlinked slot and copy base to CV slot)
 | | | | | | | |
 c v + c v c v c v c v

(iii) í j î j î b î (prefix V to derived form)
 | | | | | | | |
 v + c v c v c v = íjîjîbî (output)

(b) Derivation of íwówòp

(i) w ò p (input: underlying base form)
 | | |
 c v c

(ii) w ò p w ò p → w ó w ò p (delete unlinked slot and copy base to CV slot)
 | | | | | |
 c v + c v c c v c v c

(iii) í w ò w ò p (prefix V to derived form)
 | | | | | | | |
 v + c v c v c = íwówòp (output)

(c) Derivation of mfùfùk

(i) f ù k (input: underlying base form)
 | | |
 c v c

(ii) f ù k f ù k → f ú f ù k (delete unlinked slot and copy base to CV slot)
 | | | | | | | |
 c v + c v c c v c v c

iii) $\begin{array}{cccc} \acute{e} & f & \acute{u} & f & \hat{u} & k \\ | & | & | & | & | & \\ v + c & v & c & v & c & \end{array} = \acute{e} f \acute{u} f \hat{u} k$ (prefix V to derived form)
 (output)

(d) Derivation of ó s ù s ù t

i) $\begin{array}{cc} s & \acute{u} & l & \hat{u} & & s & \acute{u} \\ | & | & & & & | & | \\ c & v & & & & c & v \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{cc} s & \acute{u} \\ | & | \\ c & v \end{array}$ (input: underlying base form. Delete unlinked slots)

ii) $\begin{array}{cc} s & \check{u} & t \\ | & | & \\ c & v & \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{ccc} s & \check{u} & t \\ | & | & | \\ c & v & c \end{array}$ (suffixation of C to the underived form)

iii) $\begin{array}{cc} s & \acute{u} \\ | & | \\ c & v \end{array} + \begin{array}{ccc} s & \check{u} & t \\ | & | & | \\ c & v & c \end{array} \rightarrow \begin{array}{cccc} s & \acute{u} & s & \check{u} & t \\ | & | & | & | & | \\ c & v & c & v & c & v & c \end{array}$ (copy base to CV slot and delete unlinked slot)

iv) $\begin{array}{cccc} \acute{o} & s & \acute{u} & s & \hat{u} & t \\ | & | & | & | & | & \\ v + c & v & c & v & c & \end{array} = \acute{o} s \acute{u} s \hat{u} t$ (prefixation of V to derived form)
 (output)

The CV-templatic analysis shown above affirms the directionality of affixation in Obolo. The template shows that reduplication in Obolo is placed in the direction of prefixation.

5. Conclusion

Reduplication in Obolo as a morphological process is achieved through partial and full reduplication and performs both inflectional and derivational functions. For inflection, it can be used for the intensification of the property expressed by modifiers, used for aspectual marking where it is used to express the completion and emphasis of the act expressed by the verb. Reduplication aided through tonal modification can create either an emphatic statement or an inquiry. The affixation of subject markers to a complete reduplicated verb makes for sentential structures: imperative or interrogative sentences. Derivationally, complete reduplication makes for the derivation of modifiers from nouns. In congruence with the forms of nouns in Obolo, vocalic elements are affixed to reduplicated verbs for wellformedness of derived nouns. The CV-templatic analysis shows reduplication in the directionality of prefixation.

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Proverbs and Nation Building: The Ibibio Perspective

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Abstract

One of the beauties of the Ibibio language is the variety, expressiveness and sheer wisdom of its proverbs. A proverb is a short statement often used for the purpose of emphasis, stating moral principles, supporting an argument, giving advice or stating what is thought to be true and natural. Proverbs constitute a significant commentary on a people's orientation and history. They are legacies derived from diverse and complicated cultural resources handed down as public memories and transmitted through language from one generation to another. Proverbs are associated with age, just as age is associated in the mind of the Ibibio with wisdom. They are significant indices of what the user considers to be true. In the Ibibio society, proverbs also serve the functions of philosophy, ethics and law. However, despite their robust functionality, the forces of modernity such as Western Education, Christianity and Urbanisation are conspiring to endanger the Ibibio culture particularly the language (the main vehicle of cultural transmission). Consequently, its gems/ornaments which include the proverbs are gradually sliding into extinction. This paper therefore, advocates that there is the urgent need for the restoration of the Ibibio language and other crucial aspects of the Ibibio culture to a place of honour to enable the present generation use the inherent proverbs and apply same in nation building as it was the case in the past. The paper adopts a historical analytical methodology.

Keywords: proverbs, nation building, Ibibio, language, modernity

1. Introduction

The Ibibio, live in Akwa Ibom State which is their indigenous home land. They number about four million and constitute the fourth largest ethnic nationality in Nigeria (Offiong, 1991; Udofot, 2017; Akpan 2018). They number about four million people according to the figures of the 2006 National population exercise. Udofot (2017) states that their language, Ibibio is spoken all over what used to be known as the six Ibibio Districts of Calabar Province – Abak, Eket, Ikot Ekpene, Itu, Opobo (Ikot Abasi) and Uyo, while Annang, a dialectal variant of Ibibio is spoken in the former Abak and Ikot Ekpene Districts. The main occupations of the indigenous Ibibio people are farming and fishing (Udo, 1983; Akpan, 2018).

The Ibibio migrated to their present location from Usak Edet region of present-day Cameroon Republic to their abode in Akwa Ibom area. After living in the area for many centuries, a war broke out at Ibom in modern Arochukwu region of Abia State which triggered the dispersal of another wave of Ibibio to the area.

Ibibio land was a segmentary society which was organised on the basis of village republics. Each village was autonomous and independent. No village legislated for the other and the village was the only political entity which affected practically the daily lives of the citizens. The village head was chosen on the basis of age and experience who as well could claim descent from the

founder's first born male. Each village was lineage-based – *ekpuk* – and the lineage consisted of a number of families - *ufok*. Both the lineage head and the heads of families were members of the village council responsible for making all village legislations. Traditional society was one in which the old and the aged were veritable instruments for the maintenance of law and order. Along with the various age grade and secret societies such as *ekpo*, *ekpe*, *ekong*, *idiong*, *atat*, etc., the elders exercised tremendous influence in the Ibibio society (Noah, 1988).

The Ibibio are a people with rich cultural heritage. Culture is that which makes a people or a community different and gives them their identity. According to Tylor (1871), culture or civilisation, in its wide ethnographic sense, is that complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society. Ukpong (2007) observes that culture is the totality of the ways of life of a people. It embraces everything that contributes to the survival of man on earth – not only physical or biological factors but also psychological, intellectual as well as other factors of non-material nature.

According to Udoiem (2008), culture is often taken to mean our old way of life exemplified in dress, dance or cultural artifacts, some of which are no longer relevant. Culture, on the contrary, is our present way of life derived from our past which includes our language, speech, proverbs/sayings, songs, food, etc. It is the cumulative deposit of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, religion, etc.

2. Proverbs

No one knows the exact origins of Ibibio proverbs. For sayings that have come down over the centuries, and possibly over millennia, and have seen alterations here and embellishment there, no one can say for sure where they originated or who coined them. Many proverbs are derived from Ibibio folktales. In such cases, the proverbs are often the compact capsule statement deriving from the imaginary events narrated in the tale, which the narrator wants the audience to keep in their minds. These may be the wise sayings attributed to the various characters in the story most of whom, are animals, birds etc. (Esen, 1982).

Iwoketok (2014) states that Ibibio proverbs constitute a very vital linquo-cultural aspect of Ibibio people's collective experience and date back to the people's earliest beginnings. Validating this assumption are the numerous allusions made to different facets of the people's collective experience. There are therefore myriads of proverbs from Ibibio land, exhibiting near-infinite relevance. Their rarity in conversation today does not invalidate their existence and usefulness. Every conceivable subject has far more than enough Ibibio proverbs to contain the situation including the unknown, thus affirming that Ibibio proverbs signify the reality of the world across age and time. They are not mere beautifiers of speech. The more they are collected, the more they seem to emerge.

Indeed, one of the most widely used forms of oral literature is proverb. Ibibio proverbs featured among the earliest collections of the genre in Africa. In 1865, Burton collected 2,268 proverbs from various ethnic groups in Africa, including the Ibibio, Ewe, Ga, Twi and Yoruba. Also in 1965 John Messenger did a study on Ibibio proverbs. Such interest in Ibibio proverbs by foreigners has, however, not sought to verify the relationship between the genre and the people (Noah, 1994).

Noah (1994) adds that to appreciate the importance of proverbs in African literature, it is necessary to understand how the people perceive these forms. In this regard, one notices that Ibibio culture assigns proverbs certain qualities and functions not attached to ordinary verbal communication. Thus, proverbs are considered as a vital ingredient in oration or conversation, a catalyst without which the discourse flags whereas it confers sudden vitality on speech. Also, proverbs add a type of flavor to the speech, otherwise it is deficient in “taste” and cannot have the desired impact on the listener. The brevity of the proverb adds another dimension to its attributes: it is a formula that condenses speech. A brief single -sentence proverb can adequately, effectively and forcefully replace a lengthy discourse. Another important use of proverbs among the people is that they validate ideas or thinking proposed in a speech or conversation. By their succinctness and poetic appeal, proverbs impress the essence of a discourse upon the mind of the people. Finally, their wittiness and piquancy recommend proverbs as a category of philosophy whose truism is undisputed. The above perceptions of proverbs underlie the importance and popularity of the genre among the people of Akwa Ibom State. Proverbs therefore are applied in various spheres of human existence and endeavour.

McKenzie cited in Okure (1983) classifies proverbs as belonging to a class of wisdom literature formed by the union of a number of pre-existing collections or collections of sayings. Proverbs and stories are necessary for understanding a pre-literate people. He describes a proverb as a short statement of a universal truth written in expressive language and is filled with expressions of wisdom and experience of moral saying and counsels. According to him, proverbs and stories are necessary for the understanding of the African people including the Ibibio.

According to Obiechina (1975), proverbs are the kernels which contain the wisdom of the traditional people, they are philosophical and moral expositions shrunk to a few words. They derive from the day to day detailed observation of the behaviour of human beings, animals, plants and natural phenomena, from folk lore, beliefs, values, attitudes, perceptions, emotions and the entire system of thought and feelings of the society. Proverbs are said to be the “palm-oil with which words are eaten. The use of proverbs communalises and traditionalises a speaker and indicates attachment to the community and its linguistic climate. Okure posits that:

Proverbs, stories, myth and legends are found in abundance among the Ibibio. There is a proverb for every occasion, proverbs to suit every situation and to light up every experience. They have been handed down orally. Some of them are believed to be records of actual historical events, while some are believed to be created by people’s imagination. They serve many purposes. Social and personal difficulties can be settled by an appeal to the sanctioning proverbs. Some teach a moral lesson, some warn, others entertain, and some stimulate people’s imagination. There is in proverbs, a rich deposit of wisdom of many generations and wise people know how to use them properly. African societies have proverbs which teach new things to the hearer and others which warn him against evil conduct, some are used to encourage people in doing something while others show what is bound to happen in certain circumstance (Okure, 1983: 64).

The Ibibio have great regard for proverbs which are especially appropriate to adult life and are highly effective instruments of social control. They have often been characterised as the distilled wisdom of the ancestors and people respect the wisdom implicit in proverbs, as arrows that strike

at the heart. Proverbs are used to express moral values as well as the ethics of the society. They are convenient standards for appraising behaviour in terms of the approved norms and because they are pungently, clearly and wittily stated, they are ideally suited for commenting on and correcting the behaviour of others, irrespective of their age and dignity (Okure, 1983).

Okure (1983) notes that among the Ibibio, correct procedure in interpersonal relations is stressed, and the large chunk of proverbs which outline this pattern of accepted behaviour reflect this emphasis on doing the acceptable thing. To give a salutary warning to an Ibibio man, one needs to only use some of the poignant and thought-provoking Ibibio proverbs and then the culprit will feel the reubuke in his heart. To understand their moral life, moral judgement and moral values, one needs to look into the meaning of some of the proverbs, so that some of the “canons” can be visualised.

3. Nation Building

Nation building has been defined as the work-in-progress involving building a political entity based on common citizenship, building a common sense of purpose and a sense of shared identity and a collective imagination of belonging. Nation building embodies national-integration, national development and national consciousness. The absence or weakness of core values, effective leadership, national identity and ideology undermine nation building efforts (Eyoh, 2018). Elaigwu notes about the concept thus:

Nation building...on the horizontal dimension involves the acceptance of other members of the community as equal fellow members of a “corporate” nation – recognition of the rights of other members to a share of common history, resources, values and other aspects of the state – buttressed by a sense of belonging to one political community. It involves the feeling that we are all citizens entitled to a share of the bitter and the sweet. Nation building, therefore, is the wide spread acceptance of the process of state-building; it is the creation of a political community that gives a fuller meaning to the life of the state (Elaigwu; 2015: 70).

Even though the term “nation building” in modern sense gained prominence in the 1960s and 70s when President Julius Nyerere of Tanzania advocated it for fragile post-colonial African states (Eyoh, 2018), it has been applicable and relevant in the traditional Ibibio society. The above postulation is ascertained by Esen thus:

In the traditional philosophy of the Ibibio, the individual was not perceived as having any intrinsic personal worth. What counted as the worth of the individual was the extent of his contribution (actual in adults, potential in children) to the survival happiness and welfare of the society. The welfare of the group or society had precedence over that of the individual. In Western thought, the group exists so that the individual may survive. In the traditional African thought, it is the individual who exists so that the group may survive. The needs and choices of the individual often must be subordinate to the collective will and interest of the group. To assert the interests of the individual above those of the group is considered undesirable and deviant (Esen, 1982: 223).

4. The Notion of the Community in Ibibio

According to Okure (1983), the ordinary person in Africa does not merely talk about community, he or she lives and experiences community every day. Initially one may say that community is a conscious commitment to give and share life together with a limited number of people in a defined geographical area. It is a precious value that binds peoples and families together. It is a value that enables people to have a common understanding leading them to mutual trust, help, respect for personal freedom, as well as mutual responsibility. As the Ibibio is shaped by the religious, moral and social life of the community to which he belongs, he is taught to understand and to develop greater respect for communal life, social relationship, sexuality, charity, justice and relevant values. It is believed by the Ibibio that the family is the first place where a person lives in the community. The Ibibio generally believes that personal development takes place within the community, first in the family circle, then in the wider community with other human beings as he consistently strives to create that community. Indeed, while the person is of more value than the community in which he lives, it is the community that develops and helps in socialising a person. A sense of community is the atmosphere which kinship thrives (Okure, 1983).

One of the most important features of community life is “sharing”, which strengthens the relationship of mutual trust. This is why the Ibibio is taught from the early stage of his life to share what he has with close relations. This attitude may become very significant to the point that the child may not be able to eat anything without sharing with a relation. Moreover, the deep sense of sharing triggers cooperation between people in the family. Family solidarity is easily built and maintained and common goals are easily achievable. In conversations, there is a constant use of the first person plural “we” and possessive pronoun “ours”. The spirit of community eventually takes a central stage in the individual’s orientation (Okure, 1983).

5. Some Ibibio Proverbs/Wise Sayings and their Significance

5.1 *Mkpatat nwak ke ukot/ikpong akpa nte unen* (he that is alone dies like a fowl)

This proverb exemplifies kindred and community consciousness and means that the man without a family dies like a chicken. It states that the piassava had to wrap itself and he who is alone, has no family and no one to speak for him or defend him. No one defends one who is alone consequently, such a person dies like a chicken and no one asks questions. The ancient Ibibio demonstrated strong kindred ties and community spirit. They were identified by families, extended families, communities and clans which were closely knit together by beliefs, norms and taboos (Udofot, 2017). Esen (1982) posits that kindred and community spirit of the Ibibio is one of the greatest assets. Other scholars of Ibibio culture have observed the same tendency among the Ibibio. Udoidem (2008) refers to it as *ukangnyinism* or *yakami-ism*. According to him, this starts with the family. Every person has to identify with a family and is not fulfilled in self-actualisation outside his membership of a family setting. Bastards and people who cannot trace their ancestry to a recognised family were subjected to extreme ridicule in the community.

5.2 *Eto idaha ikpon ikappa akai* (a tree does not stand alone by itself and become a forest)

The proverb conveys the idea of cooperation or unity. It means that no one person can meet the needs of the whole community; rather, many people are required. It literally means that a tree does not stand alone and become a forest. It stresses the need for coming together, working together and staying together to be able to maximise accomplishment. It conveys the central orientation that the strength of the Ibibio man is in togetherness. Because a tree that stands alone

cannot make a forest, birds cannot live there and it can, therefore not be useful to the community. Forests were a very valuable asset to the Ibibio people. From the forests the people got not only wood and other building materials, but also meat from the wild animals, leaves, roots and barks for medicinal purposes and varieties of food materials. A single tree, irrespective of its hugeness, could not supply all these; only a forest could. In this sense, it was meaningless for one tree irrespective of its size and height to behave as if it could alone serve and satisfy the various needs of the people. Several trees must stand together and complement each other in supplying the needs of the people. An individual, no matter how powerful and rich, cannot be everything to everyone in the community. It requires many people with their diverse talents and capabilities working together in order to meet the various needs of the community (Esen, 1982; Ekong, 2001; Iwokedok, 2014; Udofot, 2017).

It also conveys the message of the danger of working alone as an individual. In the pre-colonial era, where inter-ethnic conflicts were rampant, a single person who is attacked alone cannot withstand the combined aggression of the opposing group. Even in the area of working together, it was usually in groups and on the basis of age grades. For instance, men worked together to clear the bush and plant or harvest for one another in turns while the women also weeded the farms and planted in groups in one another's farms. The youth also had their specific roles to play in the community. Paid labour in Ibibio land is a recent development. It used to be more effective to work together because larger grounds could be covered. If brothers/sisters contribute, the contribution can never be burdensome (Esen, 1982; Ukpong, 2007; Udofot, 2017). Udofot (2017) notes that the import of the proverb is agreement to work together. If parties do not agree, they can never come together to perform a task or engage in a project. The Ibibio were people who readily teamed up to attack a common enemy or perform a task. The teaming up created groups based on understanding and friendship which cemented the family, community and clan relationship and loyalties.

6. Child Upbringing

6. 1 *Mkpat eka unen iwoto ndito* (young chicks do not die from the trampling of their mother's feet)

This one exemplifies children upbringing. It codes the fact that mother's love and care is selfless. She must be ready to give up her comfort including her life to protect her children. Above all, she must be there with them and for them (Udofot, 2017).

It also means that the heavy tread of a mother-hen does not kill her young. In the Ibibio society, it was not only the parents who could discipline a child since the child was regarded as the "community property". Any adult who saw a child involved in an unwholesome act or immoral behaviour could easily correct and even discipline the child without fear of the parents disapproval. Indeed, parents would even be appreciative. This situation helped to check the morals of young men and women. Since girls were supposed to remain chaste until they were married, adult members of the society constituted themselves into a watchdog of the community. Songs were composed to expose and condemn unwholesome behaviour. The greatest custodian of the child's upbringing was the mother. Like the proverbial mother hen, she had to be there for the children. She did not sleep away from the house unless in extreme necessity. She gave up her comfort and make extreme sacrifices of material things to ensure that her children were brought up in a disciplined fashion. The saying that a good child is the joy of the father and a bad one is the mother's sorrow holds true among the Ibibio. The mother is blamed for her children's

misbehaviour especially in the case of teenage pregnancy outside marriage. The ancient Ibibio knew that there was no surer way to spoil the child than sparing the rod. The Ibibio could have said “spare the rod and spoil the child”, but they were a chicken-raising people. This particular proverb came from the action of the mother hen (Esen, 1982; (Udofot, 2017).

The proverb could only occur in the language of a people who engage in poultry business. In the past, there was not one family house in Ibibio land where chickens were not kept routinely. Cocks and hens were raised for eating, for sale, for sacrificial and other purposes. It was always pleasant to see a mother-hen with a large brood of chicks which she fed by scratching up food from the ground, and defended noisily against kites and hawks. Quite often, the mother hen would accidentally tread on her tender day-old chicks and the little featherless thing would squeal and roll over in pain. An onlooker would think that the chick would not survive it. But, as the Ibibio rightly observes, no chick ever dies from the tread of its mother’s feet (Esen, 1982).

7. Security Consciousness

7.1 *Eka Ebok ama obo eyen: umaha edikpoono iwot okok, etim me ama usan oton?* (the Mother Monkey said to her child; you do not like knocking your head against branches of trees; is it then the soup that you prefer?)

Monkeys used to be favourite game of hunters in many parts of Ibibio land. The forests were full of them and since monkeys live in large communities, the hunters found them relatively easy to shot. Monkeys know this and learned very early in life the tactics of survival consisting mainly of brisk swings from branch to branch at a pace that would be too hot for the hunter to follow, or too irregular for his steady aim. Such tactics must involve young monkeys new to the tricks in the inconvenience of frequently dashing their heads painfully against tree branches. Naturally, some young rebellious monkeys would resent that and refuse to take such inconvenience. The Mother-Monkey therefore admonished, that it was better for the young one to bear the pains and live longer (Esen, 1982).

8. Cyclic Change that comes progressively associated with age

8. 1 *Isua akappa, usion obuho* (as the years go round, the fragment of old pottery sinks deeper into the ground)

Uision is a piece of the fired clay from a broken earthen pot. Ibibio women were great potters whose products were sold far and near, and were used for cooking, water fetching and storage, bathing, decoration, religious and other purposes. All the pots were handmade and fired to the desired hardness, then polished. If a pot fell down, it broke into pieces like modern China ware. It is such broken pieces of clay that are known as *usion*. Sometimes when one digs into the earth, one may be surprised to find *usion* lying buried several metres below the surface. This tends to raise questions. When an earthenware breaks, the pieces are just left lying there on the surface of the ground. No one takes the trouble to bury them. So how does it come about that *usion* can be found buried so many metres below the surface? The Ibibio explanation is that as the years roll round, the pieces of clay sink further and further into the soil (Esen, 1982).

The proverb is about the cyclic change that comes along progressively with age and maturity. It implies a progressive change from the surface to the depth from the bad to the good, from youth to age, from the immature to the mature, from destructible to indestructible. In Ibibio philosophy, this change in the life-cycle of the piece of clay represents the cycle of human life. The piece of

fired clay *usion* originally comes deep down in the bowels of the earth as wet clay, the raw material from which pots are made. It is moulded into a pot. The pot is used for all sorts of purposes, until after its tasks on earth are accomplished, it breaks (and dies). Then the pieces gradually begin to sink deeper and deeper into the ground until what was formerly raw clay reunites with its original source deep down in the bowels of the earth. It is symbolic of the life cycle of man: birth, maturity, performance of earthly functions, age, death, re-union with the ancestors (Esen, 1982).

Esen (1982) commenting on the significance of the proverb states that it symbolises the fact that the first object with which the Ibibio touched their newly born baby was the lump of the earth. As a child came out of her mother's womb, the midwife who received it into the world had a lump of earth in her right hand, and as soon as the child uttered its first cry, the midwife touched its body with the lump of earth. Some over-eager midwives often got the lump of earth ready even before the labour reached its critical stages. That is the basis of another proverb: *ukite-kit iwuot eyen afo abek ntan* (picking up the lump of earth without first waiting for the baby's head to appear). In plain language; anticipating the results too early, or counting ones chicken before they are hatched.

The first contact of the child with the lump of the earth is significant. It symbolises that link-up between the new life and its origins. The ancient Ibibio, quite independently of the Bible and the Christian religion, had always known and believed that man originated from the earth. At the end of his life on earth, when all his tasks are done (just like the pot) he lies down dead and broken. But his survivors remember where he came from and send his flesh and bone back into the earth (just like the *usion*) to re-unite with his ancestral origin. Udo also underscores the significance of the land thus:

The Ibibio pre-colonial economy depended to a large extent on land. From time immemorial the Ibibio attached great importance to their land. They regarded it as their "First Mother". It is their Mother Earth, because it is the soil which is their source of water: the rivers, seas and ocean which were so much a part of their everyday life and which provided the various species of fish, for example crayfish, which they sold to many communities in what is today modern Southeastern Nigeria. It is to them that some of their water deities, for example *Ataokpo Ndem Uruan Inyang* and *Otuk idim Ndem Iwa Awa*, lived and protected them. It is the soil which bore them, so to speak, for it produced cash and food crops. It is in this soil that their ancestors were buried who though dead, continued to look after their welfare. Some of the living would, in turn, be buried there with their ancestors...the Ibibio also believed that without the land, they would be dead men, women and children. Land became the very centre of their lives and of their communities. They do nothing to profane the land, and if this happened, they immediately expiated the sin by offering sacrifices (Udo, 1983: 195).

This proverb is generally used in two kinds of situations. If a person who, was wild and unruly as a young man and was almost written off as good for nothing, gradually begins to show good sense, some wisdom and sound moral judgement in his affairs, his father and kinsmen usually become delighted in his transformation. They link the change with the growing age and maturity, and observe happily that as the years roll by the *usion* is actually sinking deeper into the earth.

On the other hand, if a man, old enough to think and act wisely behaves in a foolish way deemed inconsistent with his age, the proverb may be used to remind him that as the years roll by the *usion* in him ought to sink deeper into the earth. In such a contest, it is considered a very harsh rebuke (Esen, 1982).

9. Social Justice

9.1 *Yak ibiom obop efok, yak ekrang obop efok, ake mimaha nooh kiet obopefok, yak mba abeke* (let the eagle perch, let the kite perch, which ever says the other must not perch, let its wings break off).

This proverb is very common among the Ibibio people. In this proverb, the eagle is represented by the rich, strong or noble because it can fly higher than other birds, and kite is represented by the poor. It is the conviction of the Ibibio that the world was created for all to cultivate, above all, that man is created human and divine. The eagle and the kite (rich and poor) are both God's creature, free to ply the earth and to "perch". Neither is supposed to block the way against the other. Hence, in life, there is room for all men to "perch" and to attain supreme value. Both prejudice, hardness of heart in competition, the destruction or blocking of people's chances people's way to success in life are believed by the Ibibio to be against human progress and, above all, against God's and universal justice. Therefore, every Ibibio strongly abhors any attitude that militates against this universal progress and justice (Okure, 1983)

The proverb indicates and points to the fact without this universal notion of justice, there can be no harmony, peaceful co-existence, love and respect in the community. It expresses the fact that justice and freedom are among the fundamental human rights. Above all, that justice demands that no person be deprived of this God-given right to successful life and progress; therefore, for the Ibibio, one who tries to block the way of success of another or to destroy the other's chances is fighting against the divine will and justice and is an enemy to progress and peace. He is a person of ill will. This proverb rejects and warns against any situation of oppression of man by man which is evident in most places of work. Any situation in which "A" objectively exploits "B" or hinders his pursuit of self affirmation as a responsible person is that of opposition. Such a situation in itself constitutes violence and injustice and interferes with man's ontological and historical vocation.

10. Respect to Elders

10.1 *Uma ukpono owo mfin, eyah ukpono fien mkpon* (if you respect today's king, others will respect you when your turn comes).

Okure (1983) states that this is often given as an instruction to those governed to obey and respect their kings and chiefs. It points to the fact that respect is reciprocal and that justice demands that a man do to others what he expects others to do to him. Above all, justice demands that respect and cooperation be given to those in authority. It is one of the canons often employed by parents, rulers and superior to couch their subjects and children to good conduct and cooperation. Other parts or versions of this proverb go like this: *etok eyen ama ayie ubok nno asana, aya dia ndidia mme mbong* – "A child who can wash his hands clean may eat with elders", or "Abasi inoho idiok unam nnuk" – God does not provide a wild animal with horns. That is, one who is unjust, dishonest, un-cooperative, disrespectful cannot achieve a height. In other words, if he does, he will be a stumbling block to his people or community, he will do more harm than good.

10.2 *Ado anie ufok idiaha efere akwere?* (The soup cannot be finished when the owner of the house has not eaten)

This conveys an attitude or respect to elders which is here represented by the proverbial owner of the house. He should be cared for generously, failure to do so amounts to disrespect. This indicates the fact that in the Ibibio traditional society, elders were revered and respected by all.

11. Ingratitude

Nkok Ibok nno usine enyene edet ondom: (After a man is cured, he bites or forgets the doctor or the one who cures him)

The proverb refers to ingratitude which the Ibibio regard as injustice on the part of the person cured of his disease for rewarding evil for good, for refusing to be grateful. This becomes very significant because the Ibibio is always grateful. This serves as an instruction on the principle of “give and take”. For a man who claims his right on the one hand and neglects to carry out a corresponding duty or to respect the rights of others is unjust. Because man is social by nature, he should live, work and cooperate with others, and above all, should encourage the other. It is deemed a great injustice among the Ibibio if, after having helped a person, the one helped forgets the one who helped him. The person helped is expected to demonstrate his gratefulness not only in words, but also in deeds. Otherwise, he will be said to be guilty of ingratitude which is injustice. This proverb is often used as a reminder to the Ibibio about God, who is Supreme and about his providential care; and the obligation to offer sacrifices of thanksgiving and praise to Him. The canon also serves as an instruction to those children who tend to forget their parents and their responsibility towards them. Because justice demands that children should take care of their parents, especially in times of sickness and when the parents are approaching old age. If they fail in these responsibilities, they are said to be guilty of injustice towards their parents (Okure, 1983).

12. Early Preparation

12. 1 *Utai ekebo ke akpa itok oson itok* (The alligator said that the first dash is the mainstay of the race. That is, in a race the first dash is decisive)

The Ibibio regard the alligator as a timid animal that can disappear at the first attempt of an enemy to establish contact with it. As a result, the alligator naturally runs away with all the energy it possesses. That means the first burst is very important because if the alligator does not succeed to escape, it would be caught and that means that the first burst is the thin line between life and death. Esen (1982) asserts that the originator of this proverb positioned it to fit into any aspect of human endeavour which demands the application of the initial energy to obtain initial results. He cites the examples of football teams that capitalise on early goals to consolidate their victory.

13. Leadership

13. 1 *Obong isibono ikpoon* (A king does not shout/rule alone)

Leadership is conceived by the Ibibio people as calling on the citizenry. This concept is conveyed in the word of *boon* which means call, cry out or shout. It also depicts the manner by which Ibibio people usually disseminate information through the town-crier. The proverb therefore suggests that a ruler should realise that he cannot rule successfully by doing everything

himself. He must engage the assistance of those who can contribute positively to the welfare of his community. On the other hand, the proverb speaks to the citizenry that rulership demands the cooperation and participation of all to succeed, they should therefore be willing and ready to render their service at any time. The need for cooperation and contributive effort for a successful democracy is advocated. The general meaning of the proverb is that the best and most efficient law, organisation or individual is not infallible (Iwokedok, 2014).

13. 2 *Udia uyokho nsasak asetime idan ke ekod* (the greedy sun-bird always pulls off an arrow from its occiput)

The proverb reproves careless people and those who do not have self-control. It warns that the consequence of such negative inclination is being caught off guard by prisoners, vicious fellows or murderers. The proverb also speaks against excess selfishness and greed; especially the kind that makes people cling to positions, power and privilege at the risk of their lives, though their tenure has expired. The proverb says such people stick on until they are disgraced out of office or are disgracefully dispossessed of such positions or property. It means that there should be restraint in doing things. One should be disciplined where food is concerned. It warns that the glutton who does not show discretion in his eating habit is likely to get harmed. The teaching is that people should be satisfied with what they have or are offered because straining to get more is likely to cause them trouble, discomfort or destruction as exemplified in the life of the insatiable sun-bird.

14. Proverbs and Conflict Resolution

The conduct of peace makers in the traditional societies was underpinned by implicit philosophical values and principles (Alagoa, 2004). First, the principle that those who wish to resolve conflicts must appear impartial and inspire the trust and confidence of the parties in conflict. Accordingly, rulers who were the first line of contact in such situations were expected to behave impartially to all manners of persons in their office. In general, the Ibibio try to avoid conflict and therefore going to a court, be it formal or informal, because getting involved in a case is a great enterprise – win or lose, it costs money. Because of the corruption of many police officers, the court they dread most is the formal court. Police officers require “kola” (a code name for bribe), before they will investigate and prosecute a case. The case may drag for months or years, something the Ibibio hate. When the case is decided, there is no swearing of an oath to protect the two parties from harming each other (Offiong, 1997).

Conflict between husband and wife is common. Generally, refusing to eat a wife’s meal signifies a conflict situation between wife and husband. Usually a wife reports the problem with her husband to her parents-in-law. Often, a mother-in-law who is on good terms with her daughter-in-law will be the first to know about any conflict between her son and his wife. Regardless of who receives the complaint, an attempt to resolve the matter swiftly is always made. A woman may try to appease her husband by begging for forgiveness. Should this fail, a go-between or the woman’s family becomes involved. Always, the aim is to reconcile both parties. Divorce is the last resort and is viewed as a failure (Offiong, 1997).

Customary gender roles and stereotypes inform decisions in cases involving husband and wife. Custom dictates that women in a patriarchy be submissive to men. Thus in a case which a woman would win outright in an egalitarian society may not be decided in her favour here because this would give her license to be at loggerheads with her husband; decorum and harmony in the family are possible only if a woman is submissive. If a woman cursed her

husband, she is fined a cock; if she wished her husband's death, she is fined a she-goat. After resolution of the conflict, a wife's first meal for her husband is pounded yam, which is considered a delicacy. In deciding a case, a woman is reminded that two he-goats, two rams, or two male dogs cannot live under the same roof. In other words, a woman must not behave as if she were equal to her husband: she must be submissive (Offiong, 1997).

Conflict between extended families involves the council of elders and such conflicts almost always involve land disputes, stealing fighting, adultery, fornication and witch accusation. Once a case is reported to the village head, who is the ex-officio chairman of the council of elders, he consults with other elders in the village and then a day is set for the hearing of the case. Depending on the nature of the case, the chairman may invite elders within and outside the lineage to participate. The litigants are entitled to invite elders sympathetic to them.

According to Offiong (1997), the "jurors" for the day having been selected, the next item of business is prayer/libation. One village elder is usually well versed in the art of libation. He gets a calabash, fills it with palm wine provided by the litigants, and then calls on ancestors to be present to guide everybody in the deliberations to follow, to give the "jurors" an understanding mind to discern truth from falsehood, and punish anybody who might try to pervert justice. This exercise of libation and prayer is significant. It places the "jurors" on oath to remain impartial and gets all to focus on the desire to seek peace between litigants. It unites all present in common action before the hearing begins; it enables all to focus attention on the need for maintaining the harmony and well-being of the extended family, village or lineage.

The presiding elder then outlines the expected decorum and fines for violators and then warns that the case is serious and should not be treated in a hurry; there should be a thorough probing, and this should take as long as necessary to get to the truth. He concludes by admonishing: *okop ikoedem kiet odo owot owo*. Meaning, taking sides after hearing from one party is grossly unjust; it is a capital offence. Therefore, a decision must come only after weighing evidence of the two parties. When the plaintiff and the defendant as well as their witnesses have spoken and carefully cross-examined, cases not concluded in one day are adjourned till another day. Usually, the "jurors" retire to a convenient corner outside the view of the audience to deliberate on the evidence.

In delivering the verdict, the spokesman relies on proverbs because they convey wisdom. An elder well versed in proverbs is highly respected. Proverbs sooth and are like seasoning which makes an otherwise unpalatable food edible. In emphasising the importance of respect to constituted authority, the spokesman will say that a community without elders is doomed. Since elders are the custodians of knowledge, wisdom, and morality, they deserve the respect and cooperation of all, warning in advance that the punishment to be announced is not commensurate to the offence.

A proverb such as: *enyong ese-ayaan ebok*, meaning that (even a monkey can fall from a tree). It indicates that in spite of the total mastery of the monkey of the tree top which is his natural environment which he performs all kinds of jumping stunts, the monkey needs not be over confident of its ability as it could miscalculate the distance, takes a bad jump and fall to the ground. It was readily used to warn anybody that engages in anti-social behaviour such as stealing with the emphasis that the evil conduct will be exposed.

15. Repositioning of Ibibio Proverbs for Nation Building

A proverb is a pithy statement with a global influence. But mere brevity does not qualify a statement to be called a proverb. It must present a serious thought. It is generally conceived as the wisdom of many and the wit of one, a condensation of an experience one might say. A proverb can be amusing but not meant for entertainment. With silent guidance, proverbs mould public opinion and private life. No race, whatever the colour, age or clime, no culture, has been without them. They are a model of compressed or forceful language. It serves as a reservoir from which artists or anyone for that matter can draw to give freshness to his speech (Iwokedok, 2014). Proverbs are traditional answers to recurrent ethical problems; they provide an argument for a course of action which conforms to community values; they arise in the midst of conversation and are used by speakers to give “name” to ethical problems confronting them and to suggest ways in which it has been solved in the past. The use of proverbs in these ways would invoke an aura of moral rightness and make the comfort of past community procedure available to the present and future (Essien, 1980).

As Essien (1980) has noted, judging from the nature of people who live in a basically oral culture like Nigeria, no amount of rapid progress in technology would change the people essentially within a short time. Therefore, certain Nigerian elite who seem to be all for modernity and technology and seem to refer to the use of proverbs in a derogatory sense, needs to modify their mentality. The life of the Ibibio and other Africans appear to be deeply rooted in the use of proverbs. Contact with these proverbs would make it possible to retrace the history of certain events, especially as there were no written records. It would be possible to forge new links with the past if the culture of the people is to remain authentic.

The Ibibio has a tradition of imparting pleasurable. One of the effective ways that has been used for this purpose has been proverbs. It is believed that the proverb speaker, besides holding the attention of his audience, always provokes laughter or tears as the case may be. This apt methodology of teaching could be interjected into the Nigerian school system.

16. Conclusion

The Ibibio word for proverb is *nke*. The word is a generic name for all those types of verbal expression which have more than one meaning. Such expressions are generally short and are couched in words that are simple, pleasant, often picturesque and entertaining and easy to remember. Proverbs are the kernel which contains the wisdom of the people. They are philosophical and moral expositions shrunk to a few words and form a mnemonic device for effective communication. The proverbs of the Ibibio are recorded in the memory of the ancestors and handed down by words of mouth. They represent the people’s philosophy. A whole range of human experience can be expressed in graphic and concise form and the wider implications of specific situations brought to mind (Udoiem, 1984). Udoiem (1984) also states that the use of proverbs is a type of human communication. Like most communication, it is basically a giving and receiving of meanings. The Ibibio language (like most other African languages) is very rich in proverbs. In Ibibio culture, the master story-teller, the orator, the adviser or the wise man, if he is speaking to local listeners, often needs to use a lot of proverbs not only to captivate and retain the attention and interest of his audience, but also to stress and concretise the main issues under discussion (Udoiem, 1984). By the use of such proverbs, some which are listed above, the Ibibio show the importance attached to justice. One could go on without end, as there exist thousands of such proverbs. But these few ones show how many of their proverbial utterances are replete with moral virtue. The important or essential point that is worth mentioning is that

that proverbs are seen as statements of “factual truth”, they are expressions of beliefs and modes of speech which draw from a cultural experience, attitudes and values of the Ibibio society for their moral relevance to justice.

It should be noted that modernity has adversely affected the applicability of the Ibibio proverbs. One of the reasons is that the Ibibio people do not pay serious attention to the use of their language. As Udofot (2017) has posited, what the Ibibio need is a “cultural homecoming” starting with teaching their children their language before English language. Through that way, they will have a mother tongue and identity. They will learn Ibibio culture transmitted through the Ibibio language. The knowledge of the culture of unity, respect, togetherness, kindred and community spirit will serve as variables in nation building. The introduction of the use of proverbs into the classroom would modify the Western oriented background of learning in Nigerian schools. It is not appropriate for the Ibibio to neglect its oral culture because the advanced technological societies seem to pay less attention to theirs.

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A Pragmatic Analysis of Linguistic Politeness and Impoliteness: The Case of Medical Practitioners and Patients' Clinical Situation Interaction at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH)

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Abstract

Linguistic politeness is associated with the way a speaker uses language to protect or save the positive or negative face of a hearer, while linguistic impoliteness deals with the ways a speaker can employ language to damage an addressee's face. The aim of this paper is to pragmatically analyze polite and impolite linguistic behaviors of medical practitioners and patients during interactions in clinical situation at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). Convenience and purposive sampling techniques were employed in the collection of data from respondents in three natural languages: Igbo, Nigerian Pidgin and English language. The paper adopts a descriptive qualitative approach guided by Politeness and Impoliteness theory in the analysis of linguistic behavior of medical practitioners and patients (MP-P). The findings of this study show that verbal politeness strategies such as intensifying interest to the addressee, seeking agreement, joke strategy, hedging, giving reasons, cooperation, stating the face threatening act (FTA) as a general rule, and apologizing are employed. This study also establishes that the verbal impoliteness strategies often employed during MP-P interaction are snubbing and ignoring, exclusion of a third party, seeking disagreement, disassociating with the other, frightening, diminutives and withhold politeness. The study further reveals that occupational, generic and kinship honorifics which make interactions more polite are utilized while occupational honorifics are influenced by power and formality factors. Also, generic honorifics are influenced by power, formality, gender, and age factors while kinship honorifics are influenced by age and gender factors. Finally, the study concludes that these factors do not hinder positive effect on interactions.

Keywords: politeness, impoliteness, face, honorifics, patient.

1. Introduction.

Linguistic politeness covers all forms of linguistic behaviour through which humans form and maintain relationships (Kadar, 2019:149). The study on linguistic politeness encompasses explorations of both politeness and impoliteness, and as such, it refers to '(im) politeness research'. (Im)politeness research emanated from pragmatics which studies inherent and contextual attributes of language. In every social relation, it is common for people to use linguistic strategies in maintaining or promoting harmonious relations which is attainable by obeying the conversational rules of pragmatic competence; 'be clear' and 'be polite'. The second rule of being polite consists of subsets of three rules: don't impose, give options and make other people feel good - be friendly (Lakoff, 1989:11). However, human communication has been fraught with inconsistency in the application of these rules during conversation. Politeness strives to explain how and why individuals try to promote, protect or 'save face', especially

when embarrassing or shameful situations arise unexpectedly. In the absence of politeness during interaction, impoliteness prevails.

Politeness is associated with the ways someone can use language to protect or save the positive face or negative face of a hearer. According to Brown and Levinson (1987), “Positive face is referred to as the want of every member that his wants be desired to at least some others, while Negative face is referred to the want of every competent adult member that his actions be unimpeded by others”. Brown and Levinson (1987) explain that face is an individual feeling of self-worth or self-image, reputation or good name that everyone has and expects everyone else to recognize. A positive evaluation arises when an action is in congruence with the norms of a society and a negative evaluation occurs when an action is to the contrary (Fraser, 1990:220). An model list of politeness super-strategies that can save an addressee’s face include: bald-on-record politeness, positive politeness, negative politeness, off-record politeness and withhold politeness (Brown and Levinson, 1987:68-70). Politeness is the most important aspect to an effective communication in any society. During interaction between Yoruba language speakers, there is the use of politeness strategies in greeting, turn taking in conversation, honorifics and others. The use of honorifics is a more central means of enhancing politeness and making sure it is expressed (Habwe, 2010:127). Consequently, it is impolite for someone to come across elders and fail to acknowledge their presence through greetings and honorifics in the Yoruba culture. Other cultures in Nigeria also observe this cultural etiquette.

While we can preserve face, there is a greater possibility that we can damage face. Impoliteness is a negative attitude towards specific behaviors occurring in specific contexts that causes offence. It deals with how we communicate and take offensive messages. A speaker uses impoliteness strategies usually to damage the addressee’s positive or negative face wants (Culpeper, 2005:8). It is impolite in any kind of face to face conversation for someone to meet a new person and not greet. This is what Culpeper (1996) call withhold politeness which means the absence of an expected politeness strategy in a situation which it is expected. Culpeper (1996) created five super-strategies of impoliteness from Brown and Levinson’s (1987) politeness strategies which comprise: bald-on-record impoliteness, positive impoliteness, negative impoliteness, sarcasm or mock politeness and withhold politeness. Possible characteristics of impoliteness include being inconsiderate, aggressive, rude, inappropriate, patronizing and hurtful.

In medical practice and delivery, communication between medical practitioners and their patients is a practical process which takes place in medical institutions with the purpose of providing information about reliable treatments and their process of administration. It deals with the interaction between individuals who may or may not be equal in social status or class, background knowledge, education, age, exposure, etc, seeking to receive medical help from ailments while the other stands in a higher position of providing such help. Bensing (1993) maintains that, “patients often interact with doctors having a need to know and understand and to feel known and understood”. Medical practitioners comprised different professionals dealing with daily care and cure of patients in hospitals, clinics, sickbays or in medical institutions. Some key professionals in medical institutions include doctors, nurses, therapists, pharmacists, clinical officers, surgeons, biologists, laboratory attendants and others. However, this study involves only doctors, nurses and clinical officers. Thus, medical practitioners, as a general term refers to them.

Jorgeusen and Phillips (2002); in Ali (2015) argues that, “medical practitioners ought to realize that language is a machine that generates, and as a result, constitutes the social world”. In essence, language functions as an exchange link for thoughts and ideas in order to create social relations between interlocutors and to facilitate their requirements. Thus, what we consider polite or impolite depends on social relations and roles among interlocutors. For instance, a situation involving a huge power imbalance as might be the case in army recruit training between officers who take the role of trainers and trainees, who are subordinates, what we normally view as impolite or rude is accepted. Impoliteness may result to misunderstanding and dissatisfaction, leaving a patient or medical practitioner with the feeling of hostility. This may consequently lead to a patient’s rejection to strictly follow doctor’s order (Ali, 2015:7).

Ali (2015) explains that medical practitioners and patients’ background information is a key factor that affects their communication. Background information can include culture and perception of the medical practitioners and patients, patients’ background information about medical practitioners’ behaviour, patient’s health condition, irresponsibility of medical practitioners and patients, and the gender of medical practitioner and patient. The culture and perception has to do with information about the cultural lineage, descent or simply said tribal recognition, and the views about a particular tribe. It is well known that the culture of a community influences politeness or impoliteness.

A doctor who is of Ikwerre descent and speaks his or her language fluently may likely communicate more politely with an Ikwerre patient than an Ogoni patient. This may be due to his or her perception about the Ogonis. In the same vein, an Ogoni speaking nurse may interact more politely with an Ogoni patient than an Ikwerre patient owing from his or her view about Ikwerre people. Medical practitioners’ behaviour toward patients during consultation also affects, to a large extent, the relationship and cooperation between them. This may include medical practitioners’ choice of words, their attitude or reactions towards patients in mild or critical conditions, their voice tone and pitch when giving instructions on how and when to take treatment, and patients’ manner of response, etc.

In the Nigerian medical setting, issues and complaints pointing towards medical practitioners and patients’ linguistic and communicative incompetence is on the increase. Medical practitioners either satisfy or dissatisfy patients with the services they render, including the implied meanings in their verbal and non-verbal communication. Medical institutions ought to consider the need for positive communication in medical practitioners-patients relationship which enables medical practitioners to build positive attitude toward patients, and ultimately, patients will derive satisfaction from services they seek from health facilities. This study pragmatically analyzes the (im)politeness strategies medical practitioners employ during interaction with patients in the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH).

2. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

- i. to determine the verbal politeness strategies which medical practitioners and patients employ during interaction at UPTH
- ii. to examine the verbal impoliteness strategies medical practitioners and patients employ during interaction at UPTH

iii. to explore the use of honorific expressions in medical practitioner-patient interaction at UPTH

3. Significance of the Study

We hope that this research work will provide more insight into pragmatics especially in the area of linguistic politeness. This research will be useful to the medical profession as it will stir up consciousness of the use of polite communicative strategies between medical practitioners and patients in any situation for constructing and sustaining positive relationship to enable patients' maximum adherence to healthcare services. The study will equally be useful to language scholars and researchers particularly those with interest in pragmatic investigation of interaction in varied contexts.

4. Theoretical Background

4.1 Politeness Theory

The most prominent and influential work in the linguistic study of politeness is the theory Brown and Levinson proposed (1978, 1987). This theory has witnessed innumerable reactions, applications, criticisms, modifications, and revision. The names of Brown and Levinson is now almost synonymous with 'Politeness', as it is impossible to talk about it without referring to them. The theory focused mainly on how politeness deals with protecting interlocutors face. Brown and Levinson (1987) based their theory on Goffman's theory (1955, 1967), who was the first to introduce positive face and indicated its essence and necessity in social interaction. However, Brown and Levinson (1987), focused more apparently on the treatment of face. They emphasized two ways of portraying the concept of face. The first way dealt with face from a positive and negative point of view, while the second concentrated on the claim that positive and negative faces represent interlocutors' steady wants.

Brown and Levinson (1987) extended the idea of 'face' into politeness. They viewed politeness as a concept with two characteristics; Positive and Negative. 'Positive politeness' refers to what we can communicate to satisfy the needs of positive face while negative politeness, functions in two ways. First, it expressed the need to save an interlocutor's face negatively or positively, and second, it tried to fulfill the requirements of the negative face by way of showing respect to the addressee and bearing in mind that his rights must be respected. In this regard, interlocutors maintain their face by cooperating with each other in any social interaction as the need to maintain everyone's face relies on others. Accordingly, Brown and Levinson (1987) outlined five super-strategies of politeness, to act as a guide that controls everyday threats of face with respect to social norms which plays an important role in determining the strategy to utilize. The first super-strategy is associated with lowest face threat, and the last, with the most face threat; Bald-on-record politeness, Positive politeness, Negative Politeness, Off-record politeness, and Withhold FTA (Maximum Politeness).

4.2 Impoliteness Theory

Basing on Brown and Levinson's model of politeness strategy, Jonathan Culpeper, in 1996, presented a seminal article on impoliteness. He identified impoliteness as "the parasite of politeness" (Culpeper, 1996:8), and the politeness strategies are the opposite of impoliteness strategies. However, Mills (2005) posits that, "politeness and impoliteness are not polar opposites". The opposite here, according to Culpeper (1996) refers to its orientation to face. Impoliteness strategies attacks face which causes social disharmony but the reverse is the case in

politeness. Culpeper (1996:8) defined impoliteness as the use of strategies to attack an interlocutor's face and create social disruption. The social harmony draws from Grice's cooperative principle stating that the primary concern of communication is that the interaction needs to be cooperative (Grice, 1975). Culpeper (2008) laid emphasis on norms. He argues that norms are different and accordingly, thus, a behaviour which emanates from a special norm is politic and when such behavior is outside the norm, it becomes impolitic. Culpeper (1996) created five impoliteness super-strategies from Brown and Levinson's (1987) strategies. He asserts that, "instead of enhancing or supporting face, impoliteness super strategies are a means of attacking face" (Culpeper, 1996:356). Culpeper's impoliteness super-strategies are as follows: Bald-on-record impoliteness, Positive impoliteness, Negative Impoliteness, Sarcasm or mock politeness, and Withhold Politeness.

4.3 Face as a Concept

The term face is a central concept in studying linguistic politeness and impoliteness. This concept was originally introduced by Erving Goffman in the 1960s. Goffman acknowledged that this concept originated from Chinese culture. It is common in our daily interaction that we present a particular image of ourselves to others. The particular image we present refers to 'face' (Goffman, 1955). This term is similar in meaning to the one we use in everyday speech when we say 'losing facing, saving face, or being shamefaced'. Goffman (1967) uses the term 'face work' to refer to the behavior which involves presenting face to others, protecting our own face and respecting the faces of others. Goffman (1967) says our face is like a persona which we present in a conversation. It changes from situation to situation. For example, in one situation we might want to present the face of a good friend, while in another, we may want to appear to be an independent person. Brown and Levinson (1978), defined face as an individual's feeling of self-worth or self-image, reputation or good name that everyone has and expects everyone else to recognize. We can damage, maintain or enhance such self-image through interaction with others. While in Goffman's definition, the public element is the major factor in the construal of 'face', in Brown and Levinson's, the individual appears to be of crucial importance. Hence, this study adopts Brown and Levinson's approach to 'face'. Brown and Levinson (1987) divided the concept of 'face' into two interdependent parts, namely: 'Positive' and 'Negative' face, in explaining communicative norms by various scholars. These distinctions follow subsequently.

4.4 Positive Face

An individual's positive face is reflected in his desire for others to like, approve of, respect and appreciate him or her. The word 'positive' implies; favourable, desirable by others. Since the actions of others can sustain one's face wants, he or she has to co-operate with others in order to maintain positive face. Goffman (1967) defined positive face as "the want of every member that his wants be desirable to at least some others". Brown and Levinson (1987:62) saw positive face to include "the desire to be ratified, understood, approved, liked or admired". Hence, it is the desire of interlocutors. Schumacher (1972) explained that, "positive face is part of a background consciousness of co-interactants to react to the stimuli they share". He added that positive face is "the universal need for proximity and belonging or individualistic which is given symbolic recognition in interaction". For example, an individual could show the desire for others to like and respect him or her through the use of a positive face. Positive politeness strategies preserve positive face of the speaker and hearer.

4.5 Negative Face

An individual's negative face is reflected in his desire to have the freedom to act as one chooses. The word 'negative' means damaging, undesirable or unfavorable. It is an individual's desire for autonomy. Brown and Levinson (1987:62) defined negative face as "the want of every competent adult member that his actions be unimpeded by others". Schumacher (1972), in Rosina (2000:24) added that, "negative politeness strategies are used to cater for the negative face needs of the hearer". For example, a junior student could use negative face to show desire to be free from constraints and impositions from senior school mates. A person's negative face receives threats when he/she is told to do something, have an opinion regarding some issue or is spoken to in a manner that is threatening to the hearer's integrity. To this end, positive face and negative face couches on the need for individualistic and independence wants, respectively.

4.6 Face Threatening Acts (FTAs)

Brown and Levinson (1978) stated that, "FTAs are illocutionary acts liable to damage or threaten another person's face". In any social interaction, both positive face and negative face are subject to threats, even at the same time. Brown and Levinson (1987) confirmed that, "face is subject to threat when individuals participate in social interaction". These threats are usually known as Face Threatening Act (FTA), which can damage or threaten an individual's face. Any action that impinges to some degree upon a person's face, like orders, insults, and criticisms, is an FTA. People generally strive to avoid FTAs and are willing to incur cost in order to save face. The purpose of politeness, therefore, is to soften the FTA since it is in everyone's mutual interest to do so. If any rational speaker wants to avoid FTAs, he or she must use certain communicative strategies to mitigate the threat. Facework maintains or supports face by thwarting a potential threat to face. This can only be possible through redressive facework, since it involves the redress of an FTA. (Culpeper 2011:7).

Brown and Levinson (1987:65-68) created a distinction between FTAs that primarily threaten the hearer's face and those that primarily threaten the speaker's face. Among the former, include orders, requests, threats, criticism, contradictions, and the mention of taboo topics. The later includes expressing thanks, unwilling promises and offers, apologies, the breakdown of physical control over one's body, and confessionals. Facework, according to Goffman (1967:12), is made up of the actions by a person to make whatever he is doing consistent with face. Therefore, Brown and Levinson (1987:60) gave the assumption that, "it is of 'mutual interest' for co-interactants to co-operate by supporting each other's face". In general, people co-operate and assume each other's co-operation in maintaining face, such co-operation couches on the mutual vulnerability of face. A threat will lead to a counter-threat. Thus, the speaker has an absolute interest in maintaining the hearer's face, since this will enhance the probability of reciprocal facework (Culpeper, 2011:7).

4.7 Politeness in Honorifics

Honorific is a word derived from the Latin "honorificus", which means "showing honour". According to Brown and Levinson (1978:276), the term "honorific" is defined as "a grammatical encoding of relative social status between participants and persons or things referred to in a communicative event". Honorifics are in form of pronouns; your Excellency, my Lord, and titles; generic, kinship and occupational titles such as Mr., Mrs., uncle, sister, doctor, professor, etc. Honorifics are used to encode high status of the interlocutors. They are used to reveal the social

status of the speaker and the hearer in the verbal interaction including levels of respect and politeness. Generally, honorifics pertain to honour and respect. They serve as speech beautifiers. Levinson (1983:90), classified honorifics into two types: referential and absolute honorifics.

a. Referential honorifics are used to express the respect of the relations held between the speaker and the referent, that is, the things or persons referred to. For example, mother, father, elder brother, etc.

b. Absolute honorifics are used to convey information reserved for certain speakers and recipients such as Mr., Miss., Dr., Your Honour, Mr. President, etc. The essential function of honorifics is to communicate respect. The primary purpose of honorifics is to express politeness. Using honorifics in appropriate contextual factors will generate safe interaction. They are used according to the social norms of the society. Power, distance, formality, age and gender are all factors that influence the use of honorifics. Power can affect the intended meaning tied with the use of honorifics. Power and age are interlocked. Age determines who pays respect and to whom, like a nephew addressing his aunt by this title “aunt” instead of her first name as she is older than him. Formality depends on social context. The context of situation determines whether to use honorifics or not. Honorifics can serve such functions as giving respect, distance, formality, dignity, grace, and good manners.

5. Research Methodology

This paper adopted a descriptive qualitative design. The researcher conducted the study at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital. The choice of language was mainly not definite because of the hospital’s multilingual setting. Hence, the research population was the entire medical practitioners and patients in UPTH. This paper adopted purposive and convenience sampling techniques. Convenience sampling was administered because the samples were convenient sources of data for the researcher. The samples include: Accidents and Emergency, General Out-patient and Pediatric wards. Purposive sampling was administered on data selection after data collection and transcription process, fifteen data samples were selected. The researcher utilized digital audio recording device for recording medical practitioners-patients’ interaction, with a book and a pen as the instrument of data collection. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained ethical approval to collect data at UPTH. The study employed participant observation and secondary data collection methods: books, journals and internet sources. The researcher subjected the data to pragmatic analysis. Before data analysis, the recorded data had undergone orthographic transcription. Data analysis was done on the purposively selected data using Brown and Levinson's (1987) Politeness theory, Culpeper's (1996) Impoliteness theory.

6. Verbal Politeness Strategies in Medical Practitioners-Patients’ Interaction

Medical practitioners and patients’ interaction at UPTH is characterized by different politeness strategies. The politeness strategies identified in the data of the study are Bald-on-record, Positive politeness, Negative politeness and Off-record politeness. These have been analyzed below.

6.1 Bald-on-record Politeness Strategy

This strategy is employed in a direct, unambiguous and concise manner without redress to interlocutors’ face. Medical practitioners and patients use this strategy through direct questions and concise instructions. This is illustrated in the example below.

Example 1

- P: Doctor! Doctor! Please help me!
MP: What is the problem? (bald-on-record)
P: My daughter is dying.
MP: Go to the emergency ward now (bald-on-record)
P: Okay thank you ma

In the example above, the doctor used bald-on-record strategy to communicate in a clear, concise and unambiguous way to the patient by asking about the problem and giving a straightforward instruction. This strategy enabled the doctor to communicate with maximum efficiency without having to redress the face of the patient.

6.2 Positive Politeness Strategy

This strategy was identified in the opening, prescription and closing levels of interaction between medical practitioners and patients. It is used to redress the positive face want of the addressee. Positive politeness is shown through the following output strategies: intensifying interest to hearer, avoid disagreement, seek agreement, joke, optimism, exaggeration and giving reasons.

a. Intensifying Interest Strategy

This is a strategy used to intensify the interest of the hearer during interaction with the speaker, Medical practitioners and patients employ this strategy through the use of honorifics. This is illustrated below.

Example 2

- MP: Nne ! biala?
daughter 2SG come-PRF
'daughter have you come'
P: Eh! dede, ututu oma
INTJ brother morning good
'Yes! Brother good morning'

In the example above, the patient's interest was intensified when the clinical assistant used the honorific term in Igbo, 'nne' (daughter) to address her. The medical practitioner knew the medical background of the patient, which was why he used the Igbo honorific. The honorific is used to address young females in their youth. The patient responded by addressing the clinical assistant with the honorific term for males 'dede' (brother) which indicated due respect. The use of honorific terms intensified the interest of the patient to attend to the medical practitioner's face. This strategy is also shown in the example below.

Example 3

- MP: Mma, how are you doing?
P: Adi m nma
1SG be fine
'I am fine'

The term, 'mma' (mother) is a honorific addressed to elderly women. The already existing knowledge of the patient's background by the medical practitioner brought about the use of the Igbo honorific.

a. Seeking Agreement Strategy

This strategy is used when there is need to attempt, take an action, or make a request with due permission. Medical practitioners and patient use this strategy to seek or give consent to carry out an action. This is shown in the extract below.

Example 4

P: Doctor please can I be guarded; some people are after my life.

MP: Okay, you can.

The patient used this strategy to seek for doctor's agreement to bring his guards into the consultation room. Knowing quite well that it breaks the rule of confidentiality and privacy during consultation, the doctor gave consent to the patient's request. By this, the faces of both interlocutors have been saved because agreement was sought for and consent was given.

a. Joke Strategy

Medical practitioners and patients use this strategy to ease tension or make the other feel relaxed.

Example 5

MP: Your eye dey turn you when you dey waka?

P: Yes, and my back dey pain me

MP: So when the eyes turn you wetin you go do?
Shey you go go chop or buy coke drink?

P: (laughs) No be every time oh

Na so you dey do when eyes dey turn you too abi?

In the example above, the patient complained of dizziness and requested for medical advice. The nurse jokingly asked to know what he does when he has such experience. Instead of getting the patient's face threatened, it got the patient laughing. However, joke strategy can be misunderstood by the hearer and become a threat to the hearer's face. A misunderstood joke can make the hearer counter or confront the speaker's intention with questions or better still, silence. One good thing about jokes is that, when they are appropriately used and understood, is that they keep the conversation going.

b. Strategy of giving reason

This strategy involves the need to give reasons. Medical practitioners and patients can achieve positive politeness in their interactions through giving reasons for adhering to medications, rejecting or disallowing treatments. This is shown in the example below.

Example 6

P: The Astimin I take makes me eat too much.

MP: Yes, I know. The Astimin you drink is quite okay. It helps you gain weight (reason)

In the example above, the patient complained that the drug increases his appetite to eat. Inferably, the patient needed a change of medication. The doctor gave him reason for taking that particular drug by assuring that the drug would help the patient gain more weight. The doctor's reason for taking the drug has redressed the positive face want of the patient.

b. Cooperation strategy

This strategy has to do with mutual cooperation between medical practitioners and patients. Their interaction revealed that they employed cooperative strategy through the use of the inclusive second person personal and possessive pronouns, 'we' and 'us'. In the real sense, what the doctor really meant was 'you' or 'me'. This is exemplified below.

Example 7

MP: Okay, 'let's' see how far you can go

P: Okay

MP: So 'we' start with respiratory check.
Breathe in, breathe out.

P: Hmm...

MP: Do you feel any restriction?

he doctor requested that the asthmatic patient should perform a breathing exercise with him. He used the inclusive pronouns, 'us' and 'we' to politely get the patient involved in the exercise. The use of this strategy prevented the possibility of an imposition or order which could be a threat to the patient's face.

6.3 Negative Politeness Strategy

Negative politeness strategy is directed towards the hearer's negative face. It is mainly used if there is a minor risk to hurt the hearer's face. Acts that can likely threaten a hearer's negative face are orders, advice, warnings, etc., (Brown & Levinson, 1987). Negative politeness output strategies revealed in the data include: stating the FTA as a general rule, apologizing, minimizing threats, being conventionally indirect and hedging.

a. Minimizing Threat Strategy

This strategy involves interacting in such a way that the threat from such interaction would be minimized. In the example below, the doctor made enquiry from the patient to find out if he had the habit of not sleeping under a mosquito net and drinking untreated water, since the doctor discovered that the patient may be down with malaria and typhoid fever.

Example 8

P: These symptoms are really weighing me down.

MP: how do you enjoy sleep without a mosquito net?

P: I use mosquito nets but not all the time

MP: you drink tap water from your compound, right? e no dey scratch you for throat?

P: no be like say I just want to dey drink am doctor.

MP: you need to stop to dey drink untreated water and always sleep under net.

In the example above, the doctor perceived that the patient had the habit of not sleeping under a mosquito net and drinking untreated water. The doctor asked to know how the patient felt sleeping without a mosquito net while being exposed to malaria and typhoid fever. The doctor advised the patient not to drink untreated water and to always sleep under a mosquito net. The doctor minimized the threat with a question that would not cause harm. The doctor's question redressed the patients' negative face want.

b. Stating FTA as a general rule

Negative politeness was also realized through stating the FTA as a general rule in the data. The hospital's management, through the Ministry of Health, gave a rule stating that everyone within the premises of the hospital must always wear a facemask. This is demonstrated below.

Example 9

P: Good morning doctor

MP: Please, use your face mask

P: Okay, I forgot

MP: This is the last time I'll talk about this. Facemask is compulsory for very consultation.

The doctor observed that patients no longer comply with the health directive. He stated 'No facemask, No entry' as a general rule before any consultation. By stating the FTA as a general rule and not just for a particular patient, the doctor redressed the negative face want of the patient. The patient's response signified an acceptance of the rule.

c. Strategy of Apology

Apologizing is another strategy for redressing negative face want of interlocutors. In medical practitioners and patients' interaction, apologies have been observed to reduce the damage on the negative face want of both parties. Saying 'sorry' can bring this to effect. This is shown below.

Example 10

MP: You should have arranged those test results before coming here.

P: I'm sorry ma (hurries up to arrange the test results)

MP: Alright, let me see them?

The doctor was displeased by the patients' irresponsibility in putting her test results in the right order. The doctor expressed her feeling to the patient and the patient responded with an apology (I'm sorry). The doctor's utterance before the redress could have had a threat on the patient's face but the patient admitted her fault and apologized for being negligent of her duty as a patient. Her apology redressed the negative face want of the doctor.

d. Indirect Strategy

Being conventionally indirect is usually observed in medical practitioners and patients' interaction. It involves the use of phrases and sentences that have contextually ambiguous meanings which are different from their literal meaning. This is illustrated in the following example.

Example 11

P: I feel movements in my leg

MP: Both legs?

P: Yes

MP: Can you please show me your legs?

The patient presented the problem to the doctor telling him that she experienced some kind of movement in her leg. The doctor asked if the movement was in both legs and the patient affirmed positively. To examine the patient, the doctor indirectly requested to see her legs. The doctor's

use of ‘can’, as an indirect request, showed that it was not a direct question about the patient’s capability, but a polite request. This way, a threat to the patient’s face has been avoided.

e. Hedging strategy

Hedges are words or phrases that make an utterance less forceful or assertive. Medical practitioners and patients used this strategy in making a strong opinion come out in a polite and professional manner. Hedges qualify, soften, or make assertions meant to be impolite, politer. This has been demonstrated below.

Example 12

MP: Have you bought the medicine?

P: That thing cost oh, e never reach two weeks sef.

MP: Well, to a certain degree, I thought that you knew how serious your child’s case is.

P: I know.

In the example above, a woman brought her child who is sickle cell for routine check-up. The doctor asked the woman if she has bought her child’s drugs but she tried to avoid giving a direct answer to the doctor’s question. The doctor used the hedge phrase, ‘to a certain degree’, to partly indicate that her conviction that the woman knew how serious her child’s health condition was, was not entirely true. The doctor’s utterance in line 3 would have been plainly impolite, but the presence of the hedged phrase made it seem vague and polite.

6.4 Off-record politeness strategy

Off-record utterances are those that are not directly addressed to the hearer. Brown & Levinson (1987) assert that, “you do so in a way that says that you cannot be held accountable”. Some strategies for performing off-record are to give hints, use metaphors, being ambiguous or vague, etc. An example of medical practitioners and patients’ use of off-record in their conversation is given below.

Example 13

P: I have been sitting outside waiting for my turn since but I was the second person who came here today. What kind of stress is this? All these nurses should better be careful.

MP: Okay, please sit down. Try drinking a lot of water before coming to the hospital next time. It is very necessary.

P: Okay, but how will water solve the problem?

In the example above, the patient complained of being on the queue for a long time when he actually came so early. The expression of his dissatisfaction made the doctor use ambiguous statement to address the patient. In the real sense, what the doctor meant was that the patient should not come to the hospital reacting in such way next time. Knowing that it would be impolite if he made the statement plain, the doctor tried to protect the patient’s face so that he won’t be held accountable for his statement. The patient’s response showed that the intended meaning was not gotten. Consequently, the FTA was performed in a way that one cannot hold the speaker accountable for what he has said.

7. Verbal Impoliteness Strategies in Medical Practitioners-Patients’ Interaction

Medical practitioners and patients’ interaction can exhibit several impoliteness strategies. The common impoliteness strategies realized in the data of the study based on Culpeper’s

impoliteness theory are Positive impoliteness, Negative impoliteness, Mock or Sarcasm politeness and Withhold politeness. These have been analyzed below.

7.1 Positive Impoliteness Strategy

This strategy is used by a speaker to damage an addressee positive face wants. A positive face want is a person's will or need to be part of a certain action, or be approved of (Culpeper, 1996). Positive face can be damaged through the following output strategies of positive impoliteness shown in the following data.

a. Strategy of Snubbing and Ignoring

A speaker can damage the positive face wants of the hearer by ignoring, snubbing or failing to acknowledge his or her needs or presence. Medical practitioners and patients used this strategy during the interaction presented below.

Example 14

MP: What is the problem? You are saying you want to urinate.

P: Madam answer me abeg, I want to urinate.

MP: E be like say you neva ready. You come hospital with bad mouth.

'It seems like you're not ready. You came to the hospital with a foul mouth'.

The patient came into the hospital with swollen legs and the nurse recognized that the patient was critically ill. She demanded to know the background of patient's ailment at that time, but her patient needed to ease herself. Her patient requested to use the rest room but the nurse ignored the request of her patient. The nurse's request to know the problem's background was declined by the patient, and the patient's will to be granted access to the restroom was disregarded. Hence, the negative face of the nurse and the patient was damaged by both parties.

b. Exclusion Strategy

This strategy is employed by a speaker whenever there is an intention to exclude another hearer or a third party from any activity. It is interesting to note that medical practitioners engaged this strategy in the consultation room, especially for cases that needed privacy. This is shown below.

Example 15

P: Good morning

MP: Morning. Sit down. What's your complaint?

P: I feel movements in my leg.

MP: Who is this person with you?

P: My friend.

MP: Please excuse us. You can wait outside.

In the data above, the interaction started well with exchange of pleasantries and presentation of the problem. Though, when the doctor noticed that there was a third person in the consulting room, she employed the exclusion strategy to let the person know that her presence was not needed during the consultation. The third party was ordered to wait outside. The doctor's intent to be impolite was not genuine, yet, the hearer's positive face to support her friend was impinged.

c. Seeking Disagreement Strategy

This strategy was revealed when medical practitioners blamed patients for their ailment. The use of this strategy resulted to defensive statements from patients. From the extract below, it happened that the patient who had been on a routine drug stopped adhering to her medication and stopped attending medical appointments. The data below illustrates this.

Example 16

MP: Madam, when last did you come for your refill?

P: It's been long, I can't remember.

MP: Why is that so? You have not been on your medication for months.

P: It's not like that doctor. I have not been feeling well to come.

MP: Like seriously? What are all these rashes on your body?

You are having treatment failure and showing symptoms yet you choose not to come for medical appointment and now you say it's not like that.

P: Yes ma.

In the example, the doctor blamed the patient for not keeping to medical appointments and the patient responded defensively. Having presented the health problem and its background, the patient admitted that she had her medical appointment a long time ago. The doctor, who was already irritated, blamed the patient for not taking responsibility for her life. The defensive comment of the patient impinged on the doctor's positive face who wanted the patient to admit to her fault. However, it was the doctor's blame that led to the patient's defensive statement.

d. Strategy of disassociating from the other

This strategy is engaged when a speaker intends to deny association or common grounds with the hearer. This is can be done through avoiding close contact with each other. This is demonstrated below.

Example 17

MP: You are not doing yourself any good this woman, because you have not said the truth.

P: But I wanted to...

MP: Please, go back to the centre you came from... I don't like the way you are.

The doctor declined attending to the patient because she had complications in her health from not judiciously taking her medications and her absence during medical appointments. The doctor ordered the patient to go back to the health centre she came from, though she knew that the patient came from no health centre. The doctor avoided contact or common ground with the patient because of complications she was having. This showed that the doctor's action impinged on the positive face of the patient. Hence, the doctor was impolite during the interaction.

7.2 Negative Impoliteness Strategy

These strategies attack an addressee's negative face want. This was revealed through frightening and diminutives.

a. **Frighten Strategy**

This strategy was employed to create fear or tension intentionally or unintentionally. It was used by medical practitioner and patient to attack the negative face of the addressee. It can be intentional when the aim for delivering information, as regards to a patient's negative health condition, is to induce fear or tension in the patient. However, it is unintentional when the information is delivered only for informative purposes. This is illustrated below:

Example 18

MP: Chai! You are having serious anemia, why?

P: I don't understand.

MP: It is lack of blood. Are you sickle cell?

P: yes ma.

In the example, the doctor presented the information on the health condition of the patient with an exclamation marker 'chai!', but the message was meant to be plainly informative. The effect it would have on the patient was not considered by the doctor. The exclamation marker made the message seem to be serious. The message got the patient frightened. This indicates that the exclamation in the doctor's utterance raised an attack on the negative face wants of the patient and in the perception of the doctor's utterance.

b. **Strategy of using diminutives**

Diminutives are words used by a speaker to express smallness or to belittle a hearer. It is usually used when one person has more power over the other. Medical practitioners scarcely used diminutives during interaction with patients.

Example 19

MP: What do you think caused it?

P: I think it's because I use loud earphones.

MP: What do you mean? How can that be the cause? You are not saying the truth.

P: it's the truth ma.

MP: Look at this small pikin? Do you think I'm a child? Leave my office! When you are ready to talk, you tell me.

The patient complained of having ear pus and the doctor tried to know the background of the problem. The reason for the patient's ailment was not accepted by the doctor. However, the diminutive expression 'small pikin' showed how the doctor belittled the patient due to power and age differentials. The doctor imposed her findings of the cause of the problem on the patient who did not seem to accept the doctor's report. This indicated that the patient's negative face was threatened by the doctor's use of the diminutive expression.

7.3 Mock Politeness Strategy

Mock politeness is a strategy that uses surface politeness which is usually interpreted in an impolite way. It is regarded impolite if the polite strategy used is recognized impolite out of jokes can be taken as polite but the context can change the intent to make the hearer laugh. It is designed to protect the speaker's own face.

Example 20

MP: Are you a student?

P: yes ma.

MP: Oh! I believe you should have read around your ailment?

P: Not really.

The patient presented the background of her health problem to the doctor. The doctor asked the patient if she was a student because she was referred to the hospital from the University clinic. For being a student studying a medical related course in the University, the doctor expected her to know the cause of her ailment. The patient perceived the doctor's response as sarcastic because of the tone the doctor used in saying it. The face of the doctor is protected but the face of the patient is not.

7.4 Withhold Politeness

This strategy has to do with the absence of expected politeness behaviour in a certain situation. Welcoming, greeting and thanking are politeness behaviours that are not expected to be omitted in any conversation. Examples of this strategy used during the initiation of medical practitioner and patient interaction in UPTH are shown below.

Example 21

P: Doctor, please can I be guarded. Some people are after my life.

MP: Okay. What is the complaint?

Example 22

MP: Please use your facemask sir

P: you said?

MP: Okay, what's your complaint?

The examples above illustrate that medical practitioners and patients omitted a necessary part of their interaction which is greeting and welcoming. In example (21), the patient walked into the consulting room without greeting the doctor. This was because all he was thinking of was how he could be protected or guarded from attackers. In example (22), the medical practitioner started the conversation by stating a general rule of wearing a face mask before asking about the patient's complaint. The omission of greetings and welcoming showed that medical practitioner and patient withheld the standard politeness behaviour expected before consultation begins and after it ends.

8. Honorific Expressions Used during Medical Practitioner-Patients Interaction

A careful study of the data revealed that honorific expressions were used in the three languages used in this analysis; English, Igbo and Nigerian pidgin. These honorific terms are not strictly subject to Levinson (1983) classification of honorifics and they have been analyzed base on factors that influence their adoption.

a. Doctor

Example 23

P: Doctor good morning

MP: Good morning and welcome. Any complaint?

'Doctor' is an English honorific term used to address certified male or female medical practitioners in the consulting room. It is an occupational honorific title for individuals in the

medical practice. Based on societal norms, patients must address this kind of medical practitioners accordingly. This is influenced by professional power and formality factors. The use of this honorific term during medical interaction is a good start towards having a polite conversation as observed in the data above.

b. Nurse

Example 24

P: Nurse! Please help me

MP: What is wrong with her? Madam, what is the problem?

‘Nurse’ is an English honorific term addressed to certified male or female medical practitioners who primarily take care of patients outside the consulting room. For politeness sake, these medical practitioners must be addressed not by their personal names as seen on their name tags but by their professional title as nurses. The factors of professional power and formality also influence the use of this honorific term. In the data above, the patient addressed the medical practitioner as a nurse, and it made the nurse to respond adequately and accordingly.

c. Sir

Example 25

MP: Please use your facemask sir

P: Okay.

‘Sir’ is a generic honorific term used to address male patients and medical practitioners during medical interactions. Most times, this honorific term is used when there could be a risk to a patient’s negative face, if he is addressed by his personal name. In the data, the medical practitioner addressed the male patient as ‘sir’, this was influenced by age and gender of the patient. Also, to keep the conversation formal, both parties employ this honorific. However, a young male patient may not be addressed as ‘sir’ due to the age difference between the medical practitioner and the patient.

d. Ma/Madam

Example 26

P: Good morning ma

MP: Morning madam, you are having serious anemia, why?

P: I don’t understand ma.

‘Ma/Madam’ is a generic honorific term addressed to female medical practitioners and patients during medical interaction. A risk to the negative face of any of the parties is reduced when the honorific is utilized, rather than their personal names. This is influenced by the factors of age, gender, professional power and formality.

e. Dede

Example 27

MP: Nne I biala?

P: Eh! Dede ututu oma

‘Dede’ is a kinship honorific term which means ‘an elderly male or brother, according to the tradition of the Igbo people. It is used to express respect to males who are older than the other party involved in the interaction. In the data, the patient addressed the medical practitioner as her elder brother. This kind of honorific term is influenced by age and gender factors.

e. Mama/Nne

Example 28

MP: Mama go well

P: Thank you nwa m.

‘Mama/Nne’ is a kinship honorific term which means ‘mother’. The Igbo tradition requires that one calls the mother ‘nne’ or ‘mama’. It is an informal honorific that conveys respect to elderly females in the society. The data in examples 30 and 31 show that the medical practitioners addressed the patients as ‘nne’ and “mama”, during the starting and the closing of their conversation respectively. The use of this honorific as a polite address also extends to other older women who are old enough to be one’s mother. However, ‘nne’ can be addressed to a young lady. It is influenced by age and gender factors.

g. Nwam

‘Nwam’ is another kinship honorific which means ‘my child’. This honorific was used by the patient to address the medical practitioner who is younger than the patient after consultation, as seen in example 31 above. It is influenced by factors of age alone. The use of this honorific made the conversation closing more politic.

h. Oga

Example 29

MP: Oga, your eye dey turn you when you dey waka?

P: Yes, and my back dey pain me.

‘Oga’ is an honorific term which means “boss”. It is used in almost everyday’s conversation in Nigerian pidgin. ‘Oga’ is used to address someone who is of a higher status or age than another. In the example above, the medical practitioner addressed the aged patient as ‘oga’ to show respect and politeness. Its use is influenced by factors of age, power and formality.

8. Summary of Findings

The data analysis has provided varying range of results. Considering the verbal politeness and impoliteness strategies in medical practitioner-patient interaction, we observed that politeness strategies occurred relatively more often than impoliteness. The verbal politeness strategies identified in medical practitioner-patient interaction at UPTH are cooperation strategy, seeking agreement, intensifying interest to the addressee, giving reason, stating the FTA as a general rule, hedging, joking, apology and minimizing threat. However, the verbal impoliteness strategies identified in medical practitioner-patient interaction at UPTH are snubbing and ignoring strategies, exclusion, seeking disagreement, disassociation from the other, frightening, diminutives, mock and withhold politeness. Cooperation strategy was applied by medical practitioners and patients through greetings, honorifics and salutation. When one party proposed greeting, the other party accepted the greeting through a verbal response. Greetings and positive responses are positive politeness forms used in redressing an addressee’s positive face want (Brown and Levinson, 1987). Medical practitioners and patients initiated this politeness form once they come in contact. In English language, greetings were done by the use of the conventional ‘good morning’ and ‘good afternoon’ depending on the time one arrives at the hospital. In other languages like Igbo, greetings and their responses are based on cultural norms and are determined by age difference.

We established that the use of relevant honorifics showed certain positive social relations among the interlocutors. An honorific term must of necessity show that the person, to whom it is addressed to, is respected. During medical practitioners and patients' conversation in UPTH, honorifics were used through nominalization, especially nominals that show kinship relationship. For instance, *nne* 'mother', *dede* 'elderly brother', *mama* 'mother', *nwam* 'my child'. These were used appropriately by the interlocutors to intensify the interest of both parties. Seeking agreement was applied by the patient to seek permission to carry out an action. The patient used this strategy when he wanted to bring in his guards into the consulting room. The consultation was meant to be for just the medical practitioner and patient, no third party was allowed. The patient sought for the doctor's agreement before bringing his guards in. This was done to achieve mutual respect among the interlocutors and to enhance politeness throughout the conversation.

Joke strategy was utilized by the medical practitioner when there was a need to ease tension. This enabled the patient to open up on the background of his health problem. The medical practitioner's joke was meant to make the patient laugh. Minimizing threat strategy was applied by the medical practitioner who tried not to blame the patient for the cause of his health condition. Instead of blaming the patient, medical practitioner advised the patient from drinking unclean water and urged the patient to sleep under a mosquito net. The threat of hurting the patient through blaming was averted through this strategy. This was applied to save hearer's negative face want. Apology strategy was applied by the patient who said 'I'm sorry'. The patient had failed to do what she was supposed to do before entering into the consulting room. The doctor perceived it as irresponsibility by the patient. The patient accepted her fault and apologized. The use of apology was necessary for the conversation to go smoothly. This was used to save hearer's negative face want. In most cases, politeness strategies were used by patients than medical practitioners.

We observed that medical practitioners and patients in UPTH also used impolite strategies in different occasions. The verbal impoliteness forms were used to damage the addressee's face wants. Some were used by medical practitioners while others were used by patients. Impoliteness was applied intentionally and unintentionally, but in any case, it is not accepted. Thus, impoliteness is successful when the speaker intends to damage the hearer's face. Unintentionally, the speaker may not intend to damage the hearer's face but the hearer can still find his or her face threatened.

Snubbing and Ignoring was employed through unconcern or failure to acknowledge the pressing need or want of any interlocutor. In the data, the patient needed to use the restroom urgently but the medical practitioner was only interested in knowing the health problem of the patient. This was made obvious by the negative response of the medical practitioner who cared less about the patient's need. Exclusion strategy was utilized unintentionally by the medical practitioner. In the data, the patient entered the private consulting room with a third party (a friend) without taking permission from the medical practitioner. The medical practitioner perceived this as an invasion of privacy and confidentiality. The medical practitioner ordered the third party to leave the office. The patient and the third party perceived the reaction of the medical practitioner as impolite. The exclusion strategy was used directly to the third party without redress.

Seeking disagreement was employed through blaming from the medical practitioner and defensive responses by the patient. Thus, both the medical practitioner and patient employed

impoliteness in their conversation. The medical practitioner blamed the patient for the complications she was having. The patient was blamed because she had not been attending medical checkups and appointments. This impoliteness strategy was employed unintentionally by the medical practitioner but intentionally by the patient who used the defensive comment to respond to the medical practitioner. The strategy of disassociating from the other was applied intentionally when medical practitioners reject patients and avoid close contact with patients. This was employed by the medical practitioner when the patient denied that she has been on her drugs judiciously but the medical practitioner complained that she was showing severe complications. The medical practitioner declined her and ordered her to go back to the health centre she claimed she had been attending.

Frightening strategy was employed unintentionally by the medical practitioner in the course of delivering information about patient's health condition. The information frightened the patient. The conversation started with an exclamation marker. Although, it did not perform the specific purpose it had to. Withhold politeness strategy involves an absence of expected verbal politeness behaviour. Politeness is preferred in maintaining positive social relationship but when it is left out, it is considered impolite (Culpeper, 1996). Absence of greeting, thanking, welcoming, farewell, in medical practitioner interaction is impoliteness. Thus, in the absence of expectations of politeness forms during interaction, it is possible that there is always an attack on face.

We also established that honorific expressions used by medical practitioners and patients in UPTH are occupational, generic and kinship honorifics. The occupational honorifics are Doctor and Nurse. Generic honorifics are Sir, Ma/Madam, Oga 'boss'. Kinship honorifics are Dede 'elder brother', Mama/Nne 'mother', Nwa m 'my child'. These expressions made interaction more polite. We also noted that the use of occupational honorifics are influenced by power and formality factors, generic honorifics are influenced by power, formality, gender, and age factors, and kinship honorifics are influenced by age and gender factors. However, these factors do not hinder its positive effect on interactions.

9. Conclusion

This study has undertaken a pragmatic analysis of (im) politeness in medical practitioner-patients' interaction. It is expedient that every social interaction must be politic. Face is like a fragile mask that should be handled with care especially by medical practitioners and their patients. A threat to the face of any participant will yield impolite reactions that would not make human interaction go smoothly. Politeness strategies have a very low tendency of damaging face. Whereas impoliteness strategies encourage face damage, honorific expressions have the capacity to beautify interaction because they promote respect and politeness between medical practitioners and patients. In line with the findings in the analysis, medical practitioners should consider the importance and use of more politeness strategies in their interactions with patients. Also, the use of impoliteness strategies should be discouraged, be it intentionally or unintentionally, throughout interaction between medical practitioners and patients. More use of honorific expressions should be encouraged to foster politic relations between medical practitioners and patients.

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